

D6.3 Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities

Deliverable 6.3

Grant Agreement n°. 101084234

**Funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	01/06/2023	First draft	CE
0.2	09/06/2023	Draft reviewed by consortium members	Anastasia Oprea, Annie Roos
0.3	26/06/2023	Draft reviewed by Project Coordinators	Maura Farrell and Louise Weir
1	29/06/2023	Final version of V1	Víctor Ricardo Martínez, Elena Herrera, Michelle Perello, Beatrice Avagnina, Marlene Santacruz
1.1	29/05/2024	Update on D6.1 to D6.2 of a living document	Víctor R. Martínez
1.2	31/05/2024	Second Draft	Víctor R. Martínez, Michelle Perello, Beatrice Avagnina, Patrizio Ricci
1.3	19/06/2024	Draft reviewed by consortium members	Annie Roos, Duncan Crowley
1.4	27/06/2024	Draft reviewed by Project Coordinators	Maura Farrell and Louise Weir
2	28/06/2024	Final version of V2	Víctor R. Martínez, Michelle Perello, Beatrice Avagnina, Patrizio Ricci
2.1	30/06/2025	Exploitation Assessment	Víctor R. Martínez, Annie Roos, Silvia Sivini, Anastasia Oprea, Gerdy Verschuure-Stuip, Willem Korthals Altes, Maura Farrell, Louise Weir, Aisling Murtagh, Belyta Tembo, Tuomas Kuhmonen
2.2	10/10/2025	Exploitation Plan per Partners	Aisling Murtagh (Galway), Víctor R. Martínez (CE), Helene Ahl (HLK), Belyta Tembo (UTU), Annie Roos (LNU), Sara Mikolič (UL), Anastasia Oprea (ECOLISE), Willem Korthals Altes (TU Delft), Felicia van Tulder (HNEE), Antonín Vaishar (MENDELU).
2.3	20/11/2025	Update on D6.2 to D6.3 of a living document	Víctor R. Martínez, Rosa Caprioli, Ómar González, Silvia Pérez Palomo, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello
2.4	10/12/2025	Draft reviewed by consortium members	Annie, Roos, Silvia Sivini, Anastasia Oprea, Helene Ahl, Willem Korthals Altes
2.5	18/12/2025	Draft reviewed by Project Coordinators	Maura Farrell, Louise Weir, Aisling Murtagh
3	19/12/2025	Final version	Víctor R. Martínez

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	FLIARA
Project Title	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01-01
Project Start Date	01/01/2023
Project Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP6 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Deliverable	D6.3 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities – Final
Due Date	31/12/2025
Submission Date	22/12/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	Consulta Europa
Version	Final
Status	Final version of a living document
Author(s)	Victor R. Martínez CE
Contributors	Annie Roos, Silvia Sivini, Anastasia Oprea, Gerdy Verschuure-Stuip, Willem Korthals Altes, Maura Galway, LNU, Farrell, Louise Weir, Aisling Murtagh, Belyta Tembo, UNICAL, Tuomas Kuhmonen, Rosa Caprioli, Ómar González, ECOLISE, TU Silvia Pérez Palomo, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Delft, UTU, CE Perello
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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

PC	Project Coordinator
CD&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
WP	Work Package
Project partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG
UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POURLE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable (D6.3) constitutes the final version of the FLIARA Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation, including communication activities, and reports on the implementation of Work Package 6 (WP6) over the full duration of the project. It builds on the strategic framework, target groups, tools and guidelines initially established in Deliverable 6.1 and subsequently updated in Deliverable 6.2, which were delivered at M6 and M18 of the project, respectively, and set out the planned communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

While D6.1 and D6.2 primarily focused on defining the overall approach and specifying the activities to be undertaken, tools developed and reported progress under WP6, D6.3 adopts a summative perspective and documents the activities carried out and the results achieved. In doing so, this deliverable provides a comprehensive account of the extent to which the original communication, dissemination and exploitation objectives have been met and how activities conducted in other work packages have been translated into concrete outreach and impact.

More specifically, the report covers the period from M3 to M36 and presents evidence on the implementation of the following tasks: T6.1, which provided the overarching communication, dissemination and exploitation framework underpinning all subsequent activities; T6.2, Women led Innovation in Rural Areas Visibility Campaign; T6.3, Creating Synergies with Existing Initiatives and Relevant EU funded Projects; T6.4, Dissemination of Knowledge and Results; and T6.5, Exploitation Strategy, which encompasses the final exploitation plan. For each of these tasks, the deliverable outlines the main actions undertaken, the tools and channels employed, and the quantitative and qualitative outputs and outcomes generated, thereby offering a consolidated overview of FLIARA's external visibility, stakeholder engagement, and potential exploitation at the end of the project.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D6.3 “Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities – Final” presents the closing version of the FLIARA Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan and reports on the implementation of WP6 over the full duration of the project (M3–M36). It builds on the strategic framework, target audiences, tools and guidelines originally defined in D6.1 and updated in D6.2 and shifts the focus from planning and interim monitoring to documenting the concrete activities carried out, the audiences reached, and the impacts generated.

The deliverable has three main objectives. First, it provides a comprehensive overview of FLIARA’s external communication and visibility efforts, including the visibility campaign, visual identity, social media strategy, website, newsletters, media coverage and participation in events. Second, it summarises the dissemination of research and practice-oriented outputs – such as scientific publications, practice abstracts, fact sheets, policy briefs, videos, podcasts and webinars – and explains how these have been made accessible through the project website and open-access repositories (CORDIS, Zenodo, EU FarmBook, University of Galway Research Repository). Third, it presents the final exploitation strategy (T6.5), identifying FLIARA’s key exploitable results, mapping target user groups, and outlining how partners and stakeholders intend to sustain and scale the project’s legacy beyond its formal end.

The structure of the report mirrors these aims. Following the Executive Summary, Section 2 evaluates communication and dissemination activities against the KPIs defined in D6.1 and D6.2, showing that the project has met or exceeded its original quantitative targets. Section 3 describes the main communication components, including the visibility campaign, visual identity, website, social media and newsletters, while Section 4 addresses dissemination and exploitation, covering synergies with other initiatives, the web-based results architecture (innovators, ambassadors, practice abstracts, policy briefs, toolkit), open-access platforms, scientific publications and the exploitation plan. Section 5 summarises key lessons learned and highlights the contribution of WP6 to enhancing the visibility, recognition and uptake of women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas.

2. EVALUATION OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

2.1 KPI ANALYSIS

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for communication, dissemination and exploitation were initially defined in D6.1 and subsequently refined in D6.2, reflecting the living nature of the FLIARA communication and exploitation plan. The present final version (D6.3) reports on the implementation of Tasks 6.1 to 6.5 in WP6 and provides an overall assessment of performance against these KPIs over the full project duration. As summarised in the table below, the project has not only met but, in most cases, substantially exceeded the original quantitative targets for key communication and dissemination outputs, including participation in events (**68 events against a target of 6**), attendance at the final conference (**107 in-person and 229 online versus a target of 80**), newsletters (**6 issues as planned, with 1.482 subscribers and 781 readers per issue**, far above the initial expectations), earned media (**167 pieces against a target of at least 20 press releases**), website performance (**44.665 site visits compared to the target of 10.000 and 21.596 active users**), and social media growth (**3.993 followers against a target of 2.000**).

Scientific and non-scientific outputs have likewise surpassed the planned values, with four peer-reviewed publications (target: at least three), **32 non-scientific articles, 200 fact sheets, 25 practice abstracts, 20 videos, 10 podcasts and 5 webinars produced**, alongside **4 Community of Practice networking events, 1 gender-specific guide to innovation**, multiple targeted communication campaigns, a full suite of printed dissemination materials, and at least **5** structured synergies with other EU projects. Taken together, this performance demonstrates a strong level of engagement with academic, policy and civil society audiences and indicates that the visibility and exploitation potential of FLIARA's results have exceeded the initial expectations set at the outset of the project.

Action	Indicator	Target	Achieved
Events	Participation in national/EU events International conference N° of attendants to the international conference	Participation to 6 events 1 international conference in Brussels 80 attendants	68 events 1 conference achieved 107 participants in-person and 229 online
Newsletter	Production of newsletter Subscribers Readers reached per issue	6 newsletters 500 subscribers 150 readers per issue	6 newsletters 1482 confirmed subscribers 781 readers
Press releases	N° of press releases	At least 20 published in total	168 Published on the website 167 earned media in external platforms
Project website	Site visits	10.000 total site visits	44.665 achieved
Publications	N° of Scientific Publications	At least 3	4
Non-scientific publications	N° of publications	At least 15	32 blog articles
Factsheets	N° of factsheets	At least 200	200 fact sheets published
Submission of abstracts	N° of abstracts	At least 14	25 practice abstracts
Social media	Followers (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook, Instagram)	2.000 followers in total	3.993
Videos	N° of videos produced	At least 20 (video blogs and videos of women-led innovations)	20 videos produced detailed under D6.5
Podcasts	N° of podcast produced	At least 10	10 podcasts produced detailed under D6.5
Webinars	N° of webinars	At least 1 for civil society organisations At least 1 for researchers At least 2 for policy makers	5 webinars produced
Community of Practice Networking Events	N° of events	At least 4	4 detailed under D4.2
Gender Specific Guide to Innovation	N° of guides	At least 1	1 detailed under D4.5

Communication campaigns	N° of communication campaigns	At least the 5 defined communication campaigns	1 awareness raising campaign 1 Innovations campaign 1 toolkit campaign 1 final conference campaign 1 visibility campaign
Dissemination material	N° of prints	At least 1 roll up, 1 leaflet, 1 poster, 1 template for word and 1 for ppt	All designed (D6.1) and printed
Project website	N° of visits throughout the project	Developed and maintained throughout the project	21.596 active users
Synergies with other projects	N° of Synergies with other projects	At least 5	10 D&C Collaborations

Table 1. KPIs Communication and Dissemination Activities

3. COMMUNICATION

This section outlines the communication strategy adopted by the FLIARA project, detailing the approaches and tools used to build visibility, engage diverse stakeholders, and ensure message coherence across all channels. It presents the development and implementation of the project’s visual identity, website, social media, newsletters, and key campaigns, illustrating how these elements have contributed to raising awareness and supporting project objectives.

3.1 VISIBILITY CAMPAIGN

One of the core components of FLIARA has been the visibility campaign, designed to spotlight the role of women in farming and rural areas across Europe. Using an inbound communication approach, CE has systematically adapted and repackaged project outputs into accessible, visually engaging formats that can drive change, support uptake and reach key stakeholders, while closely supporting WP4’s CoP activities and ensuring that women remain at the forefront of all materials produced. The visibility campaign has been integrated all across the FLIARA channels and printed materials with the objective of promoting and attracting users, build community and facilitate conveying the project progress.

Figure 1. Inbound communication approach

The visibility campaign has been integrated across project activities. In-person visibility was strengthened through the CoP networking events (WP4), while online visibility was enhanced through the development of new sections on the project website, the inclusion of ambassadors in dedicated features and the creation of the innovations section and social media channels. In all major dissemination materials – including practice abstracts, fact sheets, guides, policy briefs and other communication and dissemination outputs – the 200 women innovators and the 20 Ambassadors have been visually represented, ensuring that the campaign consistently highlights women’s contributions to agriculture and rural areas.

Overall, presentations delivered by partners across Europe have been underpinned by the key visual and communication materials developed under the visibility campaign, reinforcing a coherent narrative on women-led innovation in rural contexts.

Figure 2. Visibility Campaign Materials in Action

3.2 VISUAL IDENTITY

Once the project's visual identity was established in D6.1 and further developed in D6.2, a dedicated branding for the visibility campaign was introduced to ensure a strong

connection with target groups while promoting the achievements of women-led innovations mapped through FLIARA. CE has worked diligently throughout the project to provide partners with a wide range of branded resources, going beyond the initial set of materials foreseen in D6.1.

These resources include booklets for the Community of Practice (CoP) networking events (outlined in D4.2), a Guide for Ambassadors (D4.5), event materials and layouts, loop videos, posters, lanyards, sign-in sheets and PowerPoint templates, all designed to ensure that the project's and EU funding's visual identity remained consistent and recognisable. CE has also produced additional materials on request to support partners' participation in key activities across the EU, including the design and layout of 58 policy briefs, formatted in line with the structure developed in WP5.

The visual identity evolved over three main stages. During the initial awareness-raising phase, materials relied more heavily on stock images, with the expectation that these would progressively be replaced with images from WP3. From month 18 onwards, following the completion of the innovator case studies, the campaign shifted to centring the 200 innovators and 20 ambassadors in all materials with a visibility campaign, as detailed in D6.2. The innovations section of the website served to map and curate images and content, which were then reused across campaigns, magazines, social media posts and other communication outputs.

Project partners have made extensive use of these visual resources. They have supported, for example, the Gender Guide for Innovation (D4.5), promoted project results in conference presentations (particularly under WP3 and WP4) and framed the CoP networking events held in Ireland (July 2024), Slovenia (September 2024), Italy (January 2025) and Sweden (May 2025). This has helped ensure that the visual identity and core messages of FLIARA are consistently reused by practitioners, researchers and policymakers.

3.3 WEBSITE

The FLIARA website has evolved in step with the visibility campaign, ensuring that the 200 women innovators constitute a central element of the project's online presence. The site architecture includes a home page, information about the project, the toolkit (detailed in D4.4), and a comprehensive "Results" section, which brings together Scientific Publications, Policy Briefs, Policy Booklet, Practice Abstracts, the Gender Innovation Guide, Newsletters, Deliverables, Practice Abstracts, Innovators, Ambassadors and Multimedia (videos and podcasts) content. Accessible at <https://www.fliara.eu/>.

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Figure 3. Website preview

3.4 SOCIAL MEDIA

Similarly, the campaign served the objectives of social media by enabling the elaboration of dedicated content on enhancing the role of women in farming and rural areas thanks to the involvement of the FLIARA Ambassadors and the materials collected via WP3. These elements provided the essential foundation for FLIARA to communicate and promote the project effectively across digital channels.

Figure 4. FLIARA social media grid at a glance

The visibility campaign leveraged the rich, compelling stories and data from the ambassadors and WP3 case studies, transforming them into dedicated key messages focused on female leadership, innovation, and impact. This process allowed the project to move beyond general updates and consistently spotlight the individual women through tailored narratives, amplifying the project's core message that women are vital drivers of sustainable rural development and ensuring high engagement with key stakeholders and the wider public.

FLIARA has maintained a consistent and strategic presence across its main social media channels; Instagram, LinkedIn, Facebook and X, in order to increase the visibility of women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas and to drive traffic towards project outputs hosted on the website. These channels have been used to share news items, stories from the 200 innovators and 20 ambassadors, project milestones, event announcements and follow-up materials, as well as key policy and research results emerging from other work packages. WP6 regularly posted updates highlighting individual innovators and ambassadors, drawing on the fact sheets and case studies produced under WP3 and directing users to the dedicated innovators section and related resources on the project website, which now serves as a hub connecting to the toolkit, policy briefs and other major deliverables.

Figure 5. Example of social media post

A coherent hashtag strategy has underpinned this activity, with dedicated tags such as #FLIARACoP, #FLIARAImpires, #FLIARAEU, #WomenInAgri and #RuralWomen used systematically to reinforce the project's identity, align with wider EU and international debates on gender and rural development, and enhance discoverability of posts. WP6 has also aligned posting schedules with key international days and policy moments – including International Women's Day, the International Day of Rural Women and major project events such as the Community of Practice launch and the final conference – to maximise engagement and ensure that visibility efforts resonate with broader public and policy agendas. Each post follows a common format comprising a concise narrative caption, a clear call to action directing users to specific web pages (such as news articles, event registrations, toolkit entries or innovators' profiles), and relevant tags and mentions of partner institutions and stakeholders to encourage interaction, sharing and cross-promotion.

Through this integrated approach, social media has functioned as both an outreach channel and a bridge to the project's web-based resources, supporting engagement with the four core target groups identified in the communication strategy: civil society (citizens, innovators, organisations and associations), the scientific community, innovation support services and policymakers. The combination of regular content, event-linked campaigns and cross-linking to the innovators section, toolkit and policy outputs has significantly contributed to boosting the visibility of women's contributions to agriculture and rural areas at the European level and to positioning FLIARA as a reference initiative in this field.

3.5 PROFILE INTERVIEWS

WP6 has used the website to host profile interviews with all ambassadors, produced in a journalistic style alongside the CoP events strategic approach (D4.1), Ethics, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and in line with the Data Management Plan of

FLIARA. These interviews served a dual purpose: feeding into the visibility campaign videos (D6.5) and offering accessible stories that convey the ambassadors' innovations to a broad audience beyond academic outputs. All interviews have been published on the website and were compiled in the FLIARA Magazine, of which 120 printed copies were produced and distributed to key stakeholders at the final conference on 17 October 2025 in Brussels, Belgium (see section 4.9.3 of the FLIARA Final Conference). The online versions are also available on the project website and featured in the final FLIARA final newsletter: <https://fliara.eu/tag/fliara-ambassador/>.

The interviews were promoted across social media channels along with its respective videos (D6.5), providing both audiovisual and written formats to suit different user preferences and enhancing search engine visibility through indexed content. For example, a search for “FLIARA Ambassador Slovenia Petra Matos” returns FLIARA social media posts, the YouTube video, the innovator / ambassador profile on the website and the profile interview, illustrating how targeted content and consistent inbound communication can significantly increase outreach.

Figure 6. Preview of Google Search

The dedicated articles for all the 20 FLIARA Innovation Ambassadors can be found directly in the following links:

Ambassador	Country	Title Article	Link
Ursula Kelly	Ireland	Pioneering Change in Rural Ireland: An Interview with Ursula Kelly	https://fliara.eu/pioneering-change-in-rural-ireland-an-interview-with-ursula-kelly/
Blátnaid Gallagher	Ireland	Weaving Tradition and Innovation: Blátnaid Gallagher's Journey with the Galway Wool Co-op	https://fliara.eu/weaving-tradition-and-innovation-blatnaid-gallaghers-journey-with-the-galway-wool-co-op/
Alexandra Larsson	Sweden	Beyond the Wheel: How Alexandra Larsson Is Reshaping Swedish Driving Education	https://fliara.eu/driving-change-alexandra-larssons-journey-to-revolutionise-the-swedish-driving-school-industry/
Malin Axelsson	Sweden	Malin Axelsson: Pioneering a Greener Future from the Heart of Småland	https://fliara.eu/malin-axelsson-pioneering-a-greener-future-from-the-heart-of-smaland/
Mieke Elzenga	The Netherlands	Mieke Elzenga: Redefining Rural Innovation through Sustainable Living	https://fliara.eu/mieke-elzenga-redefining-rural-innovation-through-sustainable-living/
Annette Harberink	The Netherlands	Annette Harberink: "Innovation Grows Where Values Take Root"	https://fliara.eu/annette-harberink-innovation-grows-where-values-take-root/
Natalia Díaz	Spain	A Buzz of Change: Natalia Díaz and the Rural Revolution of Ecoalpispa	https://fliara.eu/a-buzz-of-change-natalia-diaz-and-the-rural-revolution-of-ecoalpispa/
Isabel Sánchez Tejado	Spain	Isabel Sánchez Tejado: Redefining Rural Tourism with a Generative Vision	https://fliara.eu/isabel-sanchez-tejado-redefining-rural-tourism-with-a-generative-vision/

Linda Kelly	Germany	From Lupins to Leadership: The Rural Innovation of Linda Kelly	https://fliara.eu/from-lupins-to-leadership-the-rural-innovation-of-linda-kelly/
Anja Frey	Germany	Anja Frey: Redefining Calf Rearing Through Innovation and Persistence	https://fliara.eu/anja-frey-redefining-calf-rearing-through-innovation-and-persistence/
Sofia Matteis	Italy	Rooted in Resistance: The Feminist Farm of Sofia De Matteis	https://fliara.eu/rooted-in-resistance-the-feminist-farm-of-sofia-de-matteis/
Sarah Khoudja	Italy	From Discarded Nets to New Futures: The Story of Sarah Khoudja and CuCilento	https://fliara.eu/from-discarded-nets-to-new-futures-the-story-of-sarah-khoudja-and-cucilento/
Petra Matos	Slovenia	Petra Matos: Planting Seeds of Solidarity in Rural Slovenia	https://fliara.eu/petra-matos-planting-seeds-of-solidarity-in-rural-slovenia/
Saša Kržič	Slovenia	Saša Kržič: The Slovenian Pioneer Turning Tiny Greens into a Rural Revolution	https://fliara.eu/sasa-krzic-the-slovenian-pioneer-turning-tiny-greens-into-a-rural-revolution/
Rita Porkka	Finland	Rooted in the Forest: The Innovation Journey of Rita Porkka	https://fliara.eu/rooted-in-the-forest-the-innovation-journey-of-rita-porkka/
Sonja Jokiranta	Finland	Fields of Creativity: The Innovation Journey of Sonja Jokiranta	https://fliara.eu/fields-of-creativity-the-innovation-journey-of-sonja-jokiranta/
Alžbeta Nagyová	Czech Republic	Cultivating Change: How Alžbeta Nagyová	https://fliara.eu/cultivating-change-how-alzbeta-nagyova-is-redefining-green-farming-in-czechia/

		is Redefining Green Farming in Czechia	
Iva Zdražilov	Czech Republic	Iva Zdražilová: Cultivating Change, Rooted in Tradition	https://fliara.eu/iva-zadrazilova-cultivating-change-rooted-in-tradition/
Patricia Marina Toma	Romania	Patricia Marina Toma: The Artist Who Turned a Village into a Canvas of Hope	https://fliara.eu/patricia-marina-toma-the-artist-who-turned-a-village-into-a-canvas-of-hope/
Anca Veronica Marcu	Romania	Anca Veronica Marcu: Breaking Barriers and Building Futures in Rural Romania	https://fliara.eu/anca-veronica-marcu-breaking-barriers-and-building-futures-in-rural-romania/

Table 2. Profile interviews

3.6 SOCIAL MEDIA ADVERTISING

The visibility campaign was implemented not only through organic social media activity but also through targeted paid advertising designed to reach specific audiences and further promote the women innovators featured in FLIARA. A key element of this strategy was the innovations section on the website (fliara.eu/innovators), which served as the main landing environment for the campaign and showcased the individual innovation stories at national and European level, as well as in the context of the Brussels final conference.

FLIARA Country	Innovators Link
Czech Republic	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=czech_republic
Finland	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=finland
Germany	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=germany
Ireland	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=ireland
Italy	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=italy
Netherlands	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=netherlands

Romania	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=romania
Slovenia	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=slovenia
Spain	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=spain
Sweden	https://fliara.eu/innovators/?country=sweden

Table 3. Landing pages per country

Paid promotion was implemented via the Meta advertising platform, with a campaign entitled “Women Innovation Stories in Farming and Rural Areas”. Ten advertisement sets were created, one for each of the countries involved in the WP3 case studies, each using country-specific images and links to tailored landing pages. The advertisements combined concise messages designed to resonate with the target audiences and clear calls to action and were displayed on Instagram and Facebook.

Country	Ad Preview	Outreach (Meta Platforms)
Ireland		18,860 Reach

Funded by
the European Union

Romania

FLIARA Project
Sponsored · 🌐

📍 Discover how women in Romania are leading with innovation, creativity, and resilience. From rural entrepreneurship to cultural preservation – explore their stories today!

Women's Innovation Stories
Empowering Rural Futures
Romania

flara.eu
Women Innovators in Romania [Learn more](#)

50,677 Reach

Sweden

FLIARA Project
Sponsored · 🌐

📍 In Sweden, women are leading sustainable change in rural areas! Explore how they're turning innovative ideas into thriving solutions for people and the planet.

Women's Innovation Stories
Empowering Rural Futures
Sweden

flara.eu
Women Innovators in Sweden [Learn more](#)

16,315 Reach

Funded by
the European Union

<p>Spain</p>		<p>33,028 Reach</p>
<p>Finland</p>		<p>14,073 Reach</p>

Funded by
the European Union

Germany

FLIARA Project
Sponsored · View profile

👋 Meet the women leading innovation in Germany's rural landscapes! Their work blends tradition with technology, from sustainable agriculture to community-focused enterprises. 📖 Explore their journeys now.

fliara.eu
Women Innovators in Germany [Learn more](#)

15,820 Reach

Italy

FLIARA Project
Sponsored · View profile

👋 From sustainable farming to heritage-based businesses, Italy's women innovators are leading rural renewal. See how they're building strong, connected, and vibrant communities.

fliara.eu
Women Innovators in Italy
Celebrating female-led rur... [Learn more](#)

46,610 Reach

Slovenia

FLIARA Project
Sponsored · 1/18

🌱 From forest farms to eco-businesses, women innovators in Slovenia are redefining rural development. Get to know their stories and the impact they're making in their communities.

Women's Innovation Stories
Empowering Rural Futures
Slovenia

Funded by the European Union

fliara.eu
Women Innovators in Slovenia [Learn more](#)

38,413 Reach

Czech Republic

FLIARA Project
Sponsored · 1/18

🌱 Women are changing the face of rural innovation in Czechia! Get inspired by their pioneering work in sustainability, agri-tourism, and social impact. 🌟 See how they're shaping their regions.

Women's Innovation Stories
Empowering Rural Futures
Czechia

Funded by the European Union

fliara.eu
Women Innovators in Czechia [Learn more](#)

28,065 Reach

<p>The Netherlands</p>		<p>14,588 Reach</p>
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Table 4. Ads preview and outreach

3.7 NEWSLETTERS

Since the inception of the project, FLIARA has released six newsletters (<https://fliara.eu/newsletters/>), each providing a comprehensive update on activities, milestones and key results. The newsletters have been an important communication tool for informing stakeholders about progress across all work packages, highlighting women-led innovation stories and announcing upcoming events and opportunities. They have also helped to drive traffic to the project website and to ensure regular engagement with practitioners, policy makers, researchers and civil society organisations interested in rural innovation and gender equality.

Issue	Description
<p>Female-led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas</p> <p>Visit our website</p>	<p>First Newsletter (M6): The inaugural newsletter, titled "Empowering Rural Change: Welcome to the 1st FLIARA newsletter!," was launched in Month 6 of the project. It provided an introduction to FLIARA's goals, objectives, and initial activities, setting the stage for ongoing engagement and collaboration.</p>
<p>FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas</p> <p>Welcome to our 2nd newsletter!</p>	<p>Second Newsletter (M12): Building on the momentum of the first newsletter, FLIARA released its second edition, titled "Breaking Ground: FLIARA's Second Newsletter is Here," in Month 12. This newsletter delved deeper into project developments, highlighting key achievements and upcoming initiatives.</p>
<p>3rd Newsletter FLIARA</p>	<p>Third Newsletter (M18): This edition updates stakeholders on project advancements, introduces the FLIARA ambassadors as part of the visibility campaign and the community of practice, showcasing the progress made since the previous newsletter on Foresight and Trend Analysis, Assessment of Rural and Farming Policy and Legal Frameworks in Relation to Women-led Innovation and Case Study activities of the project.</p>
<p>4th Newsletter FLIARA</p>	<p>Fourth Newsletter (M24): This edition introduces the Comparative Analysis and highlights the FLIARA Policy Benchmarking. It also features the CoP events in Ireland and in Slovenia while promoting the 200 remarkable innovations led by women across the partnering countries and disseminates the approved FLIARA deliverables. It also shares news and insights of the FLIARA project.</p>

	<p>Fifth Newsletter (M30): Under this release the FLIARA webinars reports, the CoP events held in Italy and Sweden as well as the FLIARA toolkit were promoted. This edition provides insights, news, scientific publications, practice abstracts and promoted the Final Conference.</p>
	<p>Sixth Newsletter (M36): This FLIARA newsletter narrates the final steps of the project through relevant insights on policy recommendations, the gender innovation guide, the final version of the toolkit and highlights the achievements of the project via articles, news and multimedia materials derived from the visibility campaign.</p>

Table 5. Newsletters Timeline

3.8 FLIARA AMBASSADORS

FLIARA Ambassadors have played a central role in the visibility campaign. Initially selected to showcase women’s innovation in farming and rural areas, they progressively became active promoters of the project itself, using their own online channels and networks and effectively adopting the FLIARA brand as a vehicle for change.

Figure 7. FLIARA Ambassadors on Social Media

Through their participation in FLIARA activities and by sharing project content with their communities, the 20 FLIARA Ambassadors have substantially extended the project’s

outreach beyond the consortium's circles. Their engagement has amplified the visibility of the women innovators involved in the project, strengthened peer-to-peer connections among them, and reinforced FLIARA's message on women's leadership in rural innovation across Europe.

3.9 INSIGHTS

3.9.1 SOCIAL MEDIA FOLLOWERS

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/fliara.project>
 - Followers: 889
- Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/fliara_project/
 - Followers: 697
- Twitter/X: https://x.com/FLIARA_Project
 - Followers: 1413
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/fliara-project/>
 - Followers: 994

These social media accounts are key communication channels through which FLIARA ensures transparency, widespread dissemination of project outcomes, and engagement with stakeholders and the wider public. Through leveraging the power of social media, the project aims to create a vibrant online community, foster dialogue, and raise awareness about the importance of women's role in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union.

3.9.2 LINKEDIN INSIGHTS

The following insights summarise FLIARA's LinkedIn performance over three consecutive 365-day periods (2023, 2024 and 2025). Together, these metrics provide an indication of the project's reach and engagement on this professional networking platform. Over the combined period, FLIARA's presence on LinkedIn generated a total of 72.502 impressions, representing the cumulative visibility of project posts in users' feeds. This level of exposure shows that the project's content has consistently reached a substantial audience of professionals interested in agriculture, rural development and gender equality, and has contributed to reinforcing FLIARA's profile and messages among relevant stakeholders.

From January 1, 2023 to December 16, 2023

Metrics

Impressions ▾

Organic 12,937
 Sponsored 0

From December 17, 2023 to December 16, 2024

Metrics

Impressions ▾

Organic 27,913
 Sponsored 0

From December 17, 2024 to December 18, 2025

Organic 31,652

Table 6. LinkedIn Insights

3.9.3 X INSIGHTS

Over the last 36 months, the project’s social media strategy has also proven effective on X. During the project period, posts from the FLIARA account generated approximately 68.5K impressions, reflecting substantial outreach and visibility. Engagement patterns

slowed temporarily during the platform's transition from Twitter to X from mid 2024; however, this was mitigated through targeted social media advertising, which helped sustain and boost interactions and ensured that key messages continued to reach a growing audience.

Table 7. X Insights

Overall, the FLIARA X account has succeeded in capturing the interest of a broad and diverse public, including stakeholders beyond the immediate project network. The volume of impressions and interactions demonstrates the project’s capacity to disseminate its messages effectively, support ongoing dialogue and enhance the visibility of women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas, in line with FLIARA’s objective of fostering a more inclusive rural innovation ecosystem across Europe.

3.9.4 FACEBOOK INSIGHTS

Since the inception of the project, FLIARA’s Facebook page has generated a total of 28.9K impressions up to 30 June 2024. This volume of impressions indicates that project content has been widely disseminated and regularly appeared in users’ feeds. Over the same period, posts reached 9.9K users, demonstrating a substantial spread of content beyond the immediate follower base, while 1.3K content interactions (reactions, comments, shares and other user responses) point to an active and engaged audience.

From 1 July 2024 to 18 December 2025, the FLIARA Facebook page has additionally recorded 417.984 views. This second figure reflects a change in Meta’s reporting approach, whereby several Page Insights metrics – including impressions and reach –

have been progressively deprecated and replaced by “views” in the Page Insights interface and related APIs. As a result of these changes, it is no longer possible to retrieve a full historical series for all earlier metrics, and the June 2024 report serves as the last complete snapshot for impressions and reach. The current views metric nonetheless confirms that Facebook has continued to provide strong and sustained visibility for FLIARA’s activities and messages during the final phase of the project.

Table 8. Facebook Insights

3.9.5 INSTAGRAM INSIGHTS

Since its launch in M3 of the project, FLIARA’s Instagram account has made steady progress as a visual storytelling channel. Up to 30 June 2024, the account reached 2,303 unique users, reflecting growing interest and engagement from the Instagram community with the project’s content and messages.

Following subsequent changes in Meta’s insights and API reporting, Instagram now displays “views” as a primary indicator and provides only partial historical data for earlier reach metrics. Over the project period from 1 July 2024 to 18 December 2025, the

account records 95,887 views and a current cumulative reach value of 58,511, although the reach graph no longer shows a complete historical time series. This discrepancy is linked to Meta’s ongoing deprecation and remapping of legacy insights fields (such as impressions and some reach breakdowns) into new “views”-based metrics, which limits the possibility of reconstructing earlier reach data in full. Despite these technical changes, the available figures confirm that Instagram has continued to provide substantial visual exposure for FLIARA’s activities and for the women innovators featured in the project.

Table 9. Instagram Insights

3.9.6 WEBSITE INSIGHTS (GOOGLE ANALYTICS)

Since 1 January 2023, the FLIARA website has recorded a total of 44.665 visitors, as measured through Google Analytics. Within the last 32 months since the launch of the website in M4 of the project, 21.596 of these visitors were active users, indicating sustained and growing interest in the project and its outputs.

Figure 8. Website Views

Figure 9. Active users

Over the same period, 125.712 events were registered, covering user interactions such as link clicks, downloads and session starts. This performance points to a positive trend in user engagement, suggesting that the website is not only attracting visitors but also retaining their attention and encouraging active interaction with the content.

3.9.7 NEWSLETTER INSIGHTS

Thanks to FLIARA's robust communication and dissemination efforts across social media channels and the project website, the project has successfully amassed a subscriber base of 1.482 individuals and 781 readers. Such engagement underscores the effectiveness of our outreach strategies across all FLIARA platforms.

Figure 10. Newsletter Insights

- **First Newsletter:** "Empowering Rural Change: Welcome to the 1st FLIARA newsletter!" <https://fliara.eu/?na=view&id=8>
- **Second Newsletter:** "Breaking Ground: FLIARA's Second Newsletter is Here" <https://fliara.eu/?na=view&id=13>
- **Third Newsletter:** "Empowering Rural Women: FLIARA's Third Newsletter - Innovation, Impact, and Inspiration" <https://fliara.eu/?na=view&id=66>
- **Fourth Newsletter:** "FLIARA Newsletter #4: Spotlight on Women Shaping Rural Innovation" <https://fliara.eu/?na=view&id=120>
- **Fifth Newsletter:** "Spotlighting Innovation: FLIARA's Path to Policy Change" <https://fliara.eu/?na=view&id=206>
- **Sixth Newsletter:** "Legacy Edition: Tools, Stories & Policy for Rural Transformation" <https://fliara.eu/?na=view&id=277>

3.9.8 TRADITIONAL EARNED MEDIA

The project initially foresaw the publication of **at least 20 press releases**. In practice, the FLIARA Newsroom section (<https://fliara.eu/news/>) now contains **168 news items and blog articles**, illustrating a strong commitment to communicating project activities, results and stories throughout its lifetime. The aim of this sustained output has been to populate the platform with timely, accessible content derived from project progress, ensuring that information about FLIARA remains available, searchable and easy to reuse online.

Figure 11. FLIARA Newsroom

News items have covered a wide range of topics, including key meetings, participation in external events, milestones in the work packages, achievements by FLIARA innovators and ambassadors, and the release of new materials and insights. CE has applied a dedicated journalistic approach to this work, treating the Newsroom as the main hub for FLIARA communications and as a gateway for other media and stakeholders to access up-to-date information about the project. In parallel, WP6 has monitored and documented communication and dissemination activities across both external online channels and traditional press, enabling the project to quantify its earned media performance by the time of this final deliverable with **167 earned media publications** (See Annex 1 – Media Clipping).

3.10 VIDEOS AND MATERIALS PRODUCED

Over the lifespan of the project, FLIARA has produced a comprehensive suite of audiovisual materials, all of which are described in detail in Deliverable D6.5 on innovation videos, podcasts and video blogs. These outputs were designed to: (1) raise awareness of the project, (2) communicate its aims and key messages to target groups

via social media and online channels, and (3) support the wider dissemination of results across stakeholder communities. The videos are available at <https://fliara.eu/multimedia/>.

Figure 12. FLIARA Videos

The formats developed include short, descriptive and background-oriented videos aligned with the core messages set out in D6.1 and D6.2. The visibility campaign videos, in particular, were produced specifically for social media promotion and were subsequently integrated into the FLIARA Toolkit and the Gender Guide for Innovation (D4.5), ensuring that they continue to serve both communication and capacity-building purposes beyond the end of the project.

4. DISSEMINATION

This section describes the dissemination activities undertaken to ensure broad access to FLIARA's scientific and practical outputs. It covers the production and sharing of publications, fact sheets, practice abstracts, the toolkit, and other results, as well as the mechanisms for making these accessible through open repositories and strategic partnerships. Special attention is given to the ways in which dissemination has strengthened uptake by target groups and maximised the impact of project achievements.

4.1 SYNERGIES

From the outset, FLIARA recognised that establishing synergies with related EU-funded initiatives and policy platforms would be essential to maximise the visibility, uptake and long-term impact of its results in terms of communication, dissemination and exploitation. In D6.1 and D6.2, the project therefore identified a series of priority projects and networks, as well as CAP-related structures such as the EIP-AGRI Support Facility and the European Network for Rural Development, as key reference points for future collaboration. These early plans were closely linked to the work of the CoP Network (WP4), Policy Design and Assessment (WP5) and Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (WP6), and were intended to support knowledge flows and joint outreach activities around women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas.

Building on this strategic foundation, WP6 and WP7 systematically implemented a programme of synergy-building activities throughout the project period, with a clear emphasis on joint communication and dissemination actions. The process began with an online synergies event in June 2023, which brought together several EU-funded projects and served to introduce FLIARA's objectives and initial results. This was followed by a series of targeted bilateral and multilateral meetings in 2024 and 2025 with organisations including the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), ModernAKIS, EIT Food, TERINOV, AskGrant, the EU CAP Network / EIP-AGRI and the Joint Research Centre, among others, focusing on co-organised events, cross-promotion of materials and the inclusion of FLIARA content in external communication channels.

A key strand of this work involved deepening collaboration with FLIARA's sister projects, particularly GRASS CEILING and SWIFT, in order to avoid duplication and to strengthen the collective policy message on women-led innovation in rural areas. FLIARA has participated in diverse events held by these projects and vice versa as shown in the Attended Events section of this deliverable. Dedicated meetings led by TU Delft were organised to discuss policy and research developments and ensure coherence across the three consortia. In parallel, the project advanced the synergies initially envisaged with the Horizon Europe multi-actor project EU FarmBook. WP6 selected EU FarmBook as one of the repositories for FLIARA results and worked closely with its communication team to prepare featured articles, participate in their activities and make FLIARA outputs accessible via the platform. As a result, all approved deliverables from the first reporting

period and the 200 fact sheets on women-led innovations are now available through the EU CAP Network / EU FarmBook profile, significantly extending the reach of these resources.

The table below summarises a selection of the most significant synergy meetings and collaborations achieved during the reporting period, highlighting their focus on events co-organisation, joint communication and the integration of FLIARA content into external initiatives:

Date	Partner Institution/Organisation	Key Area of Collaboration
Jun 11, 2024	OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development)	Collaboration for FLIARA events.
Sep 03, 2024	ModernAKIS	Planning a joint networking event for women in agriculture and AKIS systems.
Oct 02, 2024	EIT Food	Exploring synergies, potential mutual promotion of trainings/services (e.g., EWA program), and advertising the EIT Food Lisbon event.
Jan 30, 2025	EU FarmBook	EU FarmBook Project Coordinator and members of the FLIARA Consortium explored ways to disseminate FLIARA results and fact sheets via the platform.
Feb 18, 2025	Gender Solution	Collaboration for the "Empowering Rural Communities" event: Representative participated as a finance panelist and aligned on presentation content.
Feb 20, 2025	FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations)	Collaboration for the "Empowering Rural Communities" webinar: A representative from FAO was confirmed as a keynote speaker on the "Status of Women in Agri-food Systems."
Mar 05, 2025	EU Commission – DG AGRI	Strategic collaboration for the Final Conference and the "Empowering Rural Communities" webinar, ensuring the inclusion of the Commission's perspective on gender equality and rural women.

Mar 18, 2025	TERINOV - Science and Technology Park	Planning and content creation for the 3 rd CoP online event on Effective Pitching for Business Angels for women entrepreneurs.
Mar 27, 2025	EU CAP Network / EIP-AGRI	Collaboration for the 3 rd CoP online event: A representative from the EU CAP Network prepared a presentation on CAP Network funding opportunities for rural women.
Apr 02, 2025	Joint Research Centre	Collaboration for the 3 rd CoP online event: a presentation on how to use the Rural Toolkit and funding opportunities.
Apr 03, 2025	AskGrant	Collaboration for the 3 rd CoP online event: a presentation on startup funding and technology scaling.

Table 10. Meetings for Synergies

Beyond these formal interactions, FLIARA partners contributed to and were featured in a range of external events, newsletters, online forums and policy debates hosted by sister projects, CAP networks and other EU initiatives, thereby strengthening the project’s reputation and embedding its messages in wider European discussions. Overall, the synergies initially anticipated in D6.1 and D6.2 have evolved into a dense network of collaborations which have enhanced dissemination, fostered joint reflection on policy and practice, and created additional pathways for the exploitation and long-term use of FLIARA results.

4.2 DELIVERABLES SECTION

The deliverables section was implemented following the approval of the first periodic report and will be maintained by CE in its role as Exploitation Manager after the project ends. Deliverables are linked through the Zenodo Community established by CE (<https://zenodo.org/communities/fliara>), enabling tracking of downloads and views and supporting the long-term sustainability and accessibility of outputs.

Deliverables

← Visit toolkit

Show 10 entries

Search:

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Available Downloads	Due Date (Month)
D1.1	FLIARA Conceptual framework	WP1	1 – Galway	R – Document, report	Download	6
D1.2	Women-led Innovation Research Review	WP1	1 – Galway	R – Document, report	Download	6
D1.3	Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks	WP1	1 – Galway	R – Document, report	Download	17
D1.4	Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection	WP1	1 – Galway	R – Document, report	Download	9
D1.5	Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking	WP1	1 – Galway	R – Document, report	Download	17
D2.1	Research Guidelines for Foresight and Trend Analysis	WP2	6 – UTU	R – Document, report	Download	2
D2.2	Future vision manifestations	WP2	6 – UTU	R – Document, report	Download	6
D2.3	Sustainability Innovations	WP2	6 – UTU	R – Document, report	Download	12
D2.4	Women's Potential Contributions to sustainability Innovations	WP2	6 – UTU	R – Document, report	Download	18
D3.1	Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection	WP3	4 – UNICAL	R – Document, report	Download	12

Showing 1 to 10 of 33 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 Next

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Figure 13. Deliverables section on the project's website

4.3 INNOVATORS SECTION

As outlined in D6.2, the innovations section was launched in month 19 and designed by CE (<https://fliara.eu/innovators/>), enabling users to interact with the 200 fact sheets produced under WP3 and to feed these materials into the FLIARA toolkit, conceived as a living hub for project resources. The innovations section follows a standardised structure, including:

- 🏠 Full name

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- Organisation / practice
- Country
- Website
- Social media links
- “Learn more” button linking to the detailed fact sheet

-- Find by country -- -- Find by sustainability dimension -- -- Find by area -- -- Find by type of rural context -- **Go** Reset

Innovations

Discover the rural and agricultural innovation in FIJARA's diverse case study countries. Our project identified 200 innovations across Ireland, Netherlands, Germany, Sweden, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Romania, Italy, Spain, and Finland. Each innovator's journey is captured in a dedicated fact sheet, providing insights into their pioneering contributions to agriculture and rural development. Get acquainted with these remarkable individuals and explore the innovative solutions shaping the future of agriculture and rural areas.

-- Find by country -- -- Find by sustainability dimension -- -- Find by area -- -- Find by type of rural context -- **Go** Reset

 A Womens' Collective Associazione CIRCE Italy Website Learn more	 Agnes de Boer Edzemaheerd Cow Farm Netherlands Website Learn more	 Agnese Rostagno Biala Italy Website Learn more	 Ailbhe Gerrard Brookfield Farm Ireland Website Learn more
---	--	---	--

Figure 14. Innovators section

This structure also underpins the dedicated ambassadors' section, which allows users to explore the journeys and impact of the 20 ambassadors and provides a space for targeted dissemination activities. For ambassadors, the entries include:

- Full name
- Innovation
- Country
- Website
- Social media links
- “Learn more” button

Figure 15. Preview profile innovator/ambassador section

4.4 PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

In parallel, a platform with similar features was developed for the practice abstracts prepared under WP3 and WP7. WP6 prepared the upload of these abstracts to the EIP-AGRI / EU CAP Network platform. On the project website, each practice abstract page allows users to read the content directly or download a laid-out PDF (<https://fliara.eu/practice-abstracts/>). The structure designed by CE includes:

- Title, number and authors
- Abstract text
- Download link
- Useful links

Figure 16. Preview of the Practice Abstracts section

Figure 17. Internal Structure of the Practice Abstracts landing page

FLIARA

NETWORKING: A KEY FACILITATOR FOR RURAL AND FARM WOMEN-LED INNOVATION

PRACTICE ABSTRACT 3

Authors: Maiza Farrell, Louise Weir and Aisling Murlugh
University of Galway
Website: www.fliara.eu

Networking supports rural and farm women-led innovation. FLIARA's case study comparative analysis showed the availability of and engagement with strong networks was a key aspect for successful women-led innovation.

Networking provides diverse benefits. Networks support the innovator's start-up and development. More specific benefits include access to information, building skills, and connecting with potential mentors. Networks can also provide a wider source of support including toward self-empowerment.

Be part of a diverse range of networks. For example, this could mean networking through professional organisations as well as wider local community networks. Networking at a local level is important, but so are opportunities to expand regional, national and international networks.

Availability of networks and ability to network. This appears a key part of improving levels of women-led rural and farm innovation. Networking takes time therefore directly supporting women leading innovations to take part in networking appears important to increase women's capacity for networking.

Potential for specific targeted networking supports. New ideas could be women-led innovation networking vouchers that incentivise the activity and stipend payments for joining more formal and targeted networks. Networking opportunities must be available, which makes it important to support spaces and places where these opportunities are available, such as events and network meetings, as well as available infrastructure, such as community centers. Developing networks between operators working in the same territory and/or industry or supporting more informal networks to exchange knowledge and receive support also seems relevant.

Useful links:

- See the experience of www.fliara.eu/networking-women-collective/, www.fliara.eu/networking-women-collective/, www.fliara.eu/networking-women-collective/, www.fliara.eu/networking-women-collective/, www.fliara.eu/networking-women-collective/

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Figure 18. Example of Practice Abstract

CE has maintained regular contact with the EU CAP Network communications team to create the FLIARA profile, understand the workflow for submitting drafts and prepare for future updates once D3.4 and D7.4 are approved.

In review

ⓘ Your practice abstract is currently under review by the website administrator. It will be published on the website shortly.

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
INNOVATION PATHWAYS TO SUCCESS IN RURAL AREAS

Rural issues, AKIS, incl. advice, training, on-farm demo, interactive innovation projects | Ireland, Germany (+9)

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
BUILDING CONFIDENCE AND SELF-ESTEEM IN RURAL WOMEN INNOVATORS

Rural issues, AKIS, incl. advice, training, on-farm demo, interactive innovation projects | Ireland, Germany (+9)

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
INNOVATING TO ENHANCE ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN FARMING

Rural issues, AKIS, incl. advice, training, on-farm demo, interactive innovation projects | Ireland, Germany (+9)

Figure 19. Practice Abstracts uploaded to the EU CAP Network

At the time of writing, all 25 practice abstracts are available as public drafts on the FLIARA website and have been uploaded to the EU CAP Network practice abstract section under the project profile, where they remain in draft status and in EIP AGRI

format as shown above and can be accessed via: https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/female-led-innovation-agriculture-and-rural-areas_en.

4.5 POLICY BRIEFS

A dedicated policy briefs section (<https://fliara.eu/policy-briefs>) has also been created to support the legacy and discoverability of these outputs. Templates were developed to align the policy briefs with the visibility campaign branding and the structure agreed in WP5. CE and TU Delft worked together to ensure that the online presentation facilitates dissemination and enables users to filter materials. The section allows filtering by:

- Country
- Theme or network

Each policy brief is presented with a visual card and navigation buttons and has an individual page including a placeholder for an image, country, publication date, a short abstract and a download link. Metadata (metatags) have been applied to improve indexation in search engines and increase online visibility.

Figure 20. Policy Briefs Section Structure

4.6 TOOLKIT INTEGRATION

A major development has been the full integration of the FLIARA toolkit into the website, completed in month 30 (April 2025). The structure of the toolkit, developed under the integration tool coded by CE from scratch (T6.4) and described in D6.2, provided an

easy-to-use template for partners to supply their articles. This, in turn, enabled the ECOLISE team to populate the contents developed by partners the toolkit directly through the content management system without additional web development. The overall web structure of the toolkit was developed under T6.4 and is described in detail in D4.4.

Figure 21. Toolkit Integration

To support the integration of the materials, also the results sections of the website were transferred to the toolkit under the tab of resources: the Innovators and Ambassadors sections (WP3), the Gender Innovation Guide (WP4), the Policy Booklet and the Policy Briefs (WP5) sections, trainings were also uploaded to the Toolkit, in particular the training on social media for female innovators by CE (<https://fliara.eu/pitch-presence-power-training/>) and trainings derived from the Online CoP events (D4.2).

Figure 22. Integrated Toolkit

4.7 OPEN-ACCESS PLATFORMS

All approved FLIARA deliverables have been made openly available through multiple repositories, including CORDIS, Zenodo, EU FarmBook and the University of Galway

Research Repository (former ARAN). Zenodo serves as the primary source for monitoring downloads and views gathering the statistical details since the file has been uploaded, while ARAN provides additional statistics at institutional level, only during previous 6 months, enabling the project to track the uptake and reuse of its outputs over time.

Zenodo				University of Galway Research Repository	
Deliverable Title	License/Rights	Views	Downloads	Views	Downloads
D7.2: Data Management Plan – VII	CC-BY	49	69	10	4
D7.1: Data Management Plan – V1	CC-BY	54	52	8	0
D6.4: FLIARA Project Website	CC BY-SA	67	110	10	0
D6.2: Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities V2	CC-BY	57	57	12	3
D6.1: Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities V1	CC-BY	74	81	4	2
D4.1: Strategic Action Plan	CC BY-SA	202	165	5	0
D.3.3: Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and Fact Sheets on	CC BY-SA	509	425	5	0

Female Innovations					
D3.2: Inventory of Female-Led Innovations	CC BY-SA	122	94	6	3
D3.1: Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection	CC BY-SA	99	113	2	0
D2.4: Women's Potential Contributions to Sustainability Innovations	CC-BY	166	168	6	3
D2.3: Sustainability Innovations	CC-BY	112	113	4	0
D2.2: Future Vision Manifestations	CC-BY	183	188	9	4
D2.1 Research Guidelines for Foresight and Trend Analysis	CC-BY	69	84	10	1
D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking	CC-BY	113	101	2	5
D1.4: Initial Case Study Assessment and Selection Framework	CC-BY	176	185	3	2
D1.3: Assessment of Rural and Farming Policy and Legal Frameworks in relation to Women-led Innovation	CC-BY	302	233	11	6

D1.2: Women-Led Innovation Research Review	CC-BY	153	150	10	3
D1.1 FLIARA Conceptual Framework	CC-BY	245	216	18	0

Table 11. Deliverables

4.8 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

The FLIARA project has also produced four peer-reviewed academic articles that examine the definition, significance and challenges of women-led innovation in European agriculture and rural development. These publications are listed on the project website and can be accessed via the dedicated scientific publications page: <https://fliara.eu/scientific-publications/>.

Publication/Journal	Title	Date Published	Short Description	Link
European Countryside (Sciendo)	Empowering Women-Led Innovations: Key Players In Realising The Long-Term Vision For Rural Areas	Dec 22, 2024	Proposes a clear definition and distinguishing features of women-led innovations to guide policy. Advocates for their increased support to achieve the EU's Long-term Vision for Rural Areas and align with SDG 5 on gender equality.	https://sciendo.com/article/10.2478/euco-2024-0029
Dela (University of Ljubljana)	PROJEKT FLIARA: TRAJNOSTNI RAZVOJ PODEŽELJA, NOVI PRISTOPI, VLOGA IN MOČ ŽENSK (FLIARA Project: Sustainable Rural	Dec 30, 2024	Presents the project's theoretical foundations and first-year findings from Slovenia, focusing on future visions, identifying innovations, and assessing women's potential	https://journals.uni-lj.si/Dela/issue/view/1444/1130

European Public Mosaic (EPuM)	<i>Development, New Approaches, Role and Empowerment of Women)</i>		contributions across political, economic, social, and environmental spheres.	
	Breaking barriers: how women are transforming agriculture and rural innovation	May 21, 2025	Identifies the challenges and enabling factors for women to thrive in agriculture and rural innovation. Underscores their transformative potential and provides key recommendations for policymakers to support them.	https://www.gencat.cat/eapc/epum/N26/index.html#page=107
	Gendered Mismatches in the Business Support System in Rural Sweden	Oct 28, 2025	Research focusing on Sweden that identifies a systemic bias in the business support system, which undervalues and excludes women-led initiatives focused on social/cultural sustainability over traditional growth models. Proposes policy reform.	https://www.sciepub.ish.com/article/pii/752
Rural and Regional Development				

Table 12. Scientific Publications

4.9 ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

Throughout the project, FLIARA partners have actively participated in a wide range of events across the EU, targeting policy makers, the scientific community, civil society and women innovators. Participation focused both on raising awareness of the project's themes and on presenting emerging and final FLIARA results with 68 in total. The corresponding table in Annex 2 of the present deliverable lists these contributions, in all of which the project was and will be presented, promoted and its outputs disseminated. One participation is expected at early 2026.

4.10 ORGANISED EVENTS

Under WP4, four major CoP networking events (in-person and online) were organised and are reported in detail in D4.2. In addition, five key webinars and one international final conference in Brussels were organised and promoted, providing high-visibility opportunities to share FLIARA's findings with European and international audiences.

4.10.1 WEBINARS

WP6 envisaged the organisation of a series of webinars as part of the project's communication, dissemination and synergies strategy. The first webinar, held in month 6, aimed to establish links with other EU initiatives and projects, foster early collaborations and introduce FLIARA to other consortia. This online forum took place on 30 June 2023 and brought together ten EU-funded projects working on rural development, smart communities and gender equality, including GRASS CEILING, COEVOLVERS, SWIFT, SafeHabitus, PREMIERE, DEMETER, AURORAL, ATHENA, EU-FARMBOOK and GENDERACTION+. The event created a shared space for exploring future collaboration, not only in terms of exchanging results and lessons learned, but also as a hub for joint communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

Figure 23. Establishing Synergies with EU-Funded Projects

4.10.1.1 MODERNAKIS

One of the main outcomes of these early synergies was the co-organisation of the webinar “AKIS in Action: Strengthening AKIS through women-led innovation” with the ModernAKIS project. In this event, WP6 and WP7 combined efforts to present FLIARA-related Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) results to the wider ModernAKIS community. The panel included contributions from Natalia Brzezina,

Policy Officer in DG AGRI's Research and Innovation Unit, Associate Professor Maura Farrell, FLIARA Project Coordinator, and Víctor R. Martínez, FLIARA Communication Leader at Consulta Europa. Irish and Spanish FLIARA case studies were presented to illustrate how AKIS can support female entrepreneurship in agriculture and rural areas (<https://modernakis.eu/akis-in-action-strengthening-akis-through-women-led-innovation/>). The webinar highlighted the central role of women in sustainable agriculture and rural development and underlined the need to strengthen support for women at all levels.

Figure 24. AKIS in Action: Strengthening AKIS through women led innovation

4.10.1.2 EMPOWERING RURAL COMMUNITIES: GENDER EQUALITY AND INNOVATION IN ACTION

One of the major webinars, initially foreseen for M18 and subsequently moved to M22 (March 2025), built directly on these synergies. Titled “Empowering Rural Communities: Gender Equality and Innovation in Action” as part of the Visibility Campaign, it presented results from WP1 to WP4 and featured interactive panels in cooperation with the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), the EIT Food Empowering Women in Agrifood programme and the OECD. Sister projects GRASS CEILING and SWIFT also participated actively. The event was actively promoted by WP6 and WP7 and gathered 151 online participants and a parallel livestream audience of 160 viewers (<https://fliara.eu/building-inclusive-rural-futures-the-fliara-webinar-on-gender-equality-and-innovation/>), meaning that more than 300 people were reached in total. It explored the intersection of gender equality, rural development and innovation, showcased practical solutions and successful innovations, and offered policy-oriented reflections to foster inclusive rural entrepreneurship. The event recordings and materials are available here: <https://fliara.eu/access-resources-webinar-fliara-empowering-rural-communities/>.

Figure 25. Empowering Rural Communities: Gender Equality and Innovation in Action

4.10.1.3 FLIARA ONLINE COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE EVENT: BRIDGING PRIVATE AND PUBLIC FUNDING FOR WOMEN INNOVATORS IN AGRICULTURE AND RURAL AREAS

Building on the success of the aforementioned webinar and the CoP, the fourth project webinar took the form of a public CoP session on funding opportunities for women innovators (<https://fliara.eu/funding-matters-fliara-webinar-addresses-gaps-and-opportunities-for-women-innovators-in-rural-areas/>). Organised and structured by CE (WP6 leader) in collaboration with WP4 and WP7, it brought together representatives of the EU CAP Network, TERINOV (incubator), AskGrant (funding experts) and the Joint Research Centre to promote and demonstrate the Rural Toolkit, including its funding opportunities component. The “3rd FLIARA Online Community of Practice Event: Bridging Private and Public Funding for Women Innovators in Agriculture and Rural Areas” gathered over 60 participants and connected EU-level experts, business developers, academics and rural innovators to discuss ways of improving access to finance for women in agriculture and rural communities. A post event platform is available with the recordings and the presentations at <https://fliara.eu/bridging-private-and-public-funding-for-women-innovators-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas-2/>.

Figure 26. Bridging Private and Public Funding for Women Innovators in Agriculture and Rural Areas

4.10.1.4 WEBINARS ORGANISED BY PARTNERS AT LOCAL LEVEL

4.10.1.4.1 WOMEN'S LEADERSHIP IN REGENERATIVE INTENTIONAL COMMUNITIES

On 7 March 2024, FLIARA inspired and supported the online session “Women’s leadership in regenerative intentional communities”, organised within the Communities for Future framework of ECOLISE. The event focused on social regeneration in community-led initiatives and the need to deconstruct patriarchal patterns and redefine gender relations in ecovillages and intentional communities in a just and regenerative way. Three women leaders from communities in Spain, Slovenia and the Netherlands shared their experiences of community building, gender transformation and regenerative practice, offering an interactive space for exchanging good practices, reflecting on power dynamics and exploring how female leadership contributes to socio-environmentally regenerative rural futures.

Figure 27. Women's leadership in regenerative intentional communities

4.10.1.4.2 SUSTAINABLE FUTURES FOR GENDER-EQUAL RURAL AREAS – A WEBINAR ON INNOVATION, EQUALITY, AND THE POTENTIAL OF THE COUNTRYSIDE

The FLIARA webinar, “Sustainable Futures for Gender-Equal Rural Areas – A Webinar on Innovation, Equality, and the Potential of the Countryside”, was held on 6 May 2025 and organised by the Swedish partners at Linnaeus University and Jönköping University. Embedded in Sweden's national “Rural Week” (Landsbygdsveckan), the event brought together researchers, community actors and other stakeholders to discuss the future of rural areas from the perspective of sustainability, innovation and gender equality. The session was led by Dr Annie Roos, Dr Anna Alexandersson and Dr Mathias Karlsson (Linnaeus University) in collaboration with Professor Helene Ahl (Jönköping University), all members of the Swedish FLIARA team, and further contributed to positioning FLIARA within national and European debates on gender-responsive rural development.

Figure 28. Sustainable Futures for Gender Equal Rural Areas

4.10.2 IN-PERSON EVENTS

Central to the FLIARA mission is the organisation of four CoP events, as documented in D4.2. The section details an additional series of local-level activities conducted by the FLIARA Project to expand its outreach and impact and reports the major event of the project: the Final Conference.

4.10.2.1 FROM INNOVATION TO POLITICAL ACTION – THE VOICE OF RURAL WOMEN

On 30 October 2025, the event “From Innovation to Political Action – The Voice of Rural Women” in Saschiz, Mureş County, Romania, gathered rural women from across the country to transform local challenges into a national political agenda for a more inclusive and sustainable rural future (<https://fliara.eu/romanian-rural-women-demand-political-voice-at-fliara-event/>). Organised under FLIARA by ECOLISE and ELARD, the event featured high-level parliamentary representatives, FLIARA innovators and Ambassadors, and civil society actors, who together highlighted the links between gender-based violence and economic exclusion, called for systemic national investment in women’s leadership and associations, and proposed the creation of a national network of rural women to channel local innovations into policy while strengthening infrastructures of care and solidarity.

Figure 29. From Innovation to Political Action – The Voice of Rural Women

4.10.2.2 FLIARA SYMPOSIUM IN SWEDEN

The FLIARA Symposium held on 26 November 2025 at Linnaeus University in Sweden brought together researchers to reflect on women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. The discussions were grounded in presentations by Annie Roos and Anna Alexandersson on FLIARA findings around rural women’s innovation journeys and policy structures, by Katarina Pettersson on GRASS CEILING results from living labs and

women's innovation practices, and by Helene Ahl on the historical evolution of gender equality policies in Sweden, with cross-cutting themes such as empowerment, networking, safe spaces, gender norms, cultural backlash and sustainability challenges in rural entrepreneurship (<https://fliara.eu/swedish-symposium-highlights-systemic-barriers-for-rural-women-innovators/>).

Figure 30. FLIARA Symposium

4.10.3 FINAL CONFERENCE: PREPARATION AND DELIVERY

The Final Conference of the FLIARA project, “Women Leading Rural Innovation: From Vision to Action”, took place on 17 October 2025 at the European Committee of the Regions (CoR) in Brussels, during the Rural Women’s Week. The event marked the culmination of three years of research, capacity-building, policy engagement and community development, and constituted a central milestone within the project’s dissemination and exploitation strategy. It brought together researchers, policymakers, innovation support actors, civil society organisations, FLIARA Ambassadors and women innovators to discuss the state of women-led innovation in rural areas and to explore pathways for embedding gender equality within rural and agricultural policy frameworks.

The conference attracted 155 registrations over a four-month promotional campaign, resulting in 107 participants attending onsite and 229 online viewers following the livestream. The programme was organised around five interconnected sessions: (1) setting the vision for rural women’s futures; (2) presenting evidence on innovation pathways, challenges and leadership; (3) translating research into policy frameworks; (4) exploring innovation ecosystems, gender and sustainability; and (5) discussing long-term legacy, network continuity and implementation at EU, national and regional levels. A dedicated Ambassador Roundtable provided space for frontline perspectives, anchoring

the event in lived experience. The format combined plenary presentations, interactive tools (Slido), thematic panels and a multi-actor policy workshop and served as a key moment to launch and disseminate the FLIARA Toolkit and to underline the long-term role of the Community of Practice and Ambassador Network.

4.10.3.1 STRATEGIC DESIGN AND AGENDA DEVELOPMENT

Preparation of the Final Conference formally began in December 2024, following the framework established in D6.2. CE presented an initial outline of the event to the Project Coordinators at the University of Galway, identifying core objectives, priority themes and the overall narrative arc of the conference. Early discussions focused on aligning the event with Rural Women’s Week in October 2025, on positioning the conference as a bridge “from vision to action”, and on ensuring a strong role for the Policy Workshop (WP5) and the FLIARA Ambassadors (WP3) as central features of the programme.

Figure 31. Key elements of the Final Conference

A subsequent coordination meeting with work package leaders conducted by CE was used to refine the dissemination strategy and to co-create the structure of the programme. This iterative process ensured that all WPs were appropriately represented according to their expertise and that the agenda balanced scientific, policy and community-facing contributions. On this basis, CE developed the first complete draft of the agenda, enabling partners to start preparing their interventions and allowing the communications team to initiate promotion of the event. The final programme consolidated the thematic pillars, session structure, keynote framework and Ambassador and Policy Workshop segments, and all panels were designed to comply with the CoR’s gender-balance requirements.

Figure 32. Event structure

4.10.3.2 VENUE SELECTION AND INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

Once the thematic scope and structure of the conference had been agreed, CE explored potential venues within the EU institutional landscape in Brussels. Given the project's strong policy orientation, the European Committee of the Regions (CoR) emerged as an appropriate and strategic setting. The Municipality of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, through its Mayor and CoR member Carolina Darias San Sebastián, provided an official support letter endorsing the request to host the event at the CoR. A formal application was then submitted and accepted, allowing the project to hold the Final Conference in the Jacques Delors building (Room JDE 51) within a high-level European policy environment.

4.10.3.3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND OUTREACH

Throughout the preparatory period, project partners suggested key stakeholders and networks to be invited, while CE designed and implemented a targeted outreach and registration campaign. This included tailored stakeholder mapping to ensure participation from researchers, policymakers, practitioners, civil society organisations and rural innovation actors across Member States, as well as a user-tracking mailing system to monitor engagement and manage registrations. All registered participants received timely information and updates during the promotional stages, with confirmation emails linking to a dedicated conference page on the FLIARA website, which hosted practical details, programme information and logistical guidance.

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Dear {name} {surname},

We are delighted to invite you to the **Final Conference of the FLIARA project** (Female-led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas), taking place on **Friday, 17 October 2025**, from 09:00 to 17:00, at the **Jacques Delors Building (JDE), European Committee of the Regions**, Brussels.

The event will gather stakeholders from the **European Commission, DG AGRI**, academia, civil society, and innovation ecosystems to explore how inclusive, gender-responsive approaches can shape the future of rural and agricultural development and innovation in Europe.

Participants will have the opportunity to:

- Explore the findings of the FLIARA project on foresight and trend analysis, in-depth case studies, and policy recommendations.
- Join a **high-level policy workshop** focused on rural sustainability and gender-responsive governance.
- Attend **panel discussions**, expert insights, and testimonials from women leading innovation in farming and rural areas.
- Take part in **networking opportunities and exchanges** with peers, policymakers, and practitioners.

Only registered participants will be granted access to the venue – registration is open until 5 September 2025.

[Register Here](#)

[Agenda](#)

Add to your calendar!

[+ Add to Google Calendar](#)

[+ iCal / Outlook export](#)

We look forward to welcoming you to this timely and impactful event held during **Rural Women's Week**.

Best regards,
Maura Farrell, FLIARA Project Coordinator, on behalf of the FLIARA Project Partners.

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Dear {name} {surname},

Thank you for registering for the **FLIARA Final Conference**, which will take place on **Friday, 17 October 2025**, at the **European Committee of the Regions (Jacques Delors Building – JDE)** in Brussels, Belgium. We are pleased to confirm your participation in this full-day event.

The conference will run from **09:00 to 17:00** and will feature presentations from the European Commission, DG AGRI, FLIARA project leaders, innovation ambassadors, and invited experts. Participants will also take part in a high-level policy workshop and enjoy meaningful opportunities for networking during the event.

To help you prepare, you can access **all relevant information**, including the **agenda, venue details, and travel guidance**, below.

[More information](#)

We will follow up closer to the event with final logistics, badging instructions, and access information. Should you have any questions in the meantime, feel free to contact us at info@fliara.eu.

We look forward to welcoming you to Brussels in October.

Warm regards,
Maura Farrell, FLIARA Project Coordinator, on behalf of the FLIARA Project Partners.

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<p>Dear subscriber,</p> <p>The FLIARA Final Conference – Women Leading Rural Innovation: From Vision to Action took place last week, and it was a powerful event filled with valuable discussions, insights, and inspiring stories.</p> <p>We know not everyone could attend in person, so we're excited to share the complete resources from the conference with you. This is your opportunity to catch up on everything you missed!</p> <p>We are pleased to share the full video recordings of all sessions, as well as the presentation slides used throughout the conference.</p> <p>You can access all materials through the button below:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Recordings & Slides Click here</p> <p>Whether you would like to watch the keynote speech, dive into a specific panel discussion, or review the data from the presentations, these resources are packed with information on advancing women-led innovation in rural areas.</p> <p>Thank you for being a valued member of the FLIARA community. We hope these recordings help you take our shared journey from vision to action.</p> <p>Warm regards, The FLIARA Project Team</p> <p>Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</p> <p>PRIVACY POLICY CONTACT US ABOUT NEWS UNSUBSCRIBE</p> <p>Follow the project: f X in @ ▶</p> <p>2025 © All rights reserved</p>	
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Table 13. Mailing Campaign

As part of the outreach strategy, CE also implemented a targeted advertising campaign to promote the Final's Conference. Sponsored posts were deployed via the Meta platform (Facebook and Instagram) and LinkedIn, using the conference visual identity and key messages on women-led rural innovation, the Ambassadors' role and the link to Rural Women's Week (<https://www.instagram.com/p/DPI-8JpjNjy/>). The advertisements were directed to the dedicated conference landing page on the FLIARA website and were optimised to encourage registrations and livestream views (<https://fliara.eu/events/final-conference-women-leading-rural-innovation-from-vision-to-action/>).

Funded by
the European Union

Figure 33. Advertising campaign - FLIARA Final Conference

The four-month outreach campaign resulted in **155 registrations**. On the day, **107 participants attended in person**, representing a highly diverse audience in terms of geography, sector and institutional affiliation. In parallel, CE coordinated the promotion of the livestream through social media posts, reels and newsletters, highlighting the project's final results, the involvement of ambassadors and the policy relevance of the event. According to the CoR reporting, **229 users followed the conference live online**, significantly extending its reach beyond those present onsite.

4.10.3.4 OPERATIONAL MANAGEMENT AND POLICY WORKSHOP SUPPORT

CE was responsible for the end-to-end operational management of the conference. This included coordination of audiovisual systems, camera operation and technical delivery; the design and application of the project's visual identity across on-site materials (PowerPoint templates, backgrounds, bags, notebooks, pencils, banners, signage and boards); and real-time session management and troubleshooting to ensure smooth transitions and a professional environment for speakers and participants.

Figure 34. FLIARA Promotional Materials

CE also prepared event scripts, briefed the chair, catering and photographer, managed speaker logistics and rehearsal, and produced the FLIARA “Insights” magazine with the associated Ambassador profile interviews, 120 FLIARA Packs (a bag including pencil, notebooks and stickers) and the 2026 calendar, which were distributed at the conference.

	<p>FLIARA Magazine: https://www.calameo.com/books/0080949844353f0ee3ade</p>
	<p>FLIARA Calendar: https://www.calameo.com/books/0080949843a6c0f3ab2c9</p>

Table 14. FLIARA magazine and calendar

In addition, CE provided operational support to the Policy Workshop conducted under WP5 (TU Delft), which was integrated into the conference programme. This support covered the coordination of participants, preparation of table group configurations, allocation of identification tags by role, and alignment of workshop communications within the broader mailing workflows. This ensured that all participants were clearly

informed of their role in the workshop and that the exercise contributed effectively to the refinement and uptake of FLIARA's policy recommendations.

4.10.4 REPORT ON THE FINAL CONFERENCE

4.10.4.1 SETTING THE VISION FOR RURAL WOMEN'S FUTURES

Figure 35. Sally-Ann Barret

Conference Chair Sally-Ann Barrett from Freeway Media & Communications in Ireland opened the day by welcoming attendees onsite and online. She set an energetic and inclusive tone, inviting participants to engage actively through the Slido platform for questions and interactive exchanges. She reminded the audience that the conference was not only a celebration of achievements but also a moment of collective responsibility: to transform knowledge into action and to shape the next chapter for rural Europe.

Figure 36. Maura Farrell

Taking the stage for the opening address, Associate Professor Maura Farrell, FLIARA Project Coordinator from the University of Galway, reflected on the journey of the consortium and the inspiration behind it. She emphasised that innovation in rural areas cannot be fully realised unless women's voices, skills, and leadership are recognised and supported. Dr Farrell highlighted FLIARA's evidence base, including 20 case studies and 200 women innovators, and underlined that women's contributions span all four pillars of sustainability: social, cultural, economic and environmental. She also paid

tribute to the FLIARA Ambassadors, describing them as “the embodiment of innovation in action” and a driving force in raising visibility and mobilising communities across Europe.

The keynote address was delivered by María Gafo Gómez-Zamalloa, Acting Head of Unit for Social Sustainability at the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) of the European Commission. She placed the FLIARA results within the broader EU policy landscape, recalling that gender equality is a founding principle of the European Union and a growing priority within the Common Agricultural Policy. She stressed that although women remain under-represented in farming leadership, with fewer than 32% of EU farm managers being women, and only around 2% under the age of 40, EU initiatives and upcoming strategies are seeking to address these gaps. She affirmed that women’s innovation has the power to transform not only agri-food systems but entire rural communities and reiterated the need for structural support, better data, and gender-responsive policies.

Figure 37. María Gafo Gómez-Zamalloa

The opening session concluded with the first interactive input from the audience via Slido, inviting participants to answer in one word: “what change do rural women bring to innovation?” words filled the screen, capturing the spirit and expectations of the day ahead. With this shared enthusiasm, the FLIARA Final Conference moved into its first thematic session, transitioning from vision to evidence and from reflections to concrete results.

Q&A word cloud

slido

Figure 38. Slido and the audience

4.10.4.2 UNDERSTANDING WOMEN-LED INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

The first session of the conference shifted from vision to evidence, presenting the foundations of FLIARA's research and the systemic realities shaping women's innovation journeys across Europe. Building on the momentum of the opening session, this segment equipped the audience with a clearer understanding of why change is needed and where policy and practice must evolve.

Figure 39. Louise Weir

Figure 40. Tuomas Kuhmonen

Louise Weir, FLIARA Principal Project Manager at the University of Galway, opened the session by unveiling FLIARA's conceptual and analytical framework, which serves as the backbone for the project's policy recommendations. She emphasised that women in rural areas are not a homogenous group and that innovation pathways are deeply influenced by place, culture, norms and access to opportunity. Through an extensive review of

legislation, knowledge systems and policy environments across ten EU countries (Ireland, the Netherlands, Germany, Sweden, Slovenia, Czech Republic, Romania, Italy, Spain, and Finland), the project identified persistent barriers—from patriarchal norms to fragmented support services, that continue to hinder women-led innovation. Louise stressed the importance of building “flexible, evidence-based tools that address root causes, not symptoms”, highlighting benchmarking, gender-aware policy design and ecosystem thinking as essential elements for long-term transformation.

Next, Professor Tuomas Kuhmonen, Research Director at the Finland Futures Research Centre in the University of Turku in Finland, expanded the lens toward the future, presenting the project’s foresight study and an impressive body of stakeholder evidence. With over 560 participants and 300 proposed measures, the research revealed that women have strong potential to drive environmental and social innovation, yet face disproportionate obstacles in economic, technological and political spheres. Kuhmonen underscored that the most effective levers for change are social measures, particularly networks, platforms for co-creation, visibility, and peer support, noting that “there is no single silver bullet; networks are needed everywhere.” His findings reinforced the dual message of the session: women are already key innovators, and systemic change must match their ambition.

Figure 41. Blátnaid Gallagher

To ground the research in lived experience, FLIARA Ambassador Blátnaid Gallagher delivered an energising reflection that resonated strongly in the room. Drawing on her journey as a farmer, cooperative founder and community leader, she painted a vivid picture of both the challenges and the untapped potential of rural women. Blátnaid called for “one central portal” to simplify access to information and funding for female entrepreneurs, urged policymakers to break the “silos” that isolate rural innovators, and highlighted the need to build stronger rural–urban bridges to scale enterprises beyond the local level. She reaffirmed the transformative power of visibility, “if you can see it, you can be it” and highlighted how engaging in FLIARA activities and the Community of Practice has helped women feel connected, supported and seen. Her intervention earned heartfelt applause and anchored the session in the human reality behind the data: determined, resilient and future-focused rural women who need systems that work with them.

With a shared understanding of the challenges and opportunities now clearly laid out, the conference transitioned to the heart of the FLIARA story: the women driving change on the ground and the policy frameworks needed to support them. Session 2 would turn these insights into concrete pathways for action.

4.10.4.3 PATHWAYS, CHALLENGES AND LEADERSHIP IN WOMEN-LED RURAL INNOVATION

The second session shifted the focus from vision to evidence. After hearing the policy landscape, the room turned its attention to the findings emerging from the heart of the FLIARA project: the lived realities of women innovators across Europe. Associate Professor Silvia Sivini, Sociologist at the University of Calabria in Italy, presented the results of 20 national case studies, 200 women, and a research journey spanning 10 countries, four sustainability dimensions, and diverse rural typologies. Her presentation set the tone for one of the conference's most human-centred and inspiring moments.

Silvia explained that FLIARA set out to understand how women innovate, what enables them, what slows them down, and what systems must change. The research explored three interconnected layers: innovation pathways, innovation ecosystems, and mainstreaming potential. Across regions, from the Mediterranean to the Baltic, stories varied, but the patterns were strikingly consistent.

Figure 42. Silvia Sivini

Women were found to be drivers of sustainability, not only in environmental leadership (with 97% of interviewees integrating ecological principles into their innovation) but also in creating social value, reviving cultural heritage, and strengthening local economies. They built multifunctional farms, circular-economy initiatives, social enterprises, educational programmes, and place-based tourism experiences, often using digital tools to overcome geographic isolation.

Yet, Sivini noted, the barriers were equally systemic: limited access to finance and land, persistent gender stereotypes, bureaucratic complexity, lack of tailored training, and insufficient policy coordination. Many women reported experiencing imposter syndrome

at the beginning of their journey. Others were considered “crazy” for proposing new ideas in male-led environments but succeeded through resilience, networks, and community trust. Her conclusion was clear: women are innovating against the current, not with it, and policy must catch up.

Following the research presentation, Sarah Khoudja, FLIARA Ambassador for Italy and entrepreneur, delivered a sharp and memorable reflection. Her message was simple: “innovation doesn’t wait for committees. We must break the bureaucratic chain. Women with an idea should be able to act quickly, without procedures that drain time, energy and hope.”

Figure 43. Sarah Khoudja

She urged European, national and regional institutions to simplify access to funding, arguing that many female innovators have the vision but not the administrative armour that current systems demand. Her words set the stage for the session’s core moment: the ambassador roundtable.

4.10.4.4 VOICES FROM THE GROUND: THE AMBASSADORS’ ROUNDTABLE

If the morning presentations offered evidence, structure and data, the ambassadors’ roundtable brought life, emotion and urgency into the room. The atmosphere shifted the moment the five FLIARA ambassadors took the floor, women who are not only innovators but also voices of their territories. In Brussels, their reflections became one of the most applauded and moving moments of the entire conference.

The panel opened with a simple premise: what does it really take for a woman to innovate in rural Europe? What followed was not a technical debate but a shared human journey across Sweden, Finland, Ireland, Romania and beyond.

Alexandra Larsson from Sweden: “we need to stop designing systems for big companies and expecting small rural women to survive in them.”

Alexandra, a driving school owner who has just become the first woman in her region licensed to train motorbike drivers, spoke candidly about the burden rural entrepreneurs face once they hire their first employee. Her voice was steady, but her message was sharp: “the moment you employ someone, responsibility explodes, but the support does not. We need systems designed for us, not for corporations with hr departments.” Her intervention highlighted what many nodded to: innovation is not only vision, it is paperwork, time, bureaucracy, accounting and sacrifice, and women are carrying that load on top of childcare, community pressure and unpaid care work.

Figure 44. Alexandra Larsson

Rita Porkka from Finland: “Transparency is the first form of fairness.” From northern Europe, Rita brought a different but equally revealing perspective. She runs a nature-based education initiative and spoke about the hidden walls rural women face, not only financial but also cultural: “even today, decisions about funding and development can happen in closed circles. transparency and clarity should be rights, not privileges.” Her calm delivery carried a powerful idea: if rules were clear, accessible and transparent, half of the barriers would disappear before women even asked for support.

Figure 45. Ritta Porkka

Anca Veronica Marcu from Romania: “Listen to women first. They already know what their community needs.” A former teacher and now mayor, Anca shared her experience as one of the very few women in political leadership in rural Romania. Instead of focusing

on confrontation, she chose a message of dignity and constructive change: “women don’t need more obstacles or more complexity. they need institutions that listen, simplify and accompany. when women have tools, communities move forward.” her words, soft but resolute, earned a warm round of applause. she reminded the room that policy is not abstract, policy is felt in kitchens, in schools, in farms, and in daily life.

Figure 46. Anca Veronica Marcu

Ursula Kelly from Ireland: “Networks are not a luxury. They are oxygen.” Ursula, as a rural entrepreneur and vocal advocate for women in farming, delivered one of the strongest messages of the session. For her, the conclusion is clear: “women innovate when they feel supported. networks create confidence. confidence unlocks innovation. if policymakers want results, fund the networks.” She called for continued European investment in rural development and women-led initiatives, insisting that projects like FLIARA must have a “day after”, not an end point. The audience responded with one of the loudest applauses of the day.

Figure 47. Ursula Kelly

Patricia Marina Toma from Romania: “When women tell their stories, other women rise.” Closing the panel, Patricia, an artist and cultural activist, brought emotion to the surface. She spoke of storytelling as a tool of transformation: “I arrived at FLIARA doubting whether my voice mattered. Now I leave knowing that sharing our stories is part of

changing our communities.” Her words landed in a moment of collective silence, followed by applause that felt less like recognition and more like solidarity.

Across five very different journeys, a single message emerged: Women in rural Europe are not asking for permission, they are asking for access. Access to clear information. Access to funding. Access to networks. Access to dignity and visibility. The roundtable ended not in despair, but in determination. The ambassadors proved that innovation is not only a policy goal, it is a lived, daily act of resilience and imagination. This session became a turning point in the conference rhythm: from research to reality, from findings to responsibility.

Figure 48. Patricia Marina Toma

4.10.4.5 FROM RESEARCH TO POLICY: TURNING EVIDENCE INTO ACTION

The third session of the FLIARA Final Conference marked a decisive shift in focus. After a morning dedicated to uncovering evidence, experiences, and lived realities, the spotlight turned to a central question: How can Europe transform knowledge into policy that delivers real change for rural women innovators? The session brought together researchers and policymakers to connect dots, bridge gaps, and offer concrete pathways from findings to implementation.

Figure 49. Aisling Murtagh

Dr Aisling Murtagh, FLIARA postdoctoral researcher at the University of Galway, opened the session by introducing one of the most technical yet crucial elements of the project’s policy legacy: gender benchmarking. In clear and measured language, she explained that benchmarking, in the FLIARA context, was not a bureaucratic spreadsheet exercise but a strategic tool to expose gaps, compare systems, and drive accountability. Benchmarking, she suggested, becomes powerful only when it goes beyond “ticking boxes” to identify what truly works on the ground, where barriers persist, and where policy ambition fails to translate into practice.

She reminded the audience that FLIARA had mapped existing policy frameworks, analysed gaps across Member States, and distilled women’s real-world experiences into benchmark criteria aligned with the EU Gender Equality Strategy. The result: a framework that could help policymakers evaluate whether policy measures genuinely address women’s needs in rural innovation or merely appear to do so. But benchmarking alone was not the destination. “It must be part of a wider policy toolbox,” she stressed, “and it must work alongside impact assessments, gender audits, and participatory policy design.” She remarked: Europe has tools, now it must use them with intention.

From there, the session moved seamlessly into the policy landscape, with Professor Willem Korthals Altes from Delft University of Technology translating the project’s findings into a tangible blueprint for decision-makers. His core argument was disarmingly simple: rural women cannot innovate inside systems that are not designed for them. To fix this, he laid out FLIARA’s now well-recognised model of seven enabling networks, the invisible infrastructures that shape a woman’s capacity to succeed: social networks, financial-safety networks, work–life systems, economic networks, advisory networks, learning networks, and political networks.

Figure 50. Willem Korthals Altes

Policy, he argued, must stop treating women’s barriers as individual weaknesses and instead strengthen the systems around them. Whether through childcare solutions, gender-responsive advisory services, access to finance, local procurement channels, or genuine representation in decision-making spaces, these seven networks offered policymakers a practical map for catalytic change. He reminded participants that the project’s 60 policy briefs and forthcoming booklet were not theoretical documents but instructions for action—tools ready for use at local, regional, national, and EU levels.

Figure 51. Gerdy Verschuuren-Stoop

To wrap up the policy block, Assistant Professor Gerdy Verschuuren-Stoop from Delft University of Technology took the floor to guide participants into the afternoon’s Policy Workshop, where everyone, including ambassadors, policymakers, civil society, and researchers, would co-create European-level recommendations. “After today,” she smiled, “you will not only have attended FLIARA, but you will also be part of it.” Her intervention served as a bridge: the discussion would not end at the plenary level but continue in working rooms where ideas would be transformed into concrete proposals.

Before closing the session, attention returned to the lived experiences of women innovators themselves. FLIARA Ambassador Linda Kelly from Germany shared her journey as an organic farmer who has developed and directly marketed sweet lupines, an innovation that was initially unfamiliar to consumers. She reflected on the long process of building awareness and trust around a new product, stressing that personal

belief, sustained energy and resilience were essential throughout the journey. Kelly underlined the importance of family support as a stabilising factor, particularly when facing inevitable setbacks. She also emphasised that innovation does not depend on knowing everything in advance, but on knowing whom to turn to for advice and support. In this context, she highlighted the value of strong and trusted networks, noting that participation in the FLIARA community had provided access to knowledge, encouragement and peer support. Her intervention reinforced the broader message that women in rural areas benefit significantly from mutual support, authenticity and resilient networks that enable innovation to grow over time.

Figure 52. Linda Kelly

Finally, as the session concluded, another ambassador, Sonja Jokiranta from Finland, voiced a question that resonated across the room: “if a regional authority with limited resources can only focus on one area first, which network would have the biggest impact for women innovators?” Willem’s answer was immediate: start with political networks and gender mainstreaming. If every policy begins with a gender-responsive mindset, he argued, all other networks become easier to repair. It was a fitting closure, concise, strategic, and rooted in structural change.

Figure 53. Sonja Jokiranta

With that, Session 3 ended: research had been transformed into a policy roadmap, and ambassadors had once again ensured that the policies discussed remained connected to real lives, real challenges, and real ambitions.

4.10.4.6 RETHINKING RURAL INNOVATION: GENDER, SUSTAINABILITY AND ECOSYSTEMS

The afternoon panel, “Rethinking Rural Innovation, Gender, Sustainability and Ecosystems”, marked a decisive shift in the conference narrative—from presenting evidence to confronting the systemic conditions that either enable or obstruct women-led innovation in rural Europe. Moderated by Michelle Perello, Chief Executive Officer at CE, the session brought together seven voices from EU networks, sister projects, academia, policymaking, and the European commission. What emerged was a clear message: innovation in rural regions is not only a technological or economic process — it is social, cultural, relational, and deeply gendered. And unless governance structures recognise this reality, inequalities will continue to reproduce themselves under the label of “innovation”.

Figure 54. Rethinking Rural Innovation, Gender, Sustainability and Ecosystems

Opening the exchange, David Lamb, team leader of the CAP implementation contact point, EU cap network, underscored the transformative role of networks in surfacing and scaling promising practices. With more than 600 projects linked to jobs, growth and equality in their database, Lamb highlighted that the demand for gender-sensitive innovation is real, and growing, across member states. The CAP Network's awards and calls for inspiring initiatives demonstrate that visibility and example-setting matter: when women innovators are showcased, more women step forward.

Figure 55. David Lamb

From a practitioner's perspective, Lorena van de Kolk, Coordinator of the Gender Alliance for Innovation in Agriculture (GAIA) and leader of the agri-food team in Brussels of Schuttelaar & Partners, emphasised the power of peer learning, safe spaces, and cross-border connection. Through her GAIA network, she witnesses daily how women

advance faster when they can exchange failures as openly as successes. Innovation, she argued, is “born in the field, in families and cooperatives, not only in labs”, and therefore networks must empower women as subjects of innovation, not supporting actors. Her contribution reinforced a core insight: innovation ecosystems thrive when women can connect, be visible, and be believed.

Figure 56. Lorena van de Kolk

A deeper structural critique came from Graeme Dean, who coordinates the SWIFT project, who challenged the economic reductionism that still dominates rural policy. If innovation continues to be measured only in growth, export potential, and scalability, thousands of women-led innovations, especially in agroecology and community-rooted models, will remain undervalued or invisible. Graeme stressed the soft conditions necessary for innovation to flourish: emotional support, confidence, social acceptance, and protection from stigma.

Figure 57. Graeme Dean

He pointed to historic structural inequalities, arguing that without recognising the reproductive and community labour that women perform, “the labour that sustains everything, yet appears in no budget line”, policy will keep misdiagnosing the problem. His intervention made the room visibly pause and consider innovation will be sustained if the women driving it are socially unsupported and institutionally unseen.

Figure 58. Professor Sally Shortall

The governance gap was then addressed by Professor Sally Shortall, Project Coordinator of Grass Ceiling, who offered a clear diagnosis: gender equality is still treated as an optional add-on in rural policy, instead of a requirement. While acknowledging progress through specific measures, she warned that mainstreaming has largely failed. “Unless it is compulsory in the cap regulation, it will not be prioritised by member states,” she argued, drawing on extensive comparative research.

Professor Shortall also warned against a one-size-fits-all entrepreneurial model. Many women-led innovations do not aim to employ ten people or conquer export markets, and policy must stop penalising those who innovate at a local scale in community-based and low-growth models that generate social value and territorial resilience. “Support must adapt to women’s realities, not the other way around.”

Irish MEP Maria Walsh brought a candid political perspective to the panel, underscoring that policy, funding, and leadership cannot be separated when addressing gender inequalities in rural innovation. She stressed that data remains the critical missing piece, noting that European and national institutions “lean on data to act”, yet current information on rural women, their needs, and their economic participation is still fragmented or insufficient.

Figure 59. MEP Maria Walsh

Walsh voiced frustration at persistent imbalances: women represent 40% of Europe's entrepreneurs, yet receive less than 1% of available capital, a contradiction she labelled "simply a formula that does not add up." She also criticised rigid funding models that only reward high-growth, export-oriented ventures, leaving those who wish to innovate locally with little support. Entrepreneurs who want to remain embedded in their region, she argued, "should not be punished for choosing to serve their community instead of scaling."

Reflecting on shifting political tides in Europe, Walsh warned of a growing risk-averse policy environment, cuts in key funding streams, and the rise of more conservative positions on gender. The next 18 months, she said, will be decisive for securing ring-fenced measures for generational renewal, women farmers, and gender equality within the CAP, "it cannot be a nice-to-have, it must be a need-to-have," she insisted.

She also spoke from personal experience as a farmer, describing everyday gender dynamics that remain deeply rooted in culture, not only in policy. Despite humour, her message was sharp: rural women are still expected to shoulder more responsibility, with less support, fewer resources, and structural barriers that slow or silence their contribution. Yet these same women drive household decisions, purchasing power, and rural vitality, a paradox she said must be corrected through networks, investment, and political will.

Figure 60. Magdalena Mach

Bringing the institutional perspective of the European Commission, Magdalena Mach, Policy Officer in the Research & Innovation Unit of the European Commission's DG Agriculture and Rural Development, highlighted that women have much to gain from EU innovation instruments, particularly Operational Groups under EIP-Agri, which allow 100% funding coverage, advance payments, and multi-actor cooperation. She stressed that women's natural strengths in collaboration, networking and problem-solving make them well-suited to lead such initiatives. However, she also pointed out that access depends on awareness and confidence. The tool exists, the challenge is ensuring women feel entitled to use it.

Figure 61. Associate Professor Maura Farrell

Closing the panel, Dr Maura Farrell (FLIARA Coordinator) drew the threads together. Her message was clear: Women are not asking for permission to innovate, they are already innovating. What they need is an enabling environment that recognises diverse ambitions (from small-scale to export-driven), values care and community and includes women in every level of governance. She reminded the room that the success of women innovators is never individual, it is collective, supported by families, communities and networks. Future rural policy must reflect that social reality.

This panel did not simply “rethink” rural innovation, it reframed it. It exposed the mismatch between how innovation is lived by women on the ground and how it is too often governed from above. It called for a shift from programmes that support projects to policies that transform systems. The path forward is now evident: innovation in rural Europe will only be sustainable, inclusive and effective when women are not an afterthought in the ecosystem but its architects.

4.10.4.7 BUILDING FLIARA'S LEGACY: NETWORKS, RESOURCES AND COLLECTIVE ACTION

Knowledge only becomes transformative when it is shared, applied and sustained. With this principle, Session 4 focused on how FLIARA's results will live beyond the project's timeline—through strong networks, practical tools and the continuing leadership of its ambassadors.

Anastasia Oprea from ECOLISE opened the session by presenting the evolution of the FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP), a cornerstone of the project's legacy strategy led by the University of Galway team. She highlighted how the community was built through a combination of online exchanges, four regional in-person workshops, policy dialogues and an ongoing support structure for ambassadors. The approach, she emphasised, was not merely to “involve” women in activities but to empower them as co-creators: “a group of people who share a purpose and shape it together in practice.”

Figure 62. Anastasia Oprea

Through this framework, ambassadors gained visibility, built confidence, exchanged knowledge and developed peer support circles that extend far beyond formal project tasks. Anastasia noted that FLIARA's co-creation method, its ambassador spotlighting, wellbeing safeguards and iterative feedback loops created trust, the essential ingredient for real empowerment.

Figure 63. FLIARA Ambassadors round of applause

The legacy dimension continued with Victor R. Martínez, EU Communications Manager for FLIARA at Consulta Europa in Spain, who presented the FLIARA Toolkit, now publicly available as a long-term resource. Designed as an open, user-friendly repository, the Toolkit consolidates the project's knowledge, from conceptual frameworks and research findings to innovation cards, policy outputs and multimedia materials. Martínez emphasised that its purpose goes beyond archiving: it is meant to inspire action, support learning, enable replication and strengthen women-led innovation ecosystems.

Figure 64. Victor R. Martínez

Hosted on the FLIARA website for the next two years, the Toolkit allows users to explore more than 200 innovation profiles, filter cases, access deliverables, and navigate guidance materials in a visually engaging and practical way. It also anchors the project's policy legacy, hosting briefs, workshop outputs and upcoming post-project materials. "It is a living resource," Martínez stressed, "not a final chapter."

Figure 65. Mieke Elzenga

To bring these elements back to lived experience, FLIARA Ambassador, Mieke Elzenga from the Netherlands, offered a grassroots perspective on legacy. Speaking about her journey and the bonds formed through FLIARA, she stressed that networks only create impact when they nurture relationships, trust and continuity. She shared how ambassadors are already co-developing Erasmus+ proposals, supporting each other's initiatives and engaging policymakers at local and national levels, including a recent visit by ministry representatives to her eco-village. For Elzenga, legacy means doing, not merely documenting: "We must connect the local, the regional, the national and the European levels. Only then can innovation truly move and grow."

The session concluded with a short Q&A, including a reflection from Dr Murtagh on the role of rural planning and sustainability challenges raised through the research. From the audience, she acknowledged that planning barriers and land-use constraints are recurring obstacles across Europe and confirmed that these themes will continue to inform the project's ongoing policy work as sustainability frameworks are refined.

4.10.4.8 FROM VISION TO IMPLEMENTATION: EMBEDDING GENDER EQUALITY IN EU RURAL INNOVATION

The final panel of the conference shifted the conversation from ideas to action, gathering high-level voices from EU institutions, networks, academia, and civil society. Moderated by Sally-Ann Barrett, the discussion explored one guiding question: how can Europe ensure that women-led rural innovation becomes a permanent, resourced and visible part of EU policy, not an exception, but the norm?

Figure 66. Marion Eckardt

Marion Eckardt, Head of ELARD Knowledge Hub, European LEADER Association for Rural Development, opened with a practical message from the ground. Drawing on her experience with Local Action Groups across Europe, she stressed that LEADER- and community-led local development (CLLD) remain powerful yet underused tools for women innovators. She emphasised the capacity of local networks to build mentoring structures, solve care-related barriers collectively and fund small first steps that “make the difference between an idea and a viable project.” However, she warned that the next programming period risks prioritising “hard, measurable outputs” over community-building, a shift she described as “a masculine logic that overlooks the social infrastructure innovation needs to flourish.”

Figure 67. Tara Farrell

Building on this, Tara Farrell, Chief Executive Officer from Longford Women’s Link in Ireland, argued that visibility must translate into power and continuity. The ambassadors, she said, had proven their effectiveness as role models, connectors and agenda-shapers, but they must now be formally embedded into policy ecosystems, not left as a “project output”. Tara highlighted the need for accessible resources, storytelling

platforms and political pathways, stating that “we cannot hashtag women one day and return to business as usual the next.” Her message was clear: normalising women’s leadership in rural areas is a political choice, and Europe must choose it.

Figure 68. Pascale Van Doren

From an EU support perspective, Pascale Van Doren, Team Leader of the Rural Pact Support Office, underlined the role of the Rural Pact in amplifying women’s voices through collaboration, knowledge exchange and policy advocacy. She stressed that shared ownership, across EU, national and local levels, is essential to embed gender equality in future strategies. Van Doren also insisted on better data and monitoring, noting that without gender-sensitive evidence, policymaking risks reinforcing existing gaps rather than closing them. She reminded the audience that networks like the rural pact community group on women in rural areas are now active platforms where women can influence EU agendas but warned that political commitment and follow-through remain crucial.

Figure 69. Alexia Rouby

Turning to EU strategy, Alexia Rouby, Coordinator of Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA), connected the panel to the LTVRA and the EU Rural Action Plan. She acknowledged both the innovation potential of rural women and the structural barriers

that push many to leave rural territories. Rouby noted that EU instruments already exist, from CAP to research, startup support, care-strategy measures and rural innovation policies, but called for stronger integration of gender and rural lenses so that policies “work together, not in parallel.” She welcomed FLIARA’s timing and stated that its evidence and foresight will feed into the upcoming update of the Rural Action Plan, including innovation-focused actions.

Figure 70. Hannu I. Heikkinen

Bringing a research perspective, Hannu I. Heikkinen, Professor of Cultural Anthropology, University of Oulu, reflected on patterns emerging from the project’s fieldwork. He noted that many women-led innovations are clustered in “social, care, wellbeing and community-driven sectors”; areas that current financial and subsidy systems often fail to recognise as innovation. As a result, women’s contributions remain undervalued, under-resourced and under-reported. Heikkinen urged policymakers to rethink how innovation is defined and supported and argued that EU projects should systematically include “afterlife plans” to sustain networks like those created by FLIARA, instead of letting them dissolve once funding ends.

Figure 71. Serafin Pazos-Vidal

Finally, Serafin Pazos-Vidal, Rural Policy and Governance Expert at the European Association for Innovation in Local Development and representing the Grass Ceiling Project, brought the discussion back to governance. He highlighted RURAL PROOFING

and multi-level governance as essential tools to ensure that gender equality and women-led innovation are embedded in the implementation of the Long-Term Vision. Policy, he stressed, must operate “from Brussels to local councils” and must be backed by indicators capable of tracking gender outcomes, otherwise “we will continue to fund intentions instead of results.” He also encouraged the FLIARA community to remain engaged beyond the project, noting that the months ahead, with CAP reform talks and a revision of key EU frameworks, are a window of opportunity.

Together, the panellists converged on a single conclusion: The knowledge, talent and innovation of women in rural areas is not a niche, it is a structural necessity for Europe’s future. To unlock it, policy must embrace visibility, resources, networks, care infrastructure, fair funding models and gender-sensitive governance. This panel set the tone for the conference’s final message: FLIARA has shown the way, now implementation must follow.

4.10.4.9 FROM SHARED REFLECTIONS TO A SHARED RESPONSIBILITY

The conference concluded with a synthesis of the workshop outcomes and a forward-looking message on FLIARA’s legacy. Assistant Professor Gerdy Verschuure-Stuip and Professor Willem Korthals Altes opened the final session by presenting the collective insights gathered across fourteen workshop tables. Despite the diversity of perspectives in the room, the results were strikingly coherent. Participants stressed that supporting women in rural innovation requires system thinking, not silo thinking, connecting farming, care, sustainability, entrepreneurship, education, and community life as interdependent components of rural development rather than isolated policy streams.

Across groups, several recurring needs emerged. First, participants highlighted work–life balance and care infrastructure as foundational enablers of women’s participation. Without accessible childcare and fair distribution of care duties, innovation potential is constrained long before a business plan is written. Second, many tables pointed to the shortcomings of rigid administrative systems, which too often fail to reflect the realities of women-led initiatives. From the limitations of LEADER eligibility to bureaucratic fragmentation across departments, participants called for more agile, place-sensitive funding and advisory systems. A third shared message concerned capacity, confidence and representation: role models matter, and not only “iconic” ambassadors, but also everyday role models at different stages of their journey (junior, emerging, senior). Participants also urged stronger awareness among advisors and mentors, along with better gender-disaggregated data to track progress. Finally, and powerfully, every group raised the issue of continuity: networks such as the one built by FLIARA are too valuable to dissolve at the end of a grant. Ensuring after-life strategies must become a condition, not an afterthought, of future rural and innovation programmes.

Figure 72. Presentation of Workshop Results

The room responded warmly to the workshop summary: the knowledge is clear, the momentum is real, and the responsibility to act now sits with institutions, funders, regions and communities alike.

4.10.4.10 FROM RESULTS TO RESPONSIBILITY

To close the event, FLIARA Project Coordinator Dr Maura Farrell delivered a reflective and compelling final address. She began by thanking the speakers, partners, ambassadors, sister projects, political hosts, and the European institutions that believed in the project. Her gratitude extended to the consortium and especially the women whose stories shaped every insight: “They were not participants. They were partners.”

Figure 73. Closing Remarks

Dr Farrell reminded the room that gender equality in rural areas is not merely a project goal but a European legal and democratic commitment. Yet FLIARA’s evidence shows a persistent gap between principle and practice. Across Europe, women are driving

sustainability, diversifying economies, and strengthening communities—but without equal access to land, finance, recognition, decision-making power, or care supports, their contributions remain undervalued and under-resourced.

She called on policymakers to take FLIARA’s evidence forward by embedding gender equality in rural proofing, CAP implementation, and post-2025 strategies. Women, she argued, should not merely be visible in rural policy but central to its design. Reflecting on the ambassadors and case study women, she stressed their proven impact even with limited support, adding: “imagine what these women could achieve if they were fully supported through gender-responsive rural development, access to land and finance, and a more inclusive common agricultural policy.”

Ending on a symbolic note, she echoed the words of former Irish President Mary Robinson: “women of Ireland, instead of rocking the cradle, you have rocked the system.” Dr Farrell affirmed that the women connected through FLIARA are doing exactly that across Europe, and that their work will not end with the project.

The event closed with an invitation for a final group photograph, an image that captured the spirit of the day: ambassadors, researchers, policymakers, practitioners and supporters standing together as a community, not a collection of sectors. The conference ended slightly over time, not because of delay, but because there was more to say, more to share, and more still to do. Conference materials and recordings are available at www.fliara.eu/live.

Figure 74. Group picture

5. EXPLOITATION

5.1. EXPLOITABLE RESULTS AND ROADMAP

The FLIARA project produced several exploitable results. The following table outlines each one of them:

WPs	Result to be exploited	Comment
WP1	Conceptual framework; Case Study Assessment and Selection Framework; Assessment of policy and legal frameworks to support policy benchmarking.	Dedicated activities, encompassing tasks 1.1 to 1.5, will be carried out as part of the Contextual Concepts and Assessment Frameworks in WP1. These activities will seek to enhance the current conceptual and practical understanding of women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas. To achieve this, a roadmap has been developed, outlining the actions necessary to foster synergies and networking.
WP2	Envisioning Process, Innovation Process and the Assessment Process.	An Envisioning Process has been undertaken in WP2, fostering collaboration and synergies with a wide range of stakeholders who possess the capacity to plan and shape the future. These stakeholders include local farmers, entrepreneurs, policy makers, active citizens, representatives of NGOs, development, and advisory organisations, as well as research and educational institutions who possess intimate knowledge of agriculture and rural areas in the different national contexts of the project. The aim is to capture insights, perspectives, and expertise from various sectors and regions to form a solid foundation for the project's exploitation of results, as it ensures that the developed innovations and strategies are relevant, practical, and scalable across different national contexts within the European Union.
WP3	The Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection Methodology and the Comparative Analysis of the Case Studies by Country and Sustainability Innovation Dimension.	In WP3, the FLIARA project will undertake a comprehensive analysis of women-led and gendered innovations in farming and rural communities. Under tasks 3.1 and 3.4, the project will engage directly with 200 female innovators and entrepreneurs across ten different EU countries to uncover valuable insights, lessons, and success stories from these innovative women, which can then serve as a pathway to enhance the capacity of other rural and farm women to engage in similar innovative practices. The insights gathered from this analysis will inform future policies, initiatives, and capacity-building efforts.
WP4	Community of Practice Network and Toolkit.	In WP4, the FLIARA project will implement a multi-actor approach through the establishment of the FLIARA Community of Practice Network. In particular, Task 4.2 will focus on the execution of the four networking events, which will bring together relevant stakeholders, including the selected 20 innovation ambassadors, serving as platforms to engage with key actors currently involved in rural and farming innovation. Task 4.3 is closely linked to this, as it involves all partners in

		benchmarking EU and National policy and Legal Framework during the events. This will be achieved through focus groups and workshops where the findings will be discussed, and key issues will be identified to be brought forward to policy design and assessment workshops. Furthermore, Tasks T4.4 and T4.5 will result in the creation of the FLIARA Toolkit, a user-friendly digital repository for transferring project generated knowledge to inspire both current innovative practitioners and future generations of innovative rural women.
WP5	Policy Booklet (Policy Recommendations).	In WP5, the FLIARA project aims to design more effective policy, legal, and governance knowledge and innovation systems, that will support and promote women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. Task 5.2 plays a crucial role in this process by engaging users and experts to explore the lessons learned and outcomes achieved throughout the FLIARA project. Task 5.3 is also relevant for exploitation purposes as it focuses on the development of new policy proposals based on the project's results. A supportive and inclusive policy framework will be created for replication to facilitate women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.

Table 15. Exploitation Routes

All the outcomes mentioned above will be made available to stakeholders at no cost, ensuring wide accessibility. The distribution of these results will be coordinated by the project partners and overseen by WP6, responsible for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation. Various digital channels will be utilised, including the project website and open-access platforms, social media platforms, direct emails to regional stakeholders, targeted promotion to female innovators in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union, scientific papers, abstracts, organised events, and newsletters.

The FLIARA consortium will regularly evaluate the project's outcomes to determine if additional results should be exploited, ensuring their inclusion in future updates of this deliverable. More concrete actions for long-term sustainability of FLIARA results will be agreed among the consortium towards the end of the project.

5.2. TARGET USERS FOR EXPLOITATION

The successful exploitation of FLIARA's research work hinges on the identification and engagement of target users. Throughout the project's duration, dissemination activities laid the foundation for exploitation by fostering a robust network of stakeholders and maintaining their involvement in FLIARA's initiatives. Consequently, the identified target audiences served as prime targets for exploitation efforts, as they are the most likely to exhibit interest in and derive value from the project's results.

FLIARA aims to maximise the impact and reach of its outcomes through:

- 🏛️ **Governments and policy makers:** Collaboration with governmental bodies and decision makers / policy makers will facilitate the integration of FLIARA's findings into policy frameworks, driving positive change in agricultural and rural sectors while also considering gender-based perspectives. An active involvement of policy makers in several actions of the project will facilitate the alignment of FLIARA's recommendations with existing policies, strengthening their implementation and impact.
- 🏛️ **Innovation Support Services:** Close cooperation with innovation support services will enable the translation of research into practical applications and promote the adoption of innovative practices.
- 🏛️ **Academia and scientific communities:** Engagement of academic institutions will foster knowledge exchange, scholarly contributions, and the incorporation of FLIARA's research outcomes into educational curricula. Collaboration with the scientific community will foster peer-reviewed publications, research collaborations, and the validation of FLIARA's findings.
- 🏛️ **Civil Society:** Engaging civil society organisations will help disseminate the project's results to wider audiences, raising awareness and promoting inclusive dialogue on gender equality in agriculture and rural areas.
- 🏛️ **Farming Community and Rural Society at Large:** The farming community and rural society are at the heart of FLIARA's mission. By directly engaging with farmers, rural entrepreneurs, and local communities, the project aims to empower and support their innovative initiatives, ensuring the practical applicability of its outcomes.

Through targeted dissemination and exploitation strategies, FLIARA seek to harness the collective potential of these key user groups, driving sustainable and inclusive development in agriculture and rural areas across the European Union.

5.3 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPR) AND OPEN SCIENCE STRATEGY

5.3.1 IPR MANAGEMENT AND PROTECTION OF RESULTS

The FLIARA project recognised the critical importance of managing Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in strict accordance with the rules established in the GA and CA, adhering to Horizon Europe principles. The project completed an assessment of all anticipated Key Exploitable Results (KERs) over its lifespan to formalise their exploitation potential and integrate IPR management into the final version of this Deliverable (D6.3).

Given FLIARA's overarching goal of promoting and supporting women-led innovation in rural setting without undue restrictions, the IPR strategy prioritised open access and wide dissemination.

5.3.2 IP MANAGEMENT MEASURES AND STRATEGY

The management of IPR focused on a strategic balance between author recognition and maximising public utility.

1. **Prioritisation of Open Access:** The primary strategy was to avoid any measures that would unduly restrict access or use, including for commercial purposes. The consortium prioritised open access through the strategic application of appropriate Creative Commons (CC) licences to all identified KERs.
2. **Copyright:** Copyright automatically protects all original works generated by the project. However, the consortium's approach was to actively encourage the sharing and adaptation of these works through open licensing, ensuring protection for the creators' moral rights (right to be credited).
3. **IPR Checklist:** An IPR checklist was implemented, requiring publishing partners to confirm that their materials did not contain pre-existing exploitable content that would conflict with the project's open access goals.
4. **IPR Barriers:** The assessment confirmed there will be no IPR barriers to the continued use of project materials by end-users after the project's completion, ensuring future sustainability.
5. **Long-Term Transfer:** To facilitate continued availability and support, it is anticipated that the project website and associated materials may be transferred to the European Commission or to a follow-on project supporting women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.

5.3.3 FORMALISING LICENSING DECISIONS

The selection of the most suitable Creative Commons licence was determined based on the nature and characteristics of each KER, always prioritising maximum reach and impact in line with FLIARA's objectives.

The standard licensing decision for all core project outputs (including reports, publications, and data) **was set as CC BY 4.0 (Attribution)**, as confirmed under D6.1. This permissive license promotes maximum sharing and reuse, even for commercial purposes, provided proper attribution is given. The use of a **CC BY-SA 4.0 (Attribution-ShareAlike)** licence was also considered for methodological tools where the consortium wanted to ensure that any future derivative works remain equally open. All finalised licensing decisions were clearly documented via templates and communicated to all partners.

License Button	Description of the License
Attribution (CC BY) 	This license allows others to distribute, modify, and expand upon the work, even for commercial purposes, as long as they provide credit for the original creation. This is the project's most permissive default.
Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY-SA) 	This license allows others to modify and build upon the work, even commercially, provided they credit the creator and license their new creations under the identical terms . It ensures that all derivative works remain open.

Table 16. Licensing decision

5.4 OPEN SCIENCE AND DISSEMINATION PLATFORMS

FLIARA is deeply committed to adhering to the principles and practices of Open Science and Open Access throughout the project's lifecycle.

5.4.1 OPEN SCIENCE PRINCIPLES

In compliance with Article 17 of the HORIZON Europe Model Grant Agreement, the project followed Open Science principles, sharing anonymised scientific data and knowledge in a transparent and non-discriminatory manner to relevant knowledge actors as early and openly as possible. This was achieved through the utilisation of pre-registration, registered reports, and preprints where applicable.

By implementing these practices as part of the project's methodology, FLIARA facilitated opportunities for key stakeholders to co-design and contribute to the research effort. This transparency throughout the research process facilitated valuable feedback, increased collaboration opportunities, and enhanced community confidence in the research outputs. The resulting increase in the uptake and reproducibility of research results helps avoid duplication of research efforts, ultimately enhancing the overall impact of the project.

5.4.2 OPEN ACCESS PUBLICATION STRATEGY

The project is committed to making all peer-reviewed publications openly accessible through trusted repositories, irrespective of the final publication venue.

- **Immediate Open Access:** Immediate open access after project deliverables approval was ensured through a trusted repository and will be ensured for the final project results by the Exploitation Manager (CE).

- **Journal Publication:** Publications will subsequently be submitted to Open Research Europe and/or other open access peer-reviewed scientific journals, with the content licensed for reuse under an appropriate CC licence after the project ends.

5.4.3 MAIN DISSEMINATION PLATFORMS

The following platforms were utilised to disseminate the FLIARA project outputs:

- **CORDIS:** The European Commission's primary public repository for information on all EU-funded research projects. All of FLIARA's approved public deliverables **will be made available** on this platform once approved by the EC. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084234>.
- **EU-FARMBOOK:** The project utilised the EU-FARMBOOK portal to store, curate, and share scientific data and results under well-defined, trusted conditions. This improved the accessibility of FLIARA's research to knowledge sources across disciplines and countries, enhancing collaboration. <https://eufarmbook.eu/en/projects/0ebe9ca0be9ebadaf3790db6970305d74a90dba971ec3396f77ec50e672f509c/contributions>.
- **ZENODO:** Zenodo, the open-access digital repository operated by CERN and funded by the European Commission, was utilised for uploading outputs and approved deliverables. Zenodo assigns a **Digital Object Identifier (DOI)** to every deposit, ensuring long-term preservation and facilitating citation. <https://zenodo.org/communities/fliara/>.
- **University of Galway Research Repository:** Known as ARAN, is the access to Research at the University of Galway, a digital collection of open-access scholarly publications, was identified and utilised as a valuable platform for disseminating project outputs, particularly those authored by affiliated researchers. <https://hdl.handle.net/10379/6272>.

5.5 BACKGROUND FOR EXPLOITATION

The project strictly adhered to the provisions of the Consortium Agreement (CA) regarding background knowledge.

No mandatory background access rights were required or conceded between partners for the purpose of implementing the project or exploiting results, which was explicitly stated in Attachment 1 of the CA.

However, recognising that partners naturally leveraged their own existing expertise and resources to ensure the wide dissemination and uptake of the project's results, this process of utilising internal background was expected and encouraged. Any potential sharing of background information between partners for synergistic efforts outside the

core scope was considered a voluntary and mutually agreed-upon arrangement, separate from the formal access rights obligations defined in the Grant Agreement (GA).

5.6 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY AND ASSESSMENT

5.6.1 EXPLOITATION AND DISSEMINATION METHODOLOGY

The strategic reuse and application of project results are governed by Article 16 (on the use of results) of the GA. A systematic approach to capturing and evaluating the exploitability of FLIARA’s results was fundamental to maximising their long-term impact and ensuring alignment with the principles of Open Access and wide dissemination.

Figure 75. Exploitation Methodology

5.6.2 SYSTEMATIC CAPTURE AND ASSESSMENT

Each partner, responsible for specific tasks and deliverables, ensured the comprehensive and timely documentation of all project results generated. This detailed and accurate documentation was made readily accessible to all consortium members through the project’s designated communication and storage platform (Teams).

All identified project results underwent a rigorous exploitability assessment using the FLIARA Exploitability Assessment Template. This template, completed by the main partner responsible for each KER, guided the evaluation based on the following criteria:

- 📄 **Description of the Result:** A comprehensive description of the Project Result, its key features, and its intended purpose.
- 📄 **Innovation Potential:** The degree to which the result represented a novel approach or insight within the project’s context.

- 🏠 **Relevance to Stakeholders:** The degree to which the result addressed the needs and challenges of key stakeholder groups (e.g., policymakers, women's organisations, agricultural support agencies).
- 🏠 **Potential Impact:** The potential of the result to contribute to policy changes, improved practices, or the empowerment of women in the target sectors.
- 🏠 **Target Users and Benefits:** Identification of the specific beneficiaries and a clear articulation of those benefits.
- 🏠 **Potential Exploitation Routes:** Identification of viable pathways for utilisation and dissemination beyond the project's duration (e.g., policy advocacy, training programmes).
- 🏠 **Intellectual Property Protection:** Assessment of IP needs, prioritising open access and Creative Commons licensing.
- 🏠 **Resource Requirements:** Estimation of the financial, human, and technical resources required to effectively exploit the result.
- 🏠 **Market/Policy Landscape:** An overview of the relevant policy environment and the potential for the result to influence policy.

5.6.3 EXPLOITATION PLAN PER KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULT

For each Project Result identified as a KER, a detailed and actionable Exploitation Plan was developed. This plan served as a roadmap for maximising the KER's impact and ensuring its sustainable use beyond the project's lifetime.

The FLIARA Exploitation Plan per KER Template was used to structure these detailed plans. For each KER, the key owner outlined a roadmap based on their expertise, which covered:

- 🏠 **Detailed Description of the KER:** A thorough description building upon the Exploitability Assessment.
- 🏠 **Target Users and Strategies to Reach Them:** Specific identification of intended users and effective outreach channels.
- 🏠 **Exploitation Strategy:** A clear articulation of how the KER will be made available and utilised (emphasising open access).
- 🏠 **IPR Management:** Specification of the chosen IP approach (typically Creative Commons licences).
- 🏠 **Actions Needed to Make the KER Ready for Use:** A detailed breakdown including formalising licensing, planning dissemination, translation/adaptation, and developing supporting user guides.

 Responsible Partner(s), Timelines, and Resource Requirements.

5.7 KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

Understanding the identification of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their strategic routes for exploitation is essential to maximising the impact of the FLIARA project. The FLIARA Project results have been jointly assessed by the Work Package leaders, and detailed routes for exploitation were outlined by the consortium. These routes were made available to partners with prior interest in the uptake of the project's outcomes, following a methodology established by the Exploitation Manager (CE) to facilitate effective reuse.

Below is the final, comprehensive list of KERs across all work packages (WP1 through WP7), detailing the results for further uptake beyond the project scope.

Work Package	Title of the KER	Description	Owner(s) and Contributor(s)
WP1	FLIARA Conceptual Framework	Report detailing the FLIARA co-created conceptual framework, including 30 concept notes that informed the framework and a Glossary of Terms. The conceptual framework provides a flexible model for examining and understanding how women-led innovations can initiate progress towards gender equality and sustainability in rural and farming areas. The framework includes the idea of female-led innovation journeys and a series of hypotheses as potential leverage points for improving gender equality and rural sustainability.	Galway, OULU; All partners.
WP1	Women-led Innovation Research Review	Review report examining existing knowledge on women-led innovation in farming and rural areas, as well as key gaps and future needs for research. The report contains a review of knowledge focused on a range of key areas: The	Galway; All partners.

		Rural Context; Gender in Rural Areas; Sustainable Rural Development; Rural Innovation; Female Entrepreneurship; Opportunities in Digital and Ecological Entrepreneurship. It also features a series of 31 Fact Sheets on previous European projects that collate and assess key information on European research and innovation projects with relevance to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.	
WP1	Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks	The D1.3 report provides an assessment of policy and legal frameworks in relation to women-led innovation from across the EU. It assessed farming and rural development policy, as well as wider relevant policy. The focus is on the extent to which current frameworks directly and indirectly support women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. This assessment uncovered a comprehensive framework of policies and laws impacting the innovation ecosystem and pathway towards women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.	Galway; All partners.
WP1	Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection	Report detailing the preliminary case study assessment and selection framework to be applied in WP3. This includes the initial approach to assessment of the pathways towards women-led innovation, steps to select case studies and approach to the comparative analysis.	Galway; All partners.
WP1	Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking	The D1.5 report provides initial, preliminary guidelines on policy	Galway; All partners.

		benchmarking on gender equality performance in relation to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. It provides insights and broad learnings for policy benchmarking from FLIARA report D1.3 that provides an inventory and assessment of policy and legal frameworks.	
WP2	Vision cards	Vision cards are derived from 747 innovations that were named as a way to solve sustainability issues recognised across rural areas across all partner countries. These innovations were divided into 20 categories that were made into 20 vision cards. Vision cards are a great tool for discussions around rural development to address rural issues such as lack of economic diversification, lack of infrastructure and facilities and selective population decline.	UTU; All partners.
WP2	Measures to add women's contributions to sustainability innovations	63 experts from partner countries assessed measures found by a multi-phased process to add women's contributions to solve sustainability issues in rural areas. FLIARA D2.4, table 12.	UTU; All partners.
WP2	FLIARA innovation cards	Innovation cards are a tool to facilitate finding political, social, environmental, economic and technological innovations to address sustainability problems in rural areas. D2.3, figure 15.	UTU; All partners.
WP3	Factsheets on Women Led-Innovation in farming and rural areas	200 Fact Sheets of women leading innovation in farming and rural areas	MENDELU, UOLU and UTU; HNEE; GALWAY; UNICAL; TUDelft; UL; CE; LNU; ECOLISE and ELARD
WP3	National Case studies Report	National case studies report	MENDELU, UOLU and UTU, HNEE, GALWAY, UNICAL, TU

			Delft, ECOLISE and ELARD; UL; CE; LNU
WP3	Comparative analysis	Report on the case study comparative analysis reflecting insights by macro-region and the European level (T3.4).	UNICAL and LNU; all partners
WP3	Practice abstracts - Batch 1	10 Practice Abstracts on the outcomes of the 20 case studies (T3.3) and the comparative analysis of case studies (T3.4).	UNICAL, LNU, GALWAY, LU, HLK
WP4	Strategic Action Plan	Strategic Action Plan for Community of Practice Events expands on the FLIARA methodology for establishing multi-actor, gender-responsive Communities of Practice (CoPs) in rural contexts. It outlines structured steps, tools, and stakeholder engagement strategies to ensure inclusive, effective, and replicable CoP formation across diverse European regions. Developed as a living document, the plan provides a foundational roadmap for delivering four CoP networking events during the project and serves as a strategic tool for stakeholders aiming to replicate or adapt similar participatory structures.	Galway, ECOLISE, CE
WP4	Report on Community of Practice Networking events	The Report on Community of Practice Networking Events synthesises the processes, themes, participant reflections, and outcomes of four EU-level FLIARA CoP events held in Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, and Sweden. The report provides a comparative overview of methodologies used, barriers and enablers for female-led rural innovation, and collaborative learning practices. It offers actionable insights for designing inclusive, translocal knowledge-	ECOLISE, Galway, UL, UNICAL, LNU

		sharing platforms and showcases the potential of structured CoPs in shaping rural innovation ecosystems and gender-equitable participation.	
WP4	Benchmarking Initial Report on Policy and Legal Frameworks:	The Benchmarking Initial Report analyses how EU and national legal and policy frameworks support or hinder women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. Drawing on WP1 theoretical framing, WP3 case studies, and insights from CoP workshops, it identifies legal gaps, policy blind spots, and good practices across member states. The report offers strategic input for policy reform, gender mainstreaming in rural innovation systems, and supports multi-level governance efforts to embed inclusive approaches to sustainability transitions.	ECOLISE, Galway; National Case Studies Leads
WP4	FLIARA Toolkit for Women-led Rural Innovation	The FLIARA Toolkit is a multi-format resource package designed to support the visibility, transferability, and learning from women-led innovations in agriculture and rural development. It includes fact sheets, podcasts, video blogs, and interactive materials showcasing good practices and innovation stories identified across the FLIARA case studies. Designed for both policy influence and community empowerment, the Toolkit offers accessible, engaging content for rural actors, trainers, and advocates to foster inclusive innovation processes.	ECOLISE, Galway, CE; UNICAL and LNU

WP4	Gender-Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas	The Gender-Specific Guide provides an evidence-based, user-oriented synthesis of enablers, obstacles, and pathways for supporting female-led innovation in rural and farming contexts. Drawing from case studies, foresight results, and participatory activities across FLIARA, the guide presents practical recommendations for designing supportive environments and interventions. It targets both institutional actors and community leaders, offering clear guidance on integrating gender-sensitive approaches into policy, innovation programmes, and local development strategies.	Galway, ECOLISE; Case study partners
WP5	FLIARA Policy Briefs	Policy briefs based on FLIARA evidence to inform policy stakeholders about key takeaways for practice.	All partners involved
WP5	FLIARA Policy Booklet	The policy booklet is a way to present outcomes of FLIARA to policy makers	TU Delft, Galway
WP5	Participative Scenario Report	This is a deliverable based on actions in the CoP events on participative scenario making.	Galway, UTU
WP5	Benchmarking	This is the final benchmarking report which builds on earlier produced reports.	Galway
WP5	Policy workshop	During the FLIARA final conference a specific policy workshop was held.	TU Delft
WP6	FLIARA Project Website	Project website including the results of the project (D6.4).	CE
WP6	Videos and Podcasts	Dedicated interactions recorded via the CoPs with female innovators in farming and rural areas. Includes 20 videos and 10 podcasts featured on the project's website (D6.5).	CE; All partners.

WP6	FLIARA Identity Brand	FLIARA logo design and adaptation for brand identity of the project across communication channels and materials (D6.1; D6.2 and D6.3).	CE; Galway
WP7	FLIARA Practice Abstracts – 2 batch	15 Practice Abstracts on the outcomes of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6.	Galway

Table 17. FLIARA Key Exploitable Results

5.7.1 SWOT ANALYSIS OF KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS (KERS)

The analysis of the Key Exploitable Results (KERS) generated within the FLIARA project was conducted using a SWOT framework based on partner perceptions and a participatory assessment exercise. This analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of the exploitation landscape and provides an evidence-based foundation for the formulation of targeted sustainability actions. To conduct this process the 26 identified KERS were categorised:

Category	KERS Included
Frameworks & Research Foundations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📁 FLIARA Conceptual Framework 📁 Women-led Innovation Research Review 📁 Assessment of Rural and Farming Policy and Legal Frameworks 📁 Benchmarking Report on Policy and Legal Frameworks 📁 Participative Scenario Report
Guidelines, Methodologies & Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 📁 Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection 📁 Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking 📁 Vision Cards 📁 Measures to Add Women's Contributions to Sustainability Innovations 📁 FLIARA Innovation Cards 📁 FLIARA Toolkit for Women-led Rural Innovation

Knowledge Outputs & Analytical Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gender-Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Factsheets on Women-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas National Case Studies Report Comparative Analysis Practice Abstracts – Batch 1 Report on Community of Practice Networking Events Practice Abstracts – Batch 2
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic Action Plan FLIARA Policy Briefs FLIARA Policy Booklet Policy Workshop
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FLIARA Project Website Videos and Podcasts FLIARA Identity Brand
Policy & Strategic Outputs	
Communication, Engagement & Dissemination Outputs	

Table 18. Key Exploitable Results

5.7.1.1 STRENGTHS

The FLIARA KERs demonstrate a high level of conceptual soundness and thematic coherence, reflecting robust research foundations and clear alignment with EU policy priorities in gender equality, rural innovation, and sustainability. The strong emphasis on empowerment, visibility, and cultural change positions the project as a highly relevant contributor to ongoing debates on inclusive rural development. The participatory evaluation found that policy-related outputs and communication products (including the FLIARA Policy Booklet and Toolkit) achieved strong uptake scores. The availability of multiple dissemination-oriented results, such as podcasts, videos, and factsheets,

constitutes an additional strength, enhancing transferability, accessibility, and stakeholder engagement across diverse territorial and professional contexts.

5.7.1.2 WEAKNESSES

Despite these strengths, certain internal limitations were identified. The perceived exploitation potential of more research-oriented KERs (e.g., the conceptual framework and analytical reports) remained comparatively modest. While academically valuable, these outputs require further translation, contextualisation, or simplification to enhance usability beyond expert audiences. Furthermore, the exploitation responsibilities for individual KERs were unevenly distributed across partners, increasing the risk of fragmentation if not accompanied by strong ownership mechanisms. The assessment also indicated that visibility outside the consortium remained limited for some outputs, which may constrain their immediate uptake by external policy actors or end-users.

5.7.1.3 OPPORTUNITIES

The analysis indicated a highly favourable external environment for the future exploitation of the KERs. A significant opportunity lies in the alignment of the results with EU rural policy frameworks, including the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), gender mainstreaming requirements, and ongoing institutional debates on rural attractiveness and sustainability. Partners expressed strong interest in building upon the KERs through future collaborations, follow-up projects, and multi-actor networks, demonstrating clear potential for scaling and institutionalisation of selected outputs. Given the growing policy focus on gender equality, women's entrepreneurship, and rural innovation, FLIARA is well placed to position its KERs as evidence-based resources informing governance, practice, and community initiatives.

5.7.1.4 THREATS

Several external risks were identified that may hinder or slow the exploitation of the results. The most prominent threat relates to resource dependency: without access to post-project funding, certain exploitation pathways may not be sustainable. Furthermore, institutional uptake of gender-related innovations remains uneven across European rural contexts, raising the possibility that some outputs may face limited application due to cultural or structural resistance. The exploitation of policy-oriented KERs may also be affected by political turnover, shifting policy agendas, or limited absorption capacity in national and regional administrations. Finally, competition for stakeholder attention within a saturated landscape of EU-funded projects poses an additional challenge, potentially undermining visibility if sustained communication efforts are not maintained after the project's completion.

5.7.2 KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS ANALYSIS

In this way, the above SWOT serves as a practical orientation tool that directly informs the subsequent exploitation measures and sustainability actions proposed in this plan. Building on these insights and following the agreed methodology to foster the uptake of project results, the leading partners assessed each of the identified KERs and elaborated tailored exploitation routes. These routes are outlined below by Deliverable and associated direct outcomes. To ensure that the work carried out by partners is clearly documented and remains visible KER by KER, the full assessment templates are included in this section.

5.7.2.1 WP1 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

This work package focused on establishing the foundational knowledge base and methodological frameworks for the entire project. The KERs generated are primarily research reports and guidelines intended for academic, policy, and consortium use.

D1.1: FLIARA Conceptual Framework	
Concise description of the KER	Report detailing the FLIARA co-created conceptual framework, including 30 concept notes that informed the framework and a Glossary of Terms. The conceptual framework provides a flexible model for examining and understanding how women-led innovations can initiate progress towards gender equality and sustainability in rural and farming areas. The framework includes the idea of female-led innovation journeys and a series of hypotheses as potential leverage points for improving gender equality and rural sustainability.
Partners and contributions	University of Galway led. All partners participated in co-developing the framework, with UOULU co-leading the initial stages with Galway. All partners further participated by each contributing concept notes.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>FLIARA Consortium: The D1.1 framework was applied in other WPs, particularly WP3 where it was applied to the case studies to understand women-led innovation pathways within the innovation ecosystem. Further to this it has shaped other specific tasks and work. This includes the design of a questionnaire for policy assessment in T1.4. The innovation journey idea that sits within the framework provided a core structure to spearhead Ambassador discussion panels at the CoPs.</p> <p>Academia: The framework was already drawn on to underpin a conceptual academic paper published in the European Countryside journal. There is potential to be further build on the framework in academia, informed by empirical insights and testing, to better conceptualise and understand the nature of women-led rural and farm innovation.</p> <p>Policymakers: The paper published in European Countryside uses conceptual insights to argue for an increased focus on women in realising the Long-Term Vision for Rural areas. This provides practical insights and lessons for policymakers that could be applied in future policy.</p>

Exploitation routes and access	<p>Future research: D1.1 will also be drawn on for a planned paper due to be completed by October 2025 in a special issue of the Journal of Rural Studies. This will be a co-authored paper by a number of FLIARA Consortium partners and will also analyse selected case study findings. There is also potential for future dissemination through conferences and open access publications.</p> <p>Dissemination: Open access paper published in European Countryside published in 2024. Open access article in EuPM also drew on D1.1. D1.1 is also expected to provide the basis for a chapter in the planned FLIARA book. D1.1 has been added to the University of Galway ARAN open access research repository. An infographic was also produced to provide a more visual overview of D1.1 and this features as part of the FLIARA Toolkit, as well as other entries in the toolkit that focus on elements of D1.1. Wider dissemination channels are also through FLIARA's own communications and activities such as the CoP events and final conference. The report is also added to the Zenodo repository.</p>
Protection measure and rationale	CC-BY 4.0 by M6

Table 19. D1.1: FLIARA Conceptual Framework

D1.2: Women-led Innovation Research Review	
Concise description of the KER	<p>Review report examining existing knowledge on women-led innovation in farming and rural areas, as well as key gaps and future needs for research. The report contains a review of knowledge focused on a range of key areas: The Rural Context; Gender in Rural Areas; Sustainable Rural Development; Rural Innovation; Female Entrepreneurship; Opportunities in Digital and Ecological Entrepreneurship. It also features a series of 31 Fact Sheets on previous European projects that collate and assess key information on European research and innovation projects with relevance to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.</p>
Partners and contributions	<p>University of Galway led, all partners participated to identify projects and knowledge for review. All partners reviewed and contributed to final report, particularly WP leaders.</p>
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>FLIARA Consortium: The D1.2 review was carried out to provide a basis of key knowledge to inform WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5. This ensures that FLIARA work builds on existing knowledge and works to address knowledge gaps.</p> <p>Academia: The report examines existing knowledge, key gaps and future needs for research and has been drawn on for the WP1 reports and articles already mentioned in relation to D.1.1 (European Countryside, EuPM). There is potential to further build on the knowledge base in academic publications that also draw on other FLIARA results (e.g. WP2, WP3 and WP5). The Fact Sheets also provide a concise series of information resources on EC projects with relevance to gender and innovation that also provides a wider knowledge resource that can be built on by academic stakeholders.</p>

Exploitation routes and access	<p>Future research: D1.2 will be drawn on for a planned paper due to be completed by October 2025 in a special issue of the Journal of Rural Studies. It will also be drawn on to feed into the planned ELGAR Encyclopaedia of Land Use entry on Land Use and the role of women. There is also potential for future dissemination through conferences and open access publications.</p> <p>Dissemination: D1.2 can provide a starting knowledge based for future open access articles, conference papers and short articles. D1.2 can also be drawn on in the planned FLIARA book. D1.2 has been added to the University of Galway ARAN open access research repository. Dissemination will also be through FLIARA's own channels such as the Toolkit, Final Conference and the report is added to the Zenodo repository. An infographic was also produced to provide a more visual overview of D1.2 and this features in the FLIARA Toolkit. The Factsheets will also feature in the FLIARA Toolkit.</p>
Protection measure and rationale	CC-BY 4.0 by M6

Table 20. D1.2: Women-led Innovation Research Review

D1.3: Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks	
Concise description of the KER	The D1.3 report provides an assessment of policy and legal frameworks in relation to women-led innovation from across the EU. It assessed farming and rural development policy, as well as wider relevant policy. The focus is on the extent to which current frameworks directly and indirectly support women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. This assessment uncovered a comprehensive framework of policies and laws impacting the innovation ecosystem and pathway towards women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.
Partners and contributions	University of Galway led (design data collection tools, analysis and report drafting), all partners participated (completed national data collection and review of deliverable)

Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>FLIARA Consortium: The D1.3 report provides relevant information to feed into FLIARA national Policy Briefs emerging from T5.1 where all partners can draw on the national analysis of policies. The D1.3 report fed into the subsequent benchmarking report D4.3. The report and wider data collected for D1.5 will also be further analysed for the final benchmarking report D5.3</p> <p>Academia: The D1.3 report provides an assessment of the current state of policy development in relation to supporting women-led innovation in rural areas and farming in the EU and 10 FLIARA countries. The analysis identifies some key gaps and issues for further research. The findings provide a basis for future academic analysis, such as at national level or comparative studies.</p> <p>Policymakers: The D1.3 report provides information on national policies from 10 countries as well as at the EU level. This provides important information on how women-led innovation is currently supported through policy as well as future gaps and needs. This is important information that can be used by policymakers to inform future policy improvements.</p>
Exploitation routes and access	<p>Future research: Future analysis of national policy frameworks or comparing policy frameworks at different governance levels or national contexts is possible building on this analysis. For example, the paper presented at the Rural Entrepreneurship Conference 2025 in Bangor, Wales presented an initial deeper analysis of the data collected in Ireland for D1.3. This could still be further developed for an open access peer-reviewed publication.</p> <p>Dissemination: The D1.3 report has provided a basis for conference papers such as at the Sociological Association of Ireland 2025 Conference in Cork, Ireland and Rural Entrepreneurship Conference 2025 in Bangor, Wales. It also has potential to feed into future conferences and open access articles. National policy workshops are being organised by some partners at country levels which can also provide a dissemination route towards exploitation by policymakers. These events include a national FLIARA conference in Ireland. It provides relevant information to feed into FLIARA Policy Briefs emerging from T5.1. It is planned to draw on D1.3 to feed into a chapter of the FLIARA book. D1.3 has been added to the University of Galway ARAN open access research repository. It will also provide the basis of an entry in the FLIARA Toolkit. D1.3 also feeds into wider dissemination through FLIARA's own channels, including the CoP events, final conference and is uploaded to the Zenodo repository.</p>
Protection measure and rationale	CC-BY 4.0 by M17

Table 21. D1.3: Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks

D1.4: Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection	
Concise description of the KER	Report detailing the preliminary case study assessment and selection framework to be applied in WP3. This includes the initial approach to assessment of the pathways towards women-led innovation, steps to select case studies and approach to the comparative analysis.

Partners and contributions	Galway led; All partners leading WPs involved, particularly WP3 leads UNICAL and LNU
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>FLIARA Consortium: The guidelines were used in WP3 and further refined in T3.1 to provide the final methodology for case studies applied by all partners in carrying out the national case studies. The task brought together knowledge and evidence from other tasks (T1.1, T1.2, available results emerging from WP2) to ensure the project built on and utilised the knowledge base emerging to inform a final robust and state of the art case study methodology.</p> <p>Academia: Any academic publications, conference papers and wider dissemination emerging from WP3 are underpinned by this preliminary case study assessment and selection framework. It provides a discrete report considering case study methodology and has potential to be drawn on in more methodological focused academic activities. This could include methodological scientific papers and as an example to guide future case study research design process in other studies and projects.</p>
Exploitation routes and access	Dissemination: D1.4 is disseminated through FLIARA's own channels featuring as one entry in the FLIARA Toolkit and is uploaded to the Zenodo repository. D1.4 has also been added to the University of Galway ARAN open access research repository.
Protection measure and rationale	CC-BY 4.0 by M9

Table 22. D1.4: Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection

D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking	
Concise description of the KER	The D1.5 report provides initial, preliminary guidelines on policy benchmarking on gender equality performance in relation to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. It provides insights and broad learnings for policy benchmarking from FLIARA report D1.3 that provides an inventory and assessment of policy and legal frameworks.
Partners and contributions	Galway led; All partners involved

<p>Stakeholder groups and benefits</p>	<p>FLIARA Consortium: The D1.5 report provided a first step in the FLIARA project benchmarking activities and has fed into the subsequent benchmarking report D4.3. It will also influence the final benchmarking report D5.3.</p> <p>Academia: Policy benchmarking is a complex task with room for future academic work. Benchmarking can be approached in different ways. The approach to benchmarking must also be underpinned by practical considerations, such as the availability of data. This report acts as a starting point for FLIARA benchmarking and the insights emerging can also help inform the further developing of gender policy benchmarking more broadly beyond the FLIARA project.</p> <p>Policymakers: The D1.5 report provides insights and wider considerations that are useful to policymakers in designing benchmarking frameworks, particularly in rural and farming gender equality contexts.</p>
<p>Exploitation routes and access</p>	<p>Future research: Further analysis of benchmarking methods at different governance levels or national contexts is possible building on this analysis. This is a potentially rich areas for future research.</p> <p>Dissemination: The D1.5 report provides relevant information to potentially feed into FLIARA Policy Briefs and Booklet emerging from T5.1. It is planned to draw on aspects of D1.5 to feed into a chapter of the FLIARA book. D1.5 has been added to the University of Galway ARAN open access research repository. It will also provide the basis of an entry in the FLIARA Toolkit. D1.5 is also disseminated through FLIARA's own channels, including the CoP events, final conference and is uploaded to the Zenodo repository.</p>
<p>Protection measure and rationale</p>	<p>CC-BY 4.0 by M17</p>

Table 23. D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking

5.7.2.2 WP1 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

Exploitation efforts aim to target academic communities by generating peer-reviewed publications, and policy actors by integrating the assessment of legal and policy frameworks directly into ongoing national and European policy-benchmarking activities. This ensures that the insights from the frameworks move beyond the project lifecycle to inform future evidence-based decision-making and research methodologies across the sector.

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D1.1: Conceptual Framework			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC-BY 4.0	University of Galway	Implemented in August 2024
Research publication: Journal of Rural Studies	Structure for the paper; allocate work among co-authors; collating and editing of draft; submission to journal for review	University of Galway; LNU; UNICALL; HLK	By October 2025
Chapter in FLIARA book	Develop chapter based on abstract and refinement of content of D1.1	University of Galway	ASAP; by early 2026
Resources for the FLIARA Toolkit	Complete content template for resources mapped from D1.1 for FLIARA Toolkit	University of Galway	ASAP; by September or early October 2025
Presentations at conferences	Identify further conferences and prepare for upcoming conferences (e.g. FLIARA final conference; National conference in Ireland; European Rural Sociology Conference)	University of Galway	asap and until project end date and as possible beyond this
Article on: Land Use and the role of women	Review content of D1.1 and assess relevance for ELGAR Encyclopaedia of Land Use entry on Land Use and the role of women	University of Galway	by end August 2025
Dissemination: open access ARAN database	Add D1.1 report to University of Galway ARAN open access database	University of Galway	Completed in June 2025

Dissemination: open access EUFARM BOOK database	Add D1.1 to EUFARMBOOK	Consult a Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: open access Zenodo database	Add D1.1 to Zenodo	Consult a Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: FLIARA Website	Add D1.1 to the project website	Consult a Europa	Completed in October 2024
Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D1.2: Women-led Innovation Research Review			
Action	What?	By Whom ?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC-BY 4.0	University of Galway	Implemented in August 2024
Use content as relevant in chapter (s) of FLIARA book	Review content of D1.2 and assess relevance for certain sections of FLIARA book (e.g. introduction and other chapters as relevant)	University of Galway	ASAP; by early 2026
Resources for the FLIARA Toolkit	Complete content template using D1.2 resources as mapped for the FLIARA Toolkit	University of Galway	ASAP; by September or early October 2025
Article on: Land Use and the role of women	Review content of D1.2 and assess relevance for ELGAR Encyclopaedia of Land Use entry on Land Use and the role of women	University of Galway	by end August 2025
Dissemination: open access ARAN database	Add D1.2 report to University of Galway ARAN open access database	University of Galway	Completed in June 2025

Dissemination: open access EUFARM BOOK database	Add D1.2 to EUFARMBOOK	Consult a Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: open access Zenodo database	Add D1.2 to Zenodo	Consult a Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: FLIARA Website	Add D1.2 to the project website	Consult a Europa	Completed in October 2024
Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D1.3: Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks			
Action	What?	By Whom ?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC-BY 4.0	University of Galway	Implemented in August 2024
Chapter in FLIARA book	Develop chapter based on abstract and refinement of content from D1.3	University of Galway	ASAP, by early 2026
Resources for the FLIARA Toolkit	Complete content template for D1.3 as planned for FLIARA Toolkit	University of Galway	ASAP; by September or early October 2025
Presentations at conferences/seminars and seminars relevant to policy	Identify further conferences and prepare for upcoming conferences (e.g. FLIARA final conference; National conference in Ireland)	University of Galway	ASAP and until project end date and as possible beyond this

Analysis for D5.3	Review and further analyse D1.3 and wider data collected for final benchmarking report D5.3	University of Galway	ASAP and until early October 2025
Analysis for policy briefs	Identify results from D1.3 for policy briefs (D5.1)	University of Galway	ASAP and until early October 2025
Policy influencing actions	Feed into relevant national policy consultations in Ireland (e.g. Our Rural Future, next CAP Strategic Plan) and wider engagement with policy-making actors (e.g. invite to FLIARA final and Ireland national conference) and influencing spaces (e.g. National and European Parliament)	University of Galway	Ongoing
Dissemination: open access ARAN database	Add D1.3 report to University of Galway ARAN open access database	University of Galway	Completed in June 2025
Dissemination: open access EUFARM BOOK database	Add D1.3 to EU FARMBOOK	Consulta Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: open access Zenodo database	Add D1.3 to Zenodo	Consulta Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: FLIARA Website	Add D1.3 to the project website	Consulta Europa	Completed in October 2024
Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D1.4: Initial Guidelines for Case Study Assessment and Selection			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC-BY 4.0	University of Galway	Implemented in August 2024

Resources for the FLIARA Toolkit	Complete content template for D1.4 as planned for FLIARA Toolkit	University of Galway	ASAP; by September or early October 2025
Dissemination: open access ARAN database	Add D1.4 report to University of Galway ARAN open access database	University of Galway	Completed in June 2025
Dissemination: open access EUFARMBOOK database	Add D1.4 to EUFARMBOOK	Consulta Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: open access Zenodo database	Add D1.4 to Zenodo	Consulta Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: FLIARA Website	Add D1.4 to the project website	Consulta Europa	Completed in October 2024

**Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use:
D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking**

Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC-BY 4.0	University of Galway	Implemented in August 2024
Resources for the FLIARA Toolkit	Complete content template for D1.5 as planned for FLIARA Toolkit	University of Galway	ASAP; by September or early October 2025
Presentations at conferences/seminars and seminars	Identify further conferences and prepare for upcoming conferences (e.g. FLIARA final conference; National conference in Ireland)	University of Galway	ASAP and until project end date and as possible beyond this

relevant to policy			
Analysis for D5.3	Review and further analyse D1.5 for final benchmarking report D5.3	University of Galway	ASAP and until early October 2025
Analysis for policy briefs	Identify results from D1.5 for policy briefs (D5.1)	University of Galway	ASAP and until early October 2025
Policy influencing actions	Feed into relevant national policy consultations in Ireland and wider engagement with policy-making actors and influencing spaces.	University of Galway	Ongoing
Dissemination: open access EUFARM BOOK database	Add D1.5 to EUFARMBOOK	Consulta Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: open access Zenodo database	Add D1.5 to Zenodo	Consulta Europa	Completed in December 2024
Dissemination: FLIARA Website	Add D1.5 to the project website	Consulta Europa	Completed in October 2024
Dissemination: open access ARAN database	Add D1.5 report to University of Galway ARAN open access database	University of Galway; Consulta Europa	Completed in June 2025

Table 24. WP1 – Exploitation Routes

5.7.2.3 WP2 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

This work package generated participatory tools and conceptual materials derived from multi-phased stakeholder workshops, focusing on visions and innovation types for rural sustainability. The KERs are designed for direct use by practitioners, local actors, and policymakers.

Vision cards	
Concise description of the KER	Vision cards are derived from 747 innovations that were named as a way to solve sustainability issues recognised across rural areas across all partner countries. These innovations were divided into 20 categories that were made into 20 vision cards. Vision cards are a great tool for discussions around rural development to address rural issues such as lack of economic diversification, lack of infrastructure and facilities and selective population decline.
Partners and contributions	Data was collected through multiple rounds of interviews and workshops in all partner countries. Partners conducted many workshops in a multi-phase process. First workshops and interviews cultivated many sustainability issues recognised throughout rural areas. After naming these issues, a second round of workshops were arranged to come up with visions of lively and thriving rural areas where sustainability issues have been addressed. Finally, in another round of workshops and interviews, 747 innovations were found to solve sustainability issues. Partner countries represented 3 different rural contexts with a chosen region: remote rural areas, rural areas close to city and rural villages. All these area types host a different type of relevant stakeholders, and all areas had an equal level of representation. Stakeholders represented 13 different groups including local farmers and entrepreneurs, local policy makers, active citizens, research organisations and different NGOs. UTU; All partners.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Vision cards are a low threshold way to produce a list of actions that are helpful for all actors involved in rural development. They are a great tool for making rural development more participatory, future-focused and grounded in local realities. Vision cards are used to facilitate discussion and problem solving as has been demonstrated in multiple workshop sessions. Local active members of rural communities can benefit greatly from a tool that has gathered types of innovations and the issues they address. Stakeholders such as NGOs can use the cards to encourage inclusive participation from a diverse pool, such as farmers, local leaders and rural youth. This enhances communication and shared understanding between different actors. The cards are also a great help for decision makers, policy makers and other stakeholders as they can be used to facilitate a structured dialogue when planning long-term goals. Additionally, researchers can use the cards for local workshops in effort to gauge possible paths for rural developments.
Exploitation routes and access	Since the cards are a physical resource best used when printed on cardboard, it is best that the cards can be downloaded and printed by target audiences. The cards will be available for downloading accompanied by all the relevant information. The accompanying material must have the EU stamps and logos of all consortium partners. CC BY 4.0 will be used to facilitate sharing.
Protection measure and rationale	CC BY 4.0 will be used to facilitate sharing.

Table 25. Vision cards

Measures to add women's contributions to sustainability innovations	
Concise description of the KER	63 experts from partner countries assessed measures found by a multi-phased process to add women's contributions to solve sustainability issues in rural areas. D2.4 table 12.
Partners and contributions	For this process all partnering organisations organised multiple workshops and interviews to first assess sustainability issues in their area (2.1), then to assess visions of future where sustainability issues are solved and the measures to do so (2.2). In further research stakeholders found 333 measures that could increase women's contributions to sustainability innovations either by exploiting the possibilities or by removing obstacles. After, experts within and scouted by partner organisations ranked these measures based on their expertise and experience as researchers. UTU; all partners.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Especially actors involved in sustainable rural development, rural empowerment and gender equity can benefit largely from measures for women to make an impact in rural development, such as rural women's groups and NGOs. In addition, rural communities can broaden their adoption of innovative and sustainable practices with active local women making use of the measures found. Policy makers can use the measures to guide evidence based inclusive policies that promote gender equity and rural development. The finding can also be used in research as a framework for studies on gender equity in rural development and ending sustainability problems.
Exploitation routes and access	Measures will be found in the FLIARA toolkit. The table of measures will be provided as a visual document with FLIARA logo. The accompanying material will have EU funded stamp and logos of all partners.
Protection measure rationale	The document will be under CC BY 4.0 to facilitate widespread sharing and usage.

Table 26. Measures to add women's contributions to sustainability innovations

FLIARA innovation cards	
Concise description of the KER	Innovation cards are a tool to facilitate finding political, social, environmental, economic and technological innovations to address sustainability problems in rural areas. D2.3 figure 15.

Partners and contributions	<p>UTU; all partners. The cards are based on work done by all partnering organisations. All partners have conducted interviews and workshops to find the most prevalent sustainability issues in their rural context. In total 117 stakeholders participated. 58% being women and 42% being men. Sustainability issues were found to relate to 4 different categories: political, social, environmental as well as economic and technological problems. 4 cards were made to inspire and guide a fruitful conversation to address sustainability problems in these categories.</p>
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>Innovation cards are a valuable help to all actors in rural development and community engagement. From a communal level e.g. active citizens, community leaders etc. the cards encourage participation in shaping development and identifying solutions to local challenges. Researchers, educators and facilitators can use innovation cards to offer a way to guide discussion in workshops or public forums to stimulate idea generation and community-led innovations. Innovation cards are also a great tool for youth groups in rural areas for exploring local problem solving for long-term development.</p>
Exploitation routes and access	<p>Innovation cards will be found in the FLIARA toolkit. Since the cards are a physical resource best used when printed on cardboard, it is best that the cards can be downloaded and printed by target audiences. The cards will be available for downloading accompanied by all the relevant information. The accompanying material must have the EU stamps and logos of all consortium partners.</p>
Protection measure and rationale	<p>CC BY 4.0 will be used to facilitate sharing.</p>

Table 27. FLIARA innovation cards

5.7.2.4 WP2 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

The objective of the present route is to leverage the inclusive Envisioning Process outcomes, the tangible visions and innovation pathways, to inspire practical, on-the-ground actions that foster generational renewal and gender-inclusive rural transformation within and beyond the project’s scope.

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: All WP2 identified KERs

Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC-BY 4.0	UTU	Implemented in August 2024
Provide downloadable documents of vision cards	Vision cards	UTU	By early 2026
Provide a downloadable visual document of measures for women to contribute to sustainability innovations.	Measures to add women's contributions to sustainability innovations	UTU	By early 2026
Provide downloadable documents of innovation cards	FLIARA innovation cards	UTU	By early 2026
Dissemination through events, social media and Open Access data bases (EUFARMBOOK, ARAN, Zenodo)	WP2 deliverables public	UTU; Galway; CE	Continuous - By early 2026

Table 28. WP2 – Exploitation Routes

5.7.2.5 WP3 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

The primary focus of WP3 is to establish the empirical foundation of women-led innovation. The KERs generated are mainly knowledge products aimed at inspiration, visibility, and deep insight. These include the 200 Factsheets on Women-Led Innovation, which target civil society and the broader community, and the National Case Study Reports and Comparative Analysis, which provide deep, evidence-based insights for researchers and national policymakers on specific challenges and opportunities. The exploitation route for WP3 is largely based on open access dissemination through project websites and established repositories (Zenodo, EUFARMBOOK, EIP-AGRI) to ensure maximum academic and practitioner reach.

Factsheets on Women Led-Innovation in farming and rural areas	
Concise description of the KER	200 Fact Sheets of women leading innovation in farming and rural areas

Partners contributions and	MENDELU, UOLU and UTU; HNEE; GALWAY; UNICAL; TU Delft; UL; CE; LNU; ECOLISE and ELARD
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Civil society, farming community, broader local community. They might take inspiration from the stories of these women.
Exploitation routes and access	Dissemination through the web site of the project and open access repositories
Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)

Table 29. Factsheets on Women Led-Innovation in farming and rural areas

National Case Studies Report	
Concise description of the KER	National case studies report
Partners and contributions	MENDELU, UOLU and UTU, HNEE, GALWAY, UNICAL, TU Delft, ECOLISE and ELARD; UL; CE; LNU
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Consortium partners, academia, policy makers. Consortium partners may be interested in disseminating the national case study reports or article based on them in events/conferences; Academia may be interested in empirical analyses that provide insights into the processes of female innovation in rural areas and in agriculture in specific countries. National policy makers can gain insight into the main challenges women face in promoting innovation and guidance on policy actions to be taken.
Exploitation routes and access	Dissemination through open access publications and repositories - Each national case study report should be available separately to avoid having to download the entire D3.3. They could be made available in the FLIARA toolkit (where the entire deliverable is currently available)
Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)

Table 30. National Case Studies Report

Comparative Analysis	
Concise description of the KER	Report on the case study comparative analysis reflecting insights by macro-region and the European level (T3.4).
Partners and contributions	UNICAL and LNU, all partners
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Researchers may find the overall findings interesting to build upon.
Exploitation routes and access	Published on the website
Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)

Table 31. Comparative Analysis

Practice abstracts - Batch 1	
Concise description of the KER	10 Practice Abstracts on the outcomes of the 20 case studies (T3.3) and the comparative analysis of case studies (T3.4).
Partners and contributions	UNICAL, LNU, GALWAY, LU, HLK
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Civil society, farming community, LAG, policy maker, broader local community. They can tailor decisions, actions and programmes based on the suggestions in the practice abstracts.
Exploitation routes and access	Published on the website and to be uploaded to EIP-AGRI project database
Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)

5.7.2.6 WP3 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

The exploitation routes for WP3 focus on ensuring the longevity and wide accessibility of the empirical evidence. The strategy involves immediate open-access archiving and leveraging existing practitioner platforms (like EIP-AGRI) to translate the deep case study insights into practical use for civil society and policymakers.

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: All WP3 identified KERs			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Intellectual property rights for all WP3 results	CC BY-NC-SA	UNICAL, LNU	Implemented in August 2024
National Case study reports	National Case study reports will be disseminated via the FLIARA Toolkit. It is necessary to separate all the case study reports already available in D3.2	UNICAL, ECOLIS E, CE	By early 2026

Dissemination of deliverables through open access repositories (ARAN, EUFARMBOOK, Zenodo)	WP3 deliverables	UNICAL, LNU, CE, Galway	Continuous - By early 2026
Dissemination of WP3 results through conferences, webinars and events	WP3 deliverables results	UNICAL, LNU	Continuous - By early 2026
Dissemination of Practice Abstracts via EIP AGRI (EU CAP Network platform for practitioners)	Practice Abstracts batch 1	UNICAL, CE	By early 2026
Dissemination via Project website and social media	WP3 deliverables results	UNICAL, CE	Continuous - By early 2026

Table 32. WP3 – Exploitation Routes

5.7.2.7 WP4 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

The KERs in this work package are highly practical and geared towards institutional influence. These include the Strategic Action Plan (D4.1) and the CoP Networking Report (D4.2), which provide a tested model for creating gender-responsive participatory structures that can be replicated, particularly by ECOLISE. Crucially, the FLIARA Toolkit (D4.4) and the Gender-Specific Guide (D4.5) are the main resources for capacity building, with the exploitation strategy focusing on integrating them directly into ECOLISE’s Communities for Future (CfF) learning streams. Lastly, the Benchmarking Initial Report (D4.3) acts as direct policy input, leveraging dedicated actions to translate findings into policy briefs and position papers to influence EU and national rural policy agendas.

D4.1 – Strategic Action Plan	
Concise description of the KER	Strategic Action Plan for Community of Practice Events expands on the FLIARA methodology for establishing multi-actor, gender-responsive Communities of Practice (CoPs) in rural contexts. It outlines structured steps, tools, and stakeholder engagement strategies to ensure inclusive, effective, and replicable CoP formation across diverse European regions. Developed as a living document, the plan provides a foundational roadmap for delivering four CoP networking events during the project and serves as a strategic tool for stakeholders aiming to replicate or adapt similar participatory structures.

Partners and contributions	<p>University of Galway (Lead): Coordinated the design and authorship of the Strategic Action Plan, integrating foresight and stakeholder engagement methodologies from WP1 and WP3.</p> <p>ECOLISE: Provided expertise on participatory governance structures and facilitation processes for CoP establishment.</p> <p>Consulta Europa: Contributed insights on knowledge transfer tools and communication formats aligned with the FLIARA and CoP framework.</p>
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>Consortium partners: Use the plan to coordinate and implement CoP events; gain a tested model for inclusive stakeholder engagement.</p> <p>Local, regional, and national policymakers: Access a roadmap to initiate inclusive participatory structures that inform rural innovation strategies.</p> <p>Innovation support services and NGOs: Use the plan to replicate CoP formation in rural contexts and promote bottom-up innovation ecosystems.</p> <p>Academia and researchers: Employ the plan as a case study for participatory rural governance, innovation policy, and gender-responsive frameworks.</p> <p>Rural and farming communities: Benefit from more inclusive, visible, and supported participation in policy and innovation dialogues.</p>
Exploitation routes and access	<p>Planned routes: Dissemination via FLIARA website and ECOLISE's Communities for Future platform; inclusion in policy toolkits; integration into capacity-building for member organisations.</p> <p>Access: Open access PDF available via FLIARA.eu and communitiesforfuture.org.</p>
Protection measure and rationale	<p>Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA). No formal IP protection, result is disseminated under Creative Commons to ensure open, free uptake and adaptability across sectors. This aligns with FLIARA's and ECOLISE's missions to promote participatory and commons-based rural innovation frameworks.</p>

Table 33. D4.1 – Strategic Action Plan

D4.2 – Report on Community of Practice Networking events

<p>Concise description of the KER</p>	<p>The Report on Community of Practice Networking Events synthesises the processes, themes, participant reflections, and outcomes of four EU-level FLIARA CoP events held in Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, and Sweden. The report provides a comparative overview of methodologies used, barriers and enablers for female-led rural innovation, and collaborative learning practices. It offers actionable insights for designing inclusive, translocal knowledge-sharing platforms and showcases the potential of structured CoPs in shaping rural innovation ecosystems and gender-equitable participation.</p>
<p>Partners and contributions</p>	<p>ECOLISE (Lead): Coordinated the design, data collection, facilitation documentation, and authorship of the report across all four CoP events individual reports.</p> <p>University of Galway: Provided guidance on integrating findings with the overall FLIARA conceptual and policy frameworks and assessing impact and outcomes of the FLIARA CoP.</p> <p>Event Hosts (LNU, UL, UNICAL, Galway): Organised and documented national-level activities and contributed to event-specific analysis.</p>
<p>Stakeholder groups and benefits</p>	<p>FLIARA partners and Innovation Ambassadors: Use the report to reflect on CoP participation and refine outreach strategies.</p> <p>Policymakers and CAP networks: Gain evidence of the effectiveness of inclusive networking for rural innovation policy design.</p> <p>EU/national AKIS bodies and rural development networks: Access models for gender-responsive, multi-actor engagement processes.</p> <p>Civil society and grassroots organisations: Apply findings to develop their own localised participatory innovation platforms.</p> <p>Academic institutions: Use the report to inform research and teaching on participatory rural governance and innovation systems.</p>
<p>Exploitation routes and access</p>	<p>Planned routes: Use in policy briefings, advocacy publications, Communities for Future dissemination, integration into ECOLISE grassroots policy lab formats.</p> <p>Access: Full report published on FLIARA.eu and communitiesforfuture.org under open access.</p>
<p>Protection measure and rationale</p>	<p>Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA). The report is openly accessible to maximise policy uptake, learning replication, and translocal visibility. The Creative Commons license ensures attribution and equitable reuse in non-commercial contexts, aligned with ECOLISE's advocacy goals.</p>

Table 34. D4.2 – Report on Community of Practice Networking events

D4.3 – Benchmarking Initial Report on Policy and Legal Frameworks	
Concise description of the KER	<p>The Benchmarking Initial Report analyses how EU and national legal and policy frameworks support or hinder women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. Drawing on WP1 theoretical framing, WP3 case studies, and insights from CoP workshops, it identifies legal gaps, policy blind spots, and good practices across member states. The report offers strategic input for policy reform, gender mainstreaming in rural innovation systems, and supports multi-level governance efforts to embed inclusive approaches to sustainability transitions.</p>
Partners and contributions	<p>ECOLISE (Lead): Coordinated the synthesis of benchmarking data, organised focus groups at CoP events, and led drafting of the report.</p> <p>University of Galway (Co-lead): Provided policy analysis framework, ensured alignment with WP1 and WP3 outcomes, and supported validation of findings.</p> <p>National case study leads: Contributed legal and policy data specific to their countries. Reviewed the report.</p>
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>EU and national policymakers: Use the report to align rural policy with gender equality objectives and fill policy gaps.</p> <p>Rural innovation actors (AKIS, CAP networks, LEADER groups): Gain evidence to advocate for enabling environments for women-led innovations.</p> <p>Academic institutions and think tanks: Employ the report as a reference for gender-inclusive policy analysis and rural governance studies.</p> <p>Civil society organisations: Use findings to shape advocacy and design gender-responsive rural development programmes.</p> <p>FLIARA consortium: Supports the design of future engagement and policy scenarios in WP5 and advocacy outputs in WP6.</p>
Exploitation routes and access	<p>Planned routes: Cited in FLIARA policy briefs and other outputs, promoted in ECOLISE policy dialogues and national and EU advocacy campaigns.</p> <p>Access: Open access on FLIARA.eu and Communitiesforfuture.org, distributed to relevant EU and national policy platforms.</p>
Protection measure rationale	<p>Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA). The result is published openly to promote transparency, policy alignment, and widespread uptake by policymakers, researchers, and practitioners engaged in gender-inclusive rural development.</p>

Table 35. D4.3 – Benchmarking Initial Report on Policy and Legal Frameworks

D4.4 – FLIARA Toolkit for Women-led Rural Innovation	
Concise description of the KER	<p>The FLIARA Toolkit is a multi-format resource package designed to support the visibility, transferability, and learning from women-led innovations in agriculture and rural development. It includes fact sheets, podcasts, video blogs, and interactive materials showcasing good practices and innovation stories identified across the FLIARA case studies. Designed for both policy influence and community empowerment, the Toolkit offers accessible, engaging content for rural actors, trainers, and advocates to foster inclusive innovation processes.</p>
Partners and contributions	<p>ECOLISE (Co-lead): Led the curation of materials and ensured alignment with grassroots educational use.</p> <p>Consulta Europa (Co-lead): Coordinated production, technical formatting, and integration of multimedia content.</p> <p>University of Galway (Co-lead): Oversaw content coherence with case study evidence and conceptual framework.</p> <p>WP3 lead: Provided content from national case studies and supported the creation of innovation fact sheets. WP2 lead provided the resources for deploying the Vision Cards Exercise. WP1 lead also provided content from the results of the work package.</p>
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>Community educators and trainers: Use Toolkit as a plug-and-play resource for gender-inclusive innovation training.</p> <p>Rural women innovators and networks: Gain recognition, support, and replication of their practices.</p> <p>Local development organisations and NGOs: Apply the materials in local workshops and community planning sessions.</p> <p>EU and national policy networks: Draw on content to support participatory communication and awareness-raising efforts.</p> <p>Academic institutions: Use the toolkit for teaching and research on gender, innovation, and rural transformation.</p>
Exploitation routes and access	<p>Planned routes: Integration into ECOLISE’s Communities for Future learning streams, promoted through workshops, social media, and open resource repositories.</p> <p>Access: Available via FLIARA.eu and communitiesforfuture.org, with links to media platforms (e.g., LinkedIn).</p>

Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA). Creative Commons licensing ensures the Toolkit contents hosted on the FLIARA website remains freely accessible and modifiable for non-commercial, educational, and advocacy purposes. This approach maximises reach and supports FLIARA’s goal of mainstreaming gender-inclusive rural innovation.
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Table 36. D4.4 – FLIARA Toolkit for Women-led Rural Innovation

D4.5 – Gender-Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas	
Concise description of the KER	The Gender-Specific Guide provides an evidence-based, user-oriented synthesis of enablers, obstacles, and pathways for supporting female-led innovation in rural and farming contexts. Drawing from case studies, foresight results, and participatory activities across FLIARA, the guide presents practical recommendations for designing supportive environments and interventions. It targets both institutional actors and community leaders, offering clear guidance on integrating gender-sensitive approaches into policy, innovation programmes, and local development strategies.
Partners and contributions	<p>University of Galway (Lead): Synthesised research findings from WPs 1–4 and led the guide’s conceptual design and writing.</p> <p>ECOLISE (Co-lead): Contributed grassroots insights and ensured relevance for civil society and community-level application.</p> <p>All WP3 case study partners: Provided empirical data and good practices that inform the guide’s recommendations. WP5 leads provide insight into the inclusion of policy best practices.</p> <p>Consulta Europa: design and layout of the document.</p>
Stakeholder groups and benefits	<p>Policymakers and innovation programme designers: Use guide to shape gender-inclusive rural and agricultural policies.</p> <p>Civil society organisations and women’s networks: Employ it as a tool for advocacy, training, and programme co-design.</p> <p>Rural development practitioners and advisors: Apply recommendations to support local female innovators more effectively.</p> <p>Research and academic institutions: Use as a reference in gender studies, rural development curricula, and action research.</p> <p>FLIARA Ambassadors and case contributors: Gain visibility and validation of lived experience through inclusion in the guide.</p>

Exploitation routes and access	<p>Planned routes: Incorporated in ECOLISE advocacy campaigns, training sessions, and shared with rural innovation policy platforms.</p> <p>Access: Freely downloadable via FLIARA.eu and communitiesforfuture.org; distributed through partner networks and presentations.</p>
Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA). The guide is openly licensed to support broad educational and advocacy use. No IP protection is sought to ensure maximum policy relevance, community access, and uptake across rural and institutional contexts.

Table 37. D4.5 – Gender-Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas

5.7.2.8 WP4 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

The strategic exploitation of WP4's KERs is centred on systemic change. The actions detailed below focus on integrating the FLIARA Toolkit and the Gender-Specific Guide directly into the ECOLISE network and learning streams to ensure the methodologies and resources lead to real-world capacity building and replication among European grassroots organisations.

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: Deliverable D4.1 – Strategic Action Plan			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When ?
Intellectual property rights	CC BY-NC-SA	ECOLISE, Galway, CE	Completed - August 2024
Adapt Strategic Action Plan to ECOLISE network	Review and contextualise the Strategic Action Plan to align with ECOLISE's member organisations and rural innovation priorities.	ECOLISE Secretariat with input from strategic members	By December 2025
Integrate training into and facilitation materials	Incorporate the adapted Strategic Action Plan into ECOLISE's (CfF) learning programmes and workshop facilitation guides.	CfF Working Group and ECOLISE LEARN Circle	By early 2026

Disseminate D4.1 via Zenodo and the EUFARMBOOK	Upload D4.1 to Zenodo and EUFARMBOOK with license attribution	CE	Completed - August 2024
Disseminate D4.1 via ARAN	Upload D4.1 to ARAN with license attribution	Galway	Completed - June 2025
Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D4.2 – Report on Community of Practice Networking events			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When ?
Intellectual property rights	CC BY-NC-SA	ECOLISE, Galway, CE	By December 2025
Extract transferable formats and methods from report	Identify and summarise replicable CoP event formats, facilitation approaches, and engagement strategies documented in the report.	ECOLISE Secretariat with CfF facilitators	By early 2026
Package formats into a practitioner-friendly guide	Develop a condensed, user-friendly guide from the report for member organisations to use in their own CoP processes.	ECOLISE LEARN and Communications Circle	By early 2026
Disseminate guide and promote through advocacy events	Share the guide with ECOLISE members and promote it during policy dialogues, workshops, and online events to influence participatory governance practices.	ECOLISE Advocacy and Policy Circle	By end 2026
Disseminate D4.2 via Zenodo and the EUFARMBOOK	Upload D4.2 to Zenodo and EUFARMBOOK with license attribution	CE	By early 2026
Disseminate D4.2 via ARAN	Upload D4.2 to ARAN with license attribution	Galway	By early 2026

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D4.3 – Benchmarking Initial Report on Policy and Legal Frameworks			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When ?
Intellectual property rights	CC BY-NC-SA	ECOLISE, Galway, CE	By December 2025
Extract key policy gaps and leverage points	Analyse the benchmarking findings to identify policy gaps and opportunities relevant to ECOLISE's advocacy agenda on gender and rural innovation.	ECOLISE Advocacy and Policy Circle, LEARN Circle	By December 2025
Translate findings into position papers and policy briefs	Develop concise advocacy materials targeting EU and national institutions based on the benchmarking insights.	ECOLISE Advocacy and Policy Circle	By early 2026
Train members to use findings in local advocacy	Design and deliver capacity-building workshops for ECOLISE members on using benchmarking insights to influence local and regional policy	ECOLISE Secretariat with strategic partners	By early 2026
Disseminate D4.3 via Zenodo and the EUFARMBOOK	Upload D4.3 to Zenodo and EUFARMBOOK with license attribution	CE	By early 2026
Disseminate D4.3 via ARAN	Upload D4.3 to ARAN with license attribution	Galway	By early 2026

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D4.4 – FLIARA Toolkit for Women-led Rural Innovation			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Intellectual property rights	CC BY-NC-SA	ECOLISE, Galway, CE	Implemented on April 2025
Curate and repackage toolkit content for ECOLISE use	Select relevant materials from the FLIARA Toolkit (e.g. fact sheets, videos) and adapt them to ECOLISE's thematic focus and audience needs.	ECOLIS Communications Circle	By early 2026
Integrate toolkit into ECOLISE learning and mentoring pathways	Embed the adapted toolkit in the Communities for Future learning programme and mentoring activities with grassroots groups.	CfF Working Group and ECOLISE Secretariat	2026
Promote through multilingual digital campaign	Launch an awareness campaign across ECOLISE's networks to increase visibility and uptake of the toolkit among practitioners and policymakers.	ECOLISE Communications Circle	2026
Maintain the platform active 2 years after the project's end date.	The website will remain hosted in the CE hosting service	CE	2026-2027
Disseminate D4.4 via Zenodo and the EUFARMBOOK	Upload D4.4 to Zenodo and EUFARMBOOK with license attribution	CE	By early 2026
Disseminate D4.4 via ARAN	Upload D4.4 to ARAN with license attribution	Galway	By early 2026

Actions needed to make the key exploitable result ready for use: D4.5 – Gender-Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When ?
Intellectual property rights	CC BY-NC-SA	ECOLISE, Galway, CE	By September 2025
Extract and contextualise key pathways and enablers	Identify actionable insights from the guide that align with ECOLISE’s gender justice and rural transformation priorities.	ECOLISE Secretariat and Policy and Advocacy Circle	By December 2025
Incorporate guide into ECOLISE’s community advocacy toolkit	Integrate key content into ECOLISE’s advocacy and training resources for use by members in local mobilisation and campaigning.	Policy and Advocacy Circle and Education Circle	By early 2026
Use guide to influence EU and national rural policies	Reference guide in ECOLISE’s submissions and dialogues with EU and national bodies on inclusive rural innovation strategies.	Policy and Advocacy Circle	By 2026
Disseminate D4.5 via Zenodo and the EUFARMBOOK	Upload D4.5 to Zenodo and EUFARMBOOK with license attribution	CE	By early 2026
Disseminate D4.5 via ARAN	Upload D4.5 to ARAN with license attribution	Galway	By early 2026

Table 38. WP4 – Exploitation Routes

5.7.2.9 WP5 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

WP5 is entirely dedicated to Policy Influence and Advocacy. The core mission is to translate all project evidence into actionable political documents that can directly influence policy stakeholders at national and European levels. The key exploitable results are the FLIARA Policy Briefs and the comprehensive Policy Booklet, which serve as direct, accessible outreach tools for policymakers. These resources, coupled with the Final Benchmarking Report on policy gaps and the insights from the Participative

Scenario Report, are designed to facilitate immediate uptake and reform in rural innovation policies. The final Policy Workshop will serve as the capstone event to ensure maximum engagement.

FLIARA Policy Briefs	
Concise description of the KER	Policy briefs based on FLIARA evidence to inform policy stakeholders about key takeaways for practice
Partners and contributions	Alle partners have been involved. Most partners have written specific policy briefs.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Consortium partners to use these in their communication to policy stakeholders in national policy network (reached by translated versions of the briefs) and European policy makers.
Exploitation routes and access	Policy Briefs are outlets by which earlier results of research and innovation are addressed to policy makers. The briefs are distributed to them. Making the policy briefs is also a way to get in touch with policy makers to discuss wider results of FLIARA. Briefs will be communicated through newsletters, social media, the FLIARA website and the Final Conference organised by WP6.
Protection measure and rationale	No protection measures. The briefs are made to be open and by using them better policies will emerge.

Table 39. FLIARA Policy Briefs

FLIARA Policy Booklet	
Concise description of the KER	The policy booklet is a way to present outcomes of FLIARA to policy makers
Partners and contributions	Main contributors are TU Delft and Galway. It is however based on work of all partners.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Key stakeholders are policy makers and parties that impact policy debate
Exploitation routes and access	The book will be presented at the FIARA conference on October 17th. Furthermore, the pdf will be freely available, and its existence will be widely communicated.
Protection measure and rationale	No protection measures. It is there to be used in better policies.

Table 40. FLIARA Policy Booklet

Participative Scenario Report	
Concise description of the KER	This is a deliverable based on actions in the CoP events on participative scenario making
Partners and contributions	Main author is UTU. Other partners have been active (along with stakeholders) during COP events.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Participation is not only be policy makers and consortium members, but also by a range of (female) changemakers and initiators in rural areas.

Exploitation routes and access	Outcomes will be presented using communication media.
Protection measure and rationale	No protection measures. The outcomes are to be used in policy making.

Table 41. Participative Scenario Report

Benchmarking	
Concise description of the KER	This is the final benchmarking report which builds on earlier produced reports.
Partners and contributions	Galway is the prime author of this report
Stakeholder groups and benefits	This helps policy makers to benchmark their own policies and territories. Critics of policy makers can address policymakers why they do not score well on a benchmark. To reach parties FLIARA communication channels are used.
Exploitation routes and access	The deliverable will be an open access report available on the website, the toolkit, the EU FarmBook and through Zenodo.
Protection measure and rationale	CC BY 4.0 will be used to facilitate sharing.

Table 42. Benchmarking

Policy workshop	
Concise description of the KER	During the FLIARA final conference a specific policy workshop will be held.
Partners and contributions	There will be partners, stakeholders and policymakers present during this workshop; a report of the workshop will be made to allow wider use.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Policy makers can be inspired by the workshop to use insights from FLIARA in their daily work. Other actors may use some insights to address policy makers to improve their policies.
Exploitation routes and access	For the workshop itself, there is a process on inviting stakeholders based also to an invitation to consortium members to propose potential contributors. The report will be available at the FLIARA website, and a deliverable will remain open access via Zenodo. As the policy workshop itself will be given through parallel sessions online streaming will not capture all discussions in all groups.
Protection measure and rationale	No protection measures. It will be openly available to result in better policies.

Table 43. Policy workshop

5.7.2.10 WP5 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

WP5 exploitation is a direct, advocacy-focused strategy. The routes below detail the execution of targeted dissemination actions, including the presentation of the Policy Booklet and Policy Briefs at high-level events and policy working groups to facilitate the direct uptake of FLIARA evidence into EU and national policy reforms.

Policy Booklet			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Policy Booklet	Policy booklet is drafted based on future use by stakeholders in policy and practice	TU Delft in discussion with University of Galway	In 2025, until September 2025
Presentation	Presentation of policy booklet at final FLIARA conference	Partners	October 17th 2025
Social media	Social media	Partners	At the moment booklet is available
Direct contact	Direct informing relevant stakeholders	Partners	at the moment booklet is available

Policy Briefs			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Drafting briefs	Policy briefs are drafted based on future use by stakeholders in policy and practice	All partners have a role in this	In 2025. Many policy briefs are already drafted
Discussion (with local actors)	Policy briefs are discussed with relevant policy stakeholders	Partners	in 2025. This can be before finalisation or after, but is needed to ensure uptake and relevance
Social media	Social media mentions of policy briefs	Partners	The moment that briefs are available and ready for dissemination
Cross-reading for inspiration	Cross-reading of policy briefs developed by other partners to consider adjusting one to own context	Partners	Summer 2025
Participatory Scenario Development Report			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Report will be written and published	This is a formal deliverable of FLIARA	Galway is responsible input comes from UTU COP events	End of 2025
Discussion on outcomes during FIARA events	Such as at final conference	Organising events CE; discussion by authors of report	autumn 2025

Social media	Social media attention on participative making	CE and authors	autumn 2025
Benchmarking report			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Presentation or report	Report will be written and published	Galway	End of 2025 the report will be finalised and published after formal approval by the commission
Discussion over benchmarking at FLIARA events	This happens for example during the final conference	Galway (CE organises activities)	during 2025
Social media	Social media attention on benchmarking (also based on previous reports)	CE coordinates but authors can also do so	2025
Final Conference report on policy workshop			
Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Invitations	Key stakeholder from policy and practice will be invited to join	all partners	Spring 2025
Holding workshop	Policy workshop will be organised in a way that KER will be discussed for the relevant audience	TU Delft/Galway/CE	Before October 17th

Harvesting key outcomes	Key outcomes of policy workshop will be harvested	TU Delft	Oct 17th-november 2025
Report	Report of the conference will be drafted	TU Delft (outcomes to be discussed with project partners)	Nov-25
Presentation of results	Outcomes will be presented to stakeholders present and to stakeholders not present	TU Delft/Galway/CE	Nov/Dec 2025
Social media	(social) media will be used to communicate on event	CE and all partners	spring-dec 2025

Table 44. WP5 – Exploitation Routes

5.7.2.11 WP6 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

WP6 focuses on External Communication and Brand Identity to ensure the project's results and messages are coherent, visually recognisable, and reach the widest possible audience. The main KERs are foundational for all outreach efforts: the established FLIARA Identity Brand (logo and guidelines) and the central repository, the FLIARA Project Website. To make findings accessible and engaging, the project also produced media like Videos and Podcasts, which are key resources integrated into the FLIARA toolkit for community and policy use, ensuring long-term visibility beyond the project's duration. Exploitation of the project results will be directly linked to the use of the FLIARA visual identity during and beyond the project lifespan.

FLIARA Identity Brand	
Concise description of the KER	FLIARA logo design and adaptation for brand identity of the project across communication channels and materials (D6.1; D6.2 and D6.3).
Partners and contributions	CE; Galway.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Policymakers, innovation support services, academia, civil society, the farming community, and the broader rural community.

Exploitation routes and access	The FLIARA branding facilitates the application of the logo across all digital and printed materials of the project, it is fully exploited since the beginning of the project by all partners in every material produced. The FLIARA brand acts as the identity of the project ensuring its recognisability and connecting with the target groups. For all exploitable materials the FLIARA Logo has been made available on the project website, and its branding guidelines are available in D6.1 which is fully accessible via the project website and open access repositories such as ARAN, EU Farmbook and Zenodo.
Protection measure and rationale	Registered trademark® by the University of Galway

Table 45. FLIARA Identity Brand

FLIARA Project Website	
Concise description of the KER	Project website including the results of the project (D6.4).
Partners and contributions	CE
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Policymakers, innovation support services, academia, civil society, the farming community, and the broader rural community.
Exploitation routes and access	The FLIARA Project website represents the main online available window to access all project's available resources, it hosts deliverables, fact sheets, blog posts, news, practice abstracts, policy briefs and relevant documents of the project. The exploitation entails presenting and disseminating the platform via social media, in-person events, online events and by any communication and dissemination channel available. The main exploitation is its use across all media. The website will be available online up to two years after the project ends under the responsibility of CE.
Protection measure and rationale	Copyright notice implemented on the project website since its launch in M4.

Table 46. FLIARA Project Website

Videos and Podcasts	
Concise description of the KER	Dedicated interactions recorded via the CoPs with female innovators in farming and rural areas. Includes 20 videos and 10 podcasts featured on the project's website (D6.5).
Partners and contributions	CE; Galway, UL, UNICAL, TU Delft, LNU, HNEE, ELARD, MENDELU.
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Policymakers, innovation support services, academia, civil society, the farming community, and the broader rural community.

Exploitation routes and access	Videos and podcast will be made available through online channels such as YouTube, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, X and Spotify acting as repositories. The materials will be fully accessible via the Multimedia Section on the FLIARA website and embedded in the FLIARA toolkit for wider use.
Protection measure rationale	CC BY 4.0 used to facilitate sharing via the FLIARA Toolkit (YouTube).

Table 47. Videos and Podcasts

5.7.2.12 WP6 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

The exploitation activities for WP6 focus on the longevity and accessibility of the project’s digital identity and outreach materials. These actions ensure that the FLIARA Identity Brand remains recognisable and that all communication assets such as the project website, including the Videos and Podcasts, are maintained and continuously promoted for two years post-project completion.

Action	What?	By Whom?	When?
Protection of the website	Copyright	CE	Completed - April 2023
Trademark®	FLIARA Identity Brand Creative Disclosure Agreement	Galway	ASAP; 2026
Intellectual property rights	Videos and Podcasts	CE	Continuously until end of 2025
Dissemination	Podcast	CE	Continuously until end of 2025
Dissemination	Videos	CE	Continuously until end of 2027

Dissemination	Project Website	CE; All partners	Continuously until end of 2027
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Table 48. WP6 – Exploitation Routes

5.7.2.13 WP7 – KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

WP7 central KER is the second batch of Practice Abstracts. These abstracts summarise the overall outcomes from WP1 through WP6 into concise, usable formats designed specifically for practitioners, civil society, and local action groups (LAGs). Exploitation is focused on ensuring these final, summarised results are uploaded to major European platforms like EIP-AGRI and other open-access repositories to maximise practical uptake and ensure the project's legacy continues to inform rural development policies and initiatives.

Practice abstracts - Batch 2	
Concise description of the KER	15 Practice Abstracts on the outcomes of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5 and WP6
Partners and contributions	Galway, LWL, UTU, UL, ECOLISE, TU DELFT, HNEE, CE
Stakeholder groups and benefits	Civil society, farming community, LAG, policy maker, broader local community. They can tailor decisions, actions and programmes based on the suggestions in the practice abstracts.
Exploitation routes and access	Published on the website and to be uploaded to EIP-AGRI project database of the EU CAP Network.
Protection measure and rationale	Licensing: Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA)

Table 49. Practice abstracts - Batch 2

5.7.2.14 WP7 – EXPLOITATION ROUTES

WP7 represents the final consolidation phase of the project's exploitation efforts. The primary action is ensuring the second batch of Practice Abstracts is fully disseminated through major practitioner channels, guaranteeing that the synthesised key outcomes from all WPs reach Local Action Groups, civil society, and the farming community efficiently.

Action	What?	By Who m?	When?
Intellectual property rights	Creative Commons	CE	Completed – September 2025
Dissemination of deliverables through open access repositories (ARAN, EUFARMBOOK, Zenodo)	Practice Abstracts	CE, Galway	Continuous – By early 2026
Dissemination of Practice Abstracts via EIP AGRI (EU CAP Network platform for practitioners)	Practice Abstracts batch 2	– CE	ASAP; Early 2026

Table 50. WP7 – Exploitation Routes

5.8 EXPLOITATION PLAN PER PARTNER

The following section details how the KERs will be utilised by the FLIARA consortium partners, based on the FLIARA Exploitation Plan per Partner Template. This template required each partner to detail:

- **KERs of Main Interest:** Identification of the specific KERs most relevant to the partner's ongoing work and strategic priorities.
- **Integration with Current Work and Plans:** A clear explanation of how the KERs align with existing activities, research agendas, or policy advocacy efforts.
- **Planned Exploitation Activities:** A detailed description of how the partner intends to utilise each KER (e.g., integrating into training, informing policy work, leveraging networks, or incorporating into new project proposals).

5.8.1 ECOLISE

ECOLISE	KER of main interest: Strategic Action Plan for Community of Practice Events (Deliverable D4.1)
<p>The Strategic Action Plan is a transferable methodology for initiating inclusive multi-stakeholder engagement around gender-just rural innovation. For ECOLISE, this is an asset to enhance its Communities for Future framework by embedding structured co-creation spaces in rural regions. Beyond FLIARA, ECOLISE will adapt and upscale this model to train member organisations in building regional learning platforms, fostering intersectoral alliances, and advancing policy advocacy grounded in lived rural experiences—especially those of women leaders. The Action Plan serves as both a blueprint and capacity-building tool for grassroots innovation ecosystems.</p>	
ECOLISE	KER of main interest: Report on Community of Practice Networking Events (Deliverable D4.2)
<p>This report documents the process, structure, and outcomes of four high-impact Community of Practice (CoP) events across Europe. ECOLISE will exploit this result to showcase the effectiveness of community-driven, gender-responsive innovation platforms in influencing rural development agendas. As a legacy asset, the report provides replicable formats for grassroots-led networking and knowledge exchange. ECOLISE will use it to support ongoing advocacy for participatory governance models within EU rural and Green Deal policies, while also sharing it with its member networks as a practical guide for organising inclusive, multi-actor policy dialogues at local and regional levels.</p>	
ECOLISE	KER of main interest: Benchmarking Initial Report on Policy and Legal Frameworks (Deliverable D4.3)
<p>This report synthesises gaps and opportunities in EU and national policies impacting women-led innovation in rural areas. ECOLISE will leverage it to reinforce its policy advocacy, particularly in aligning local initiatives with broader systemic change. The benchmarking tool informs ECOLISE’s grassroots policy labs and supports its mission to democratise policymaking by grounding demands in lived experiences. Post-FLIARA, it will be used to train community actors in policy analysis and to strengthen ECOLISE’s contributions to consultations and position papers targeting CAP reform, the EU Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas, and future gender-equality frameworks.</p>	

ECOLISE	KER of main interest: FLIARA Toolkit for Women-led Rural Innovation (Deliverable D4.4)
<p>The FLIARA Toolkit compiles actionable resources—fact sheets, podcasts, video blogs—showcasing women-led rural innovations. ECOLISE will exploit it as an educational and advocacy instrument within its Communities for Future programme, tailoring the content for use in grassroots training, awareness campaigns, and community resilience building. It will serve as a living library of inspiration and practical guidance for local groups striving to centre gender equity in innovation. By translating this toolkit into multiple formats and languages, ECOLISE will widen its reach and empower its network to promote inclusive, regenerative solutions across diverse rural contexts.</p>	
ECOLISE	KER of main interest: Gender-Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas (Deliverable D4.5)
<p>This guide synthesises key drivers, barriers, and enabling conditions for female-led rural innovation. ECOLISE will adopt it as a foundational reference to mainstream gender justice across its strategic actions and community-led policy engagements. It provides concrete pathways for empowering women innovators and will inform ECOLISE’s future capacity-building, storytelling, and advocacy efforts. Positioned as a tool for systemic transformation, the guide will support ECOLISE in amplifying women’s agency in decision-making spaces and shaping narratives around just transitions—linking grassroots practice with EU-level gender and rural development frameworks.</p>	

Table 51. ECOLISE: KER of main interest

5.8.2 GALWAY

Galway	KER of main interest: D1.1: Conceptual Framework D1.2: Women-led Innovation Research Review
<p>These deliverables provide content that will feed into the FLIARA book, particularly the chapters towards the start of the book in section 1 that frame the publication and provide background on existing knowledge. These deliverables can also provide a basis for further conference papers and wider peer-reviewed academic publications published as open access. They have already provided a basis for a number of conference papers and presentations at a variety of events (e.g. other European funded projects and local stakeholder events). The co-authored paper alongside other FLIARA partners published in European Countryside titled 'Empowering Women-Led</p>	

<p>Innovations: Key Players in Realising the Long-Term Vision For Rural Areas' draws on D1.1 and D1.2. Three further publications are also in progress led by the Galway team (a encyclopaedia entry, book chapter and a peer-reviewed journal article) that link to these deliverables. The findings also provide context and evidence that have fed into new funding applications.</p>	
Galway	<p>KER of main interest: D3.3: Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and Fact Sheets on Female Innovations - specifically the Ireland Case Studies (2x Farm and 1x Rural) and D3.4 – Comparative analysis report</p>
<p>The D3.3 deliverable provides content that will provide a basis for a chapter of the FLIARA book reflecting on the Irish case studies. The Irish case studies also provide a potential basis for further wider peer-reviewed academic publications and conference papers published as open access. The case study findings have also provided an important evidence base for Ireland's policy briefs published under D5.1 and this is also discussed further below. The case studies also provide a resource that can feed into undergraduate and postgraduate teaching at the Discipline of Geography, University of Galway. The findings also provide context and evidence that have fed into new funding applications. The comparative analysis report D3.4 also provides scope for co-authored publications with other FLIARA partners. The D3.3 Fact sheets on women-led innovations can provide a resource for local development organisations, such as Local Action Groups, and shape their work supporting women-led innovation.</p>	
Galway	<p>KER of main interest: D1.5 - Initial Guidelines Policy Benchmarking D4.3 - Benchmarking Initial Report D5.3 - Gender Benchmarking Report</p>
<p>These reports have potential to feed into a peer-reviewed academic publication and conference papers on gender benchmarking. They have already been drawn on in presentations for FLIARA's own dissemination events and Community of Practice. The reports more broadly provide a sound knowledge basis that can feed into the policy influencing work of the Rural Studies Cluster at the Discipline of Geography. There is also further room to build on this knowledge base and adapt, refine and further develop it in a national and local context in Ireland. These deliverables also provide policy related content that can feed into closing chapters of the FLIARA book where policy conclusions and recommendations are outlined.</p>	
Galway	<p>KER of main interest: D5.1 - Policy booklet and policy briefs and D1.3 – Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks in relation to women-led innovation</p>
<p>As part of D5.1, the University of Galway team, in collaboration with our Teagasc and Longford Women's Link FLIARA colleagues have produced nine national policy briefs for Ireland covering policy domains related to agriculture, rural development and gender equality. D1.3 provided an important baseline of policy information in which to frame our policy briefs. Case study findings from D3.3 also provided a core evidence base relating to key challenges and opportunities focused on in Ireland's national policy briefs. The policy briefs and booklet provide a set of policy stakeholder</p>	

<p>engagement tools to assist with the wider policy influencing work of the Rural Studies Cluster at the Discipline of Geography, such as targeting Local Action Groups and wider policy stakeholders. They will feed into continuing to build the existing efforts in policy influence and policy stakeholder engagement in the field of gender, rural and farming policy. These deliverables also provide content that will feed into the FLIARA book, particularly a chapter on the European policy context.</p>	
Galway	<p>KER of main interest: D4.4 – FLIARA Toolkit D4.5 – Gender Specific Guide to Female- Led Innovation in Farming and Rural areas D3.3 – Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and Fact Sheets on Female Innovations D1.2: Women-led Innovation Research Review</p>
<p>These resources provide a set of materials that can feed into undergraduate and postgraduate teaching at the Discipline of Geography in subjects linked to rural and agricultural geography, as well as wider fields of innovation and gender studies within the geography discipline. They also provide important tools and materials the University of Galway team will disseminate in our networks to policy and entrepreneur stakeholders. The D4.5 Gender Specific Guide can also provide a resource for local development organisations, such as Local Action Groups, and shape their work supporting women-led innovation.</p>	
Galway	<p>KER of main interest: D2.2 – Future vision manifestations D2.3 – Sustainability Innovations D2.4 – Women’s Potential Contributions to sustainability Innovations</p>
<p>Based on the Connemara region findings specifically, these deliverables provide content that can provide a potential basis for peer-reviewed academic publications published as open access in collaboration with our UTU colleagues. The vision cards provide a resource that can potentially feed into teaching of undergraduate and postgraduate modules at the Discipline of Geography, University of Galway.</p>	
Galway	<p>KER of main interest: D5.2 – Participatory Scenario Development Report</p>
<p>This report provides a basis for potential peer-reviewed academic publications and conference papers co-authored with our colleagues at UTU. This report also provides evidence to assist with the wider policy influencing work of the Rural Studies Cluster at the Discipline of Geography. The Discipline of Geography has prior experience of scenario development from other European projects. This report adds to the Rural Studies Cluster’s knowledge and resources based in this specialist approach to policy influence and policy stakeholder engagement. The findings will be disseminated by the University of Galway team in our networks to policy and entrepreneur stakeholders.</p>	

Galway	KER of main interest: D3.5 – Practice Abstracts – batch 1 and D7.4 – Practice Abstracts – batch 2
<p>The Practice Abstracts provide tools for policy and entrepreneur stakeholder engagement. The findings will be disseminated by the University of Galway team in our networks to academic, policy and entrepreneur stakeholders.</p>	
Galway	KER of main interest: D4.1 – Strategic Action Plan and D4.2 – Report on Community of Practice Networking events
<p>These deliverables provide a model for implementation of a Community of Practice (CoP), as well as assessment and reporting of how this model worked in practice. This provides important knowledge and learnings that can be applied to other multi-actor projects applying the CoP model and further funding applications by University of Galway where a CoP model might also be relevant to implement. The findings will be disseminated by the University of Galway team in our networks to academic, policy and entrepreneur stakeholders.</p>	

Table 52. Galway: KER of main interest

5.8.3 UTU

UTU	KER of main interest: Policy Booklet
<p>Chapter 1. elaborates on gaps in policy. UTU can take these gaps into consideration in future research projects e.g. how to address these gaps and find solutions. Chapter 2. FLIARA methods and futures can be implemented as good practices and examples. This chapter would be very useful for other projects relating to women in rural areas. These methods also provide example on how to facilitate participation, and this can be applied to other groups as well (young people, farmers etc.). Chapter 4. Farming and Agri-food gather information that is useful in many rural development initiatives relating to agriculture. UTU (FFRC) is deeply engaged in rural development and will find these policy findings helpful in future projects.</p>	

UTU	KER of main interest: D3.3 reports and fact sheets on female innovation
<p>Case study reports derived from women innovators in rural and farm context can be exploited in other research projects even on a national level. There is much potential in doing research relating to Nordic rural entrepreneurship, good practices and examples. We can explore the differences between Swedish and Finnish rural development, entrepreneurship and practices.</p>	
UTU	KER of main interest: Vision Cards
<p>Vision cards will be useful to us in future research projects. The cards can be used in diverse ways to facilitate dialogue in rural development as well as foresight workshops. For us, tools like vision cards are immensely helpful with gathering insights from different stakeholder groups from policy makers, researchers, NGO's and local communities.</p>	

Table 53. UTU: KER of main interest

5.8.4 TU DELFT

TU Delft	KER of main interest: Policy Booklet
<p>Condensed overview of policy relevant outcomes of FLIARA can be of interest for education and valorisation of research efforts.</p>	
TU Delft	KER of main interest: Benchmarking Report
<p>Benchmarking can be considered a way to compare progress and the methods produced can be used for further analysis.</p>	

TU Delft	KER of main interest: WP3 results
Overview and analysis of female innovators in farming in rural areas is an asset for thinking and reflecting on rural areas.	
TU Delft	KER of main interest: Assessment of rural and farming policy and legal frameworks
In WP1 an overview is made of polices. This can be used to place certain policies in context.	
TU Delft	KER of main interest: FLIARA Conceptual Framework
Conceptual frameworks can be of relevance for the analysis of rural issues.	

Table 54. TU Delft: KER of main interest

5.8.5 HLK – JÖNKÖPING

HLK	KER of main interest: Policy briefs
<p>In cooperation with LNU (Linnaeus University) meetings were held with policy- and administrative stakeholders to present and discuss the policy briefs. Five meetings were conducted in September 2025.</p> <p>A debate article focussing the pivotal role of provision of rural schools, preschools and leisure activities for enabling female-led innovation was published in four local Swedish newspapers in November 2025.</p>	
HLK	KER of main interest: Case study (D3:3)
<p>The findings from the case studies will be used to write academic papers. Two papers are in the process as of September 2025, in cooperation with other consortium partners.</p>	
HLK	KER of main interest: Case study (D3:3)
<p>The findings of the case study will be used as input and background material to formulate applications for research grants. Two such applications, focusing on the role of digitalisation for women's rural entrepreneurship are in process as of September 2025.</p>	

Table 55. HLK – Jönköping: KER of main interest

5.8.6 HNEE

HNEE	KER of main interest: German Policy Recommendations (D5.1)
<p>The draft German policy recommendations have already been disseminated to women’s, rural and farmers’ associations and shared with policy experts at the National Foundation for Gender Equality. Building on this dissemination, our exploitation plan includes (once the policy briefs are finalised within the consortium) sharing the translated briefs directly with German policymakers in late 2025 and early 2026. This will include:</p> <p>Circulating them to the gender equality officers of all German Federal States with an invitation to a personal online talk to explain and discuss the options for further incorporation. We expect the arrangement of at least 5 online talks with officials from the equality and diversity departments of different Federal States.</p> <p>On the national level, we will send our set of policy briefs to equality officers or others responsible for gender mainstreaming at the Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs, Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry for the Environment. We expect to arrange at least 2 online talks with officials of Federal Ministries. Not all ministries have such an equal opportunity officer, or if they do, it’s mainly for staff, not specifically gender mainstreaming.</p> <p>This direct engagement will support the adoption of gender-sensitive policies and further HNEE’s impact in the sector. By actively liaising with key stakeholders and policy experts and engaging in policy dialogues, HNEE strengthens its reputation as a specialist in gender aspects of agriculture. These activities open new opportunities for HNEE to provide expert policy advice and take part in future policy development processes at both the regional and national levels.</p>	
HNEE	KER of main interest: Results of German Case Study (D3.3)
<p>A forthcoming scientific article will highlight the unique sustainability competencies demonstrated by women innovators in the German context. Once published in a leading journal related to agriculture or rural studies, and presented at relevant scientific conferences, this result will enhance HNEE’s reputation as a research institution specialising in gender-related agricultural research. The article will serve as a foundation for further research collaborations and recognition in academic circles. Furthermore, to ensure the results have practical impact at HNEE, the findings from the German case study will be disseminated through internal events selected in consultation with HNEE’s equal opportunity officer. Planned activities include contributions to the recurring Gender and Climate Workshops, a Lunch Lecture, and a dedicated session for Women and Girls in Science Day 2026. These initiatives will make the research accessible and relevant to HNEE’s academic staff and students, fostering institutional learning and promoting gender and sustainability competencies within the academic community.</p>	

<p>HNEE</p>	<p>KER of main interest: Findings of the German Case Study (D3.3 and D3.4), as well as D4.4 FLIARA Toolkit and D4.5 Gender Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas.</p>
<p>The findings from the German case study, along with Deliverables D4.4 and D4.5, will serve as foundational resources for HNEE’s advisory services targeted at potential women innovators in Germany. By translating these results into actionable guidance, HNEE will equip women in agriculture with the knowledge and competencies needed to drive innovation and sustainability.</p> <p>To maximise impact, HNEE will develop outreach initiatives in collaboration with leading organisations focused on women and innovation in agriculture, including the Thünen Institut, the German Rural Women Association, and the German Rural Network (which connects to state-level Innovation Support Services). These partnerships will create synergies, expand the reach of HNEE’s expertise, and foster a supportive ecosystem for women-led rural innovation.</p> <p>Through these actions, HNEE will reinforce its profile as a practice-oriented institution committed to sustainable development and the advancement of women in agriculture.</p>	
<p>HNEE</p>	<p>KER of main interest: Gender-focused project experience</p>
<p>The experience gained through participation in FLIARA equips HNEE with the practical skills required to apply successfully for new projects with a gender dimension. By integrating these competencies, HNEE will strengthen its ability to meet and demonstrate compliance with gender equality objectives—a key requirement in publicly-funded research and innovation initiatives.</p> <p>We will connect with HNEE colleagues who are preparing or conducting gender-focused projects to share best practices, foster cross-project learning, and enhance capacity for effective project implementation. These collaborative actions not only support ongoing fulfilment of gender equality goals but also reinforce HNEE’s reputation as a competent and experienced partner in gender-focused research and innovation.</p> <p>Together, these exploitation activities will enable HNEE to further its strategic aims in gender equality, expand its project portfolio, and contribute expertise to broader research and policy networks.</p>	

Table 56. HNEE: KER of main interest

5.8.7 LNU

LNU	KER of main interest: Policy Briefs
<p>In cooperation with HLK meetings were held with national and local policy- and administrative stakeholders to present and discuss the policy briefs. Five meetings were planned as of September 2025. LNU will continue this works during 2026 sharing insights from FLIARA and the policy briefs at events LNU is invited to. One of the policy briefs will be the basis for further research and an article.</p>	
LNU	KER of main interest: Case studies, WP2 deliverables
<p>The findings from the case studies will be used to write academic papers. The findings from WP2 in Sweden will also be used as the basis for an article. In total five papers are in the process as of September 2025. Two in cooperation with other consortium partners.</p>	
LNU	KER of main interest: Case study D.3.3, WP2 deliverables
<p>The findings of the case study will be used as input and background material to formulate applications for research grants. As of September 2025, three applications are being developed: one on rural development, one on digital village futures and one on farming future.</p>	

Table 57. LNU: KER of main interest

5.8.8 UL

<p>UL</p>	<p>KER of main interest: Future vision manifestations (D2.2), Sustainability Innovations (D2.3), Women's Potential Contributions to Sustainability Innovations (D2.4), Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas (D3.3), Comparative analysis report (D3.4) and Innovation Women videos, podcasts, and video blogs (D6.5)</p>
<p>One of the main exploitable results for our organisation is the integration of FLIARA results into teaching materials and activities at the Faculty of Arts, Department of Geography, University of Ljubljana. At the Master's level, courses such as Rural Development Disparities and Endogenous Rural Development will incorporate theoretical insights, empirical findings, and methodological approaches from the project. FLIARA deliverables represent a valuable knowledge asset that could strengthen the postgraduate curriculum at our Faculty and enriches students' understanding of gender, innovation, and sustainability in rural contexts. At the undergraduate level, FLIARA results will also be embedded in teaching practice. In the courses Agricultural Geography and Rural Geography, project findings will be used to showcase real-life examples of women-led innovations, future visions for rural areas, and pathways of sustainable rural development. Innovation Women videos, podcasts, and video blogs will also be integrated into career shadowing activities within the course Career Development of Employees at the Department of Psychology, Faculty of Arts.</p>	
<p>UL</p>	<p>KER of main interest: Gender Specific Guide to Female-Led Innovation in Farming and Rural Areas (D4.5), Practise Abstracts (D3.5 and D7.4), Women's Potential Contributions to Sustainability Innovations (D2.4)</p>
<p>UL is integrating the research results of the FLIARA project into our work with rural stakeholders, especially through Local Action Groups (LAGs), within the framework of the Slovenian Rural Development Society/Association educational activities, where members of our research team are active. We already know that gender perspective in rural and agricultural innovation will be one of the topics of the Slovenian Rural Parliament (June 2026). Already in the preparatory phase, within the regional rural parliaments (autumn 2025), this theme has been highlighted and included as topic of one of the workshops, led by FLIARA UL team. We will discuss it further with stakeholders in rural development (LAGs, municipalities, representatives of the agricultural advisory service, educational institutions, entrepreneurs, etc.).</p>	
<p>UL</p>	<p>KER of main interest: "D1.1 FLIARA Conceptual framework, D3.1 Research Guidelines and Thematic Selection and D4.3 Benchmarking initial report</p>
<p>The topic of female-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas will be proposed to Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency and the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food as a priority theme for Target Research Programmes in the 2026/2027 call for research–application projects. By applying FLIARA framework at the national level and methodological guidelines we would like to contribute to further evidence-based support in Slovenia.</p>	

UL	KER of main interest: D5.1 Policy Booklet and Policy Briefs
<p>As part of our exploitation strategy, we will integrate project summaries, in particular policy briefs and policy recommendations, into the activities of interdisciplinary working groups at the Ministry. Two members of our team are active in the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food's working group on young farmers, where we will specifically highlight the female/gender perspective and ensure that it becomes an integral part of our contributions to the generational and innovation renewal policy dialogue.</p>	
UL	KER of main interest: D2.2 Future vision manifestations, D2.3 Sustainability Innovations
<p>Within the framework of the promotional activities of the Department of Geography, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana, and in cooperation with secondary and primary schools, we have also highlighted this topic as part of our outreach offer for school kids. In these activities, we primarily drew on the results of WP2, particularly the visions of the future of rural areas.</p>	
UL	KER of main interest: WP3 case studies, also WP2 outputs
<p>The findings from the case studies will be further analysed and translated into academic outputs, including peer-reviewed journal articles. Two papers are already in preparation. Similarly, we expect that the results from WP2, visions-innovations-women contribution of rural areas, will also be translated into academic publications.</p>	

Table 58. UL: KER of main interest

5.8.9 MENDELU

MENDELU	KER of main interest: Policy Recommendations
<p>The usability of the project results towards practice will be based on six Policy briefs, which cover various aspects of the problem. These results will be used in communications with regional authorities, authorities of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic and its branches, subjects dealing with female question or when working in various committees and advisory bodies, possibly for appearances in the media. In interaction with practice, the recommendations will be further elaborated and modified. This procedure is in line with the university's current orientation towards greater application of results in practice.</p>	
MENDELU	KER of main interest: research development, WP1, WP6
<p>The implementation of the FLIARA project results towards further research will be used in the preparation of other research projects. This concerns not only the issue of women, but also the issue of rural entrepreneurship in various types of activities. Participation in the preparation of the HORIZON-RIA project "New relationship between the youth, family and society" or participation in the Visegrád+ project "Family Farms in Short Food Supply Chains: Transfer of Experience from Czechia, Slovakia and Poland" can be mentioned. The gained data is applied in publishing activities. The aim is to expand research into the position of rural women, which, with some exceptions, is neglected in Czech science.</p>	

MENDELU	KER of main interest: deepening the education through knowledge and network, WP3, WP4
<p>The results of the FLIARA project will also be used in teaching students, especially in the subject of Geography of Agriculture, Environmental Ethics, Rural Development or others, including the University of the 3rd Age. Topics for bachelor's, master's and doctoral theses will be offered. The contacts with innovative women in the field obtained are used to prepare excursions for students. We assume that the main problem of women's issues is the persistence of certain patriarchal prejudices, which can be overcome through education.</p>	

Table 59. MENDELU: KER of main interest

5.8.10 CE	
CE	KER of main interest: FLIARA Conceptual Framework
<p>The framework will be incorporated into CE's internal methodology for designing new EU projects, ensuring future proposals explicitly adopt the FLIARA approach to gender-inclusive innovation. CE will use it in regional and national policy advocacy to demonstrate a best-practice model for rural innovation.</p>	
CE	KER of main interest: FLIARA Policy Briefs & Policy Booklet
<p>These are key resources for CE's advocacy work on Gender Equality in rural areas. They will be actively used to inform and influence regional and national policy discussions in Spain, particularly during consultations related to CAP Strategic Plans and rural development initiatives.</p>	
CE	KER of main interest: FLIARA Innovation Cards, Vision Cards, & Factsheets

These highly practical and visual tools will be immediately integrated into CE's training and workshop portfolio. They will be used to facilitate discussions on sustainability, innovation, and gender equality with stakeholders, especially Local Action Groups (LAGs) and local community leaders across Spain.

CE

**KER of main interest:
Videos and Podcasts**

These materials will be used to create engaging content for CE's online training modules and webinars, improving the accessibility and reach of FLIARA findings to a wider audience of practitioners and students in the Canary Islands and beyond.

CE

**KER of main interest:
FLIARA Project Website**

CE is committed to hosting and technically maintaining the public FLIARA website on its servers for a minimum of two years after the project ends (until 31 December 2027) to guarantee continued access to all resources. There will be a possibility to extend its hosting (CE will cover the cost of the associated expenses).

CE

**KER of main interest:
FLIARA Identity Brand**

Ensure the FLIARA visual identity, logo, and branding are used consistently in all post-project dissemination efforts and proper crediting FLIARA trademarks by the University of Galway.

CE	KER of main interest: D3.3 Case Study Report
Use the collated data and case study analysis in Spain in future project proposals demonstrating CE's expertise in women-led innovation and rural sustainability.	
CE	KER of main interest: D4.1 – Strategic Action Plan
The SAP, originally elaborated to guide the Community of Practice by the University of Galway and ensure network sustainability, will be used by CE as a consultancy blueprint. CE will leverage its structure and proposed actions to advise regional and local authorities (including LAGs) on developing evidence-based action plans that address gender inequality in rural areas specifically for Outermost Regions.	

5.9 MEASURES TO MAXIMISE EXPLOITATION

The exploitation strategy is centred on maximising academic, policy, and civil society uptake of project results. All outputs are designed for free access and use, with licensing that supports educational, advocacy, and policy development objectives. No commercialisation is foreseen, as the project focus is on public interest and knowledge valorisation across stakeholder communities.

5.9.1 LONG-TERM SUSTAINABILITY, ARCHIVING, AND IMPACT MONITORING

To ensure the FLIARA project's results remain accessible and continue to foster impact beyond the project's official end date, the consortium has implemented a robust long-term sustainability and archiving strategy, primarily managed by CE. Given the cessation of formal reporting by consortium partners post-project, and wider dissemination of the KERs, all monitoring efforts focus on automated metrics and verifiable archival commitments.

5.9.1.1 SUSTAINABILITY COMMITMENTS (CE RESPONSIBILITY)

Commitment	Description	Duration
Website Hosting & Maintenance	The project website (www.fliara.eu) will remain active, serving as the central hub for all project	2 Years post-project end.

	documentation, specific news, and links to open-access resources.	
Digital Archiving (Zenodo)	All final, approved public deliverables, including reports, policy documents, and toolkits, will be uploaded to a dedicated Zenodo Community under a Creative Commons license (CC BY) to guarantee permanent, citable access.	Continuous.
Specialised Platform Dissemination	Key practice-oriented results, including all Practice Abstracts (D3.5, D7.4) and relevant research reviews (D1.2), will be disseminated via the EIP-AGRI (now EU CAP Network) practitioner section and the EUFARMBOOK .	Continuous.
Network Maintenance	The official FLIARA Community of Practice LinkedIn Group (current members: 150+) will be monitored by CE as a legacy knowledge-sharing platform for continued dialogue among policymakers, researchers, and practitioners.	2 Years post-project end.

Table 60. Sustainability Commitments

5.9.1.2 MEASURABLE EXPLOITATION TARGETS (TRACKABLE METRICS)

The following targets are set based on platforms or verifiable actions and will be monitored by CE beyond the GA to assess the initial success and enduring reach of the project outputs.

Area of Exploitation	Target KER(s)	Metric (Target to be Achieved by Project End + 1 Year)
Open Access Reach	All Final Deliverables	Achieve 500 cumulative downloads of all final project deliverables uploaded to the Zenodo and ARAN repositories.
High-Level Policy Impact	Policy Booklet (D5.1), Policy Briefs (D5.1)	Achieve at least 1 formal citation or direct reference to FLIARA's Policy Briefs or Benchmarking reports in a high-level strategic document (e.g., OECD, European Commission working paper, national strategic plan).

Community & Practice Uptake	FLIARA (D4.4), Gender-Specific (D4.5)	Toolkit Gender-Guide Achieve 1,000 unique page views or PDF downloads of the FLIARA Toolkit and Gender-Specific Guide combined via the project website and open-access repositories.
Academic Pipeline Success	Case Study Findings (D3.3), WP2/WP5 Reports	At least 5 peer-reviewed academic articles resulting from FLIARA are formally published by consortium members within the year post-project closure.

Table 61. Post-project Trackable Metrics

5.9.2 PARTNER COMMITMENT TO POST-PROJECT EXPLOITATION

The consortium’s exploitation strategy is designed to create sustainable outputs that are intrinsically linked to the partners’ core activities. While formal project reporting concludes, all partners remain professionally and institutionally committed to fostering the uptake of FLIARA results through their long-term, established channels:

- **Academic Integration:** Partner Universities (Galway, UL, UTU, TU Delft, LNU, HLK, HNEE) have integrated FLIARA material into teaching curricula and will pursue peer-reviewed publications using internal research funds and university resources, leveraging the project data as foundational material for academic careers and departmental specialisations.
- **Policy Advocacy Alignment:** Non-profit and advocacy partners (ECOLISE, CE) and policy-engaged universities (HNEE, UL, LNU) will continue to use the Policy Briefs, Benchmarking Reports to inform their regular contributions to EU and national policy consultations (e.g., CAP, Rural Vision, Gender Equality frameworks), ensuring FLIARA's evidence remains current in high-level policy dialogues.
- **Future Project Leverage:** All partners have identified using FLIARA concepts and methodologies (D1.1 Conceptual Framework, D4.1 Strategic Action Plan) as the foundation for future research grant proposals, guaranteeing that the project's intellectual legacy directly influences the design and execution of subsequent, related projects.

In this way, the FLIARA results are not standalone deliverables but rather essential building blocks for the partners' ongoing institutional missions in promoting gender equality, innovation, and sustainability in rural Europe.

5.9.2.1 FLIARA LOGOTYPE INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY PROTECTION (TRADEMARK)

To ensure the long-term protection and integrity of the project's logotype, the FLIARA name and logo will be registered as a national trademark in Ireland, led by the University of Galway and under a Creative Disclosure Agreement, funded annually by the University of Galway. This strategic exploitation measure protects the logo and prevents unauthorised commercial use by third parties post-project. The registration secures the intellectual asset value of the brand, which is critical for leveraging the project's reputation in future funding applications, spin-off projects, and policy consultations. To guarantee seamless future dissemination and legacy activities by the consortium, the University of Galway will grant all partners an irrevocable, non-exclusive, royalty-free licence to use the registered trademark indefinitely for all non-commercial, public-good dissemination and exploitation purposes related to FLIARA's results. This means no partner organisation will incur any fees or usage payments for utilising the FLIARA brand or logo in relation to non-commercial follow-up work.

Figure 76. FLIARA Trademark

5.9.2.2 SCHOLARLY LEGACY: THE EDWARD ELGAR BOOK

The flagship academic output and a major element of the project's intellectual legacy is the forthcoming book, "Policy Infrastructures for Female-Led Rural Innovation", to be published by the prestigious Edward Elgar Publishing and led by Galway.

This publication represents the definitive scholarly synthesis of all FLIARA research, drawing on the foundational conceptual work (WP1), the envisioning processes (WP2), case studies (WP3), and policy analyses (WP5). Coordinated by the University of Galway and featuring chapters from consortium partners (LWL, Teagasc, TU Delft, HNEE, UL, UTU, MENDELU, UNICAL, OULU, HLK, ECOLISE, ELARD, LNU, and CE), this book will serve as the essential reference point for researchers, students, and advanced policy analysts focused on gender, rural development, and innovation globally.

5.9.2.3 POLICY LEGACY: POLICY BRIEFS AND POLICY BOOKLET

The direct policy legacy of FLIARA is channelled through 58 policy briefs and the overarching FLIARA policy booklet published via the FLIARA project repositories. This is the project's most practical output for immediate political and governance action.

These resources translate complex evidence into a clear, actionable roadmap for strengthening the ecosystems that enable women's innovation. They crystallise findings around the seven interconnected networks (social, financial, work–life, economic, advisory, learning, and political) that are crucial for rural sustainability and gender equality.

FLIARA has established a robust policy infrastructure designed to influence future iterations of the CAP Strategic Plans and other rural development funding instruments across Europe for years to come by presenting these policy outputs to high-level bodies, including the OECD and the European Commission and national level.

5.9.2.4 THE FLIARA TOOLKIT: CENTRAL REPOSITORY FOR EXPLOITATION

All exploitation routes—including the academic chapters, the policy briefs, the innovation cards, and the conceptual frameworks—converge in the FLIARA Toolkit, which is accessible via the project website or at www.fliara/toolkit.

As the partner responsible for the website and visual identity, CE is committed to ensuring the integrity of this legacy. CE guarantees the technical hosting and maintenance of the website and toolkit for a minimum of two years post-project (until 31 December 2027). This commitment, alongside the open-access licensing (CC-BY) of all final deliverables, guarantees that FLIARA's complete body of work remains a permanent, citable, and easily exploitable resource for all future users.

5.9.3 EXPLOITATION TRANSITION

The FLIARA project has structured its exploitation efforts to maximise integration during the funded period, ensuring that all KERs are translated into actionable formats (toolkits, policy briefs) and presented to target audiences before December 31, 2025. Post-closure, the exploitation phase transitions into archival preservation and long-term monitoring. The commitment from CE ensures the sustainability of all digital assets, while academic partners continue to convert the project's foundational data into citable, high-impact publications, leveraging their institutional resources to secure the project's enduring legacy.

5.9.4 RISKS AND MITIGATION STRATEGIES

While the plan anticipates wide uptake of FLIARA outputs by academic, policy, and civil society actors, several risks could affect long-term sustainability and impact:

5.9.4.1 SUSTAINED ACCESS AND HOSTING:

- **Risk:** Project repositories or digital platforms (websites, toolkit hosting) may not be maintained beyond the initial two years post-project, limiting access to outputs.
- **Mitigation:** Partners commit to hosting resources for at least two years and to seeking integration with larger institutional or European repositories (e.g., Zenodo, ARAN, EUFARMBOOK) for longer-term preservation.

5.9.4.2 POLICY UPTAKE BARRIERS:

- **Risk:** Recommendations may not be adopted by policymakers due to shifting priorities, limited awareness, or lack of engagement.
- **Mitigation:** Continued outreach is planned via workshops, conferences, direct dialogue (e.g., online meetings with equality officers), and engagement with networks to maximise policy relevance and visibility.

5.9.4.3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

- **Risk:** Limited or inconsistent engagement from civil society or practitioner groups might reduce the plan's reach.
- **Mitigation:** The strategy includes partnering with established networks (e.g., ECOLISE), multilingual campaigns, and integrating resources into ongoing advocacy and learning programmes.

5.9.4.4 DATA PROTECTION AND LICENSING COMPLIANCE

- **Risk:** Misuse or misattribution of open-access outputs may occur.
- **Mitigation:** All resources disseminated via repositories are covered by clear Creative Commons licensing, emphasising attribution and appropriate use, and periodic monitoring of repositories will be carried out.

Regular review of risks and active adaptation of mitigation strategies will be carried out by WP leaders and the Exploitation Manager (CE) up to four years after the project ends.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Over three years, WP6 has provided a robust and adaptive framework for communication, dissemination and exploitation, enabling FLIARA to reach and engage a wide spectrum of stakeholders while consistently exceeding its initial quantitative targets. The KPI analysis shows very strong performance across events (68 events in which FLIARA has been presented and an international final conference with 107 onsite and 229 online participants), newsletters (six issues with 1.482 subscribers and 781 readers per issue), earned media (167 pieces), website analytics (44.665 visits and 21.596 active users) and social media growth (3.993 followers across main channels), as well as in the production of scientific and non-scientific outputs (four peer-reviewed articles, 22 non-scientific publications, 200 fact sheets, 25 practice abstracts, 20 videos, 10 podcasts and six webinars).

Qualitatively, the visibility campaign, the strong and coherent visual identity, and the focus on the stories of 200 women innovators and 20 FLIARA Ambassadors have positioned the project as a reference point on women-led rural innovation in Europe. The integrated digital architecture – comprising the website, innovators and ambassadors' sections, practice abstracts, policy booklet and policy briefs and the toolkit – has created a user-friendly gateway to FLIARA resources, while synergies with sister projects, the EU CAP Network / EU FarmBook and other EU-level actors have embedded FLIARA messages within wider policy and practice communities.

The final exploitation plan consolidates these achievements into a forward-looking strategy that identifies key exploitable results, defines their value propositions, and sets out concrete pathways for continued use by partners, ambassadors, advisory services, policymakers and civil society organisations. WP6 has contributed significantly to the long-term sustainability and potential scaling of FLIARA's impact by ensuring open-access availability of core outputs, clarifying roles and responsibilities for post-project maintenance, and anchoring results in existing European networks and repositories.

ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 – MEDIA CLIPPING

Featured	Title	Type	Link
SuperScience	EU Horizon Europe Project: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas “FLIARA”	Factsheet	https://www.superscienceme.it/corner-progetto/fliara-female-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/
University of Ljubljana - Univerza v Ljubljani	Projekt FLIARA vzpostavlja podporno okolje za inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	Factsheet	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/images/drustvo/aktualno/2023/LAS_novice/%C5%A1tevilka_2/Fliara_izjava_za_javnost.pdf
Madam Business Prosperita	Role žen v zemědělství a venkovském životě	Magazine	https://www.iprosperita.cz/images/pdf_mb/madam_business_2023-03.pdf
Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development	FLIARA, GRASS CEILING and SWIFT: Supporting women-led innovation in rural areas	News	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/items/782608/en
Iberian Press	Inicia FLIARA el proyecto europeo que apoyará las prácticas rurales innovadoras lideradas por mujeres	News	https://www.iberianpress.es/noticia/inicia-fliara-el-proyecto-europeo-que-apoyara-las-practicas-rurales-innovadoras-lideradas-por-mujeres/44569
Canarias 7	Mujeres de toda Europa liderarán la innovación rural a través del proyecto FLIARA	News	https://www.canarias7.es/economia/mujeres-europa-lideraran-20230127210835-nt.html
Desarrollo Local	Proyecto europeo FLIARA	News	https://desarrollolocal.emprenemjunts.es/?op=8&n=29228
Demeter	FLIARA: FEMALE LED INNOVATION IN AGRICULTURE AND RURAL AREAS	News	https://h2020-demeter.eu/fliara-female-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/

Galway Pulse	University of Galway receives €3 million to enhance female innovation in agriculture and rural areas	News	https://galwaypulse.com/2023/02/18/agriculture-fliara/amp/
National Rural Network	European Project to Enhance Women's Role in Rural Life Launched	News	https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/farm-viability/farm-viability-news/european-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life-launched/
CYSNEWS .CZ	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://www.cysnews.cz/veda/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/
Red Rural Nacional	El proyecto europeo "FLIARA" saca a la luz las prácticas en innovación ejercidas por las mujeres rurales	News	https://www.redruralnacional.es/noticia/el-proyecto-europeo-fliara-saca-la-luz-las-practicas-en-innovacion-ejercidas-por-las
TU Delft	FLIARA - De rol van vrouwen in een duurzamere toekomst voor het platteland	News	https://www.tudelft.nl/2023/bk/fliara-de-rol-van-vrouwen-in-een-duurzamere-toekomst-voor-het-platteland
Hochschule für nachhaltige Entwicklung Eberswalde (HNEE)	Start für Verbundprojekt „FLIARA“ – Frauengeführte Innovationsprozesse in Landwirtschaft und ländlichem Raum	News	https://www.hnee.de/de/Aktuelles/Hochschulkommunikation/Pressemitteilungen/Start-fr-Verbundprojekt-FLIARA-Frauengefhrte-Innovationsprozesse-in-Landwirtschaft-und-lndlichem-Raum-E11716.htm
Galway Bay FM Limited	University of Galway launches €3m European project to enhance women's role in rural life	News	https://galwaybayfm.ie/galway-bay-fm-news-desk/university-of-galway-launches-e3m-european-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life/
OpenAIRE Research Graph	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	News	https://beopen.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_he::312ece601a4933e1b85d0a9447adc49e
EUROPAPRESS	Una pyme canaria gestionará un proyecto de investigación sobre	News	https://www.europapress.es/islas-canarias/noticia-pyme-canaria-gestionara-proyecto-investigacion-innovacion-mujeres-

	la innovación de mujeres en agricultura y zonas rurales		agricultura-zonas-rurales-20230131131649.html
Teagasc	Horizon Europe project FLIARA to enhance women's role in rural life, agriculture and rural affairs	News	https://www.teagasc.ie/rural-economy/rural-economy/agricultural-economics/research/fliara/
Linnaeus University	FLIARA Kick-off meeting marks the beginning of the project	News	https://lnu.se/en/meet-linnaeus-university/current/news/2023/fliara-kick-off-meeting-marks-the-beginning-of-the-project/
Linnaeus University	Project: FLIARA – Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	News	https://lnu.se/en/research/research-projects/project-fliara-female-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/
Galway Daily	University of Galway launches project to enhance women's role in rural life	News	https://www.galwaydaily.com/news/university-of-galway-launches-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life/
Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA vzpostavlja podporno okolje za inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/index.php?option=com_k2&view=item&id=1428:projekt-fliara-vzpostavlja-podporno-okolje-za-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-in-na-podezelju&Itemid=888&acm=89
Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA - kakšno podeželje želimo?	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/novice/item/1469-ohranimo-travniske-sadovnjake
Društvo za razvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA vzpostavlja podporno okolje za inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/novice/item/1428-projekt-fliara-vzpostavlja-podporno-okolje-za-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-in-na-podezelju
Industria Ambiente	Comienza el proyecto europeo FLIARA que apoyará las prácticas rurales innovadoras lideradas por mujeres	News	https://www.industriambiente.com/noticias/20230127/comienza-el-proyecto-europeo-fliara-que-apoyara-las-practicas-rurales-innovadoras-lideradas-por-mujeres#.Y9PQEsmZNPY

LaVanguardia	Una pyme canaria gestionará un proyecto de investigación sobre la innovación de mujeres en agricultura y zonas rurales	News	https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/canarias/20230131/8722164/pyme-canaria-gestionara-proyecto-investigacion-sobre-innovacion-mujeres-agricultura-zonas-rurales.html
That's Farming	University of Galway launches European-wide women in ag project	News	https://thatsfarming.com/farming-news/womens-role-in-rural-life/
Agriland	University of Galway project to enhance women's role in rural life	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/university-of-galway-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life/
Irish America Magazine	University of Galway Launches EU Project to Enhance Women's Role in Rural Life	News	https://www.irishamerica.com/2023/01/news-roundup-january-14/
Irish Farmers Journal	University of Galway launches project for women in agriculture	News	https://www.farmersjournal.ie/university-of-galway-launches-project-for-women-in-agriculture-744347
MENDELU	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://mendelu.cz/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/?psn=200
Galway Advertiser	University of Galway launches European project to enhance women's role in rural life	News	https://www.advertiser.ie/galway/article/133459/university-of-galway-launches-european-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life
Radio Faro del Noroeste	Mujeres de toda Europa liderarán la innovación rural a través del proyecto FLIARA	News	https://www.radiofarodelnoroeste.es/secciones/sociedad/item/13663-mujeres-de-toda-europa-lideraran-la-innovacion-rural-a-traves-del-proyecto-fliaara
El Blog de Anna Conte	Mujeres de toda Europa liderarán la innovación rural a través del proyecto FLIARA	News	https://elblogdeannaconte.com/mujeres-toda-europa-lideraran-innovacion-rural-a-traves-proyecto-fliaara/

MENDELU	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://af.mendelu.cz/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/
Društvo za rozvoj slovenskega podeželja	Projekt FLIARA - kakšno podeželje želimo?	News	http://www.drustvo-podezelje.si/novice/item/1469-ohranimo-travniske-sadovnjake
ProfiPress	Vědci z Mendelovy univerzity budou zkoumat roli žen v zemědělství	News	https://zemedelec.cz/vedci-z-mendelovy-univerzity-budou-zkoumat-rolu-zen-v-zemedelstvi/
Envi Web	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://www.enviweb.cz/rss/305917
AGRÁRNÍ WWW PORTÁL	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	http://www.agris.cz/clanek/221934
ZAHRADNÍ CTVI	Vědecký tým z MENDELU bude zkoumat roli žen ve venkovském životě	News	https://zahradaweb.cz/vedecky-tym-z-mendelu-bude-zkoumat-rolu-zen-ve-venkovskem-zivote/
Advertiser.ie	University of Galway launches European project to enhance women's role in rural life	News	https://www.advertiser.ie/galway/article/133459/university-of-galway-launches-european-project-to-enhance-womens-role-in-rural-life
DunavNET	FLIARA – Online Forum	News	https://dunavnet.eu/fliara-online-forum/
IrishFarmer	Lessons from India and Europe on co-operative farming	News	https://www.farmersjournal.ie/lessons-from-india-and-europe-on-co-operative-farming-769240
RURALIZATION PROJECT	University of Galway to lead European project on enhancing women's role in agriculture	News	https://ruralization.eu/2023/05/university-of-galway-to-lead-european-project-on-enhancing-womens-role-in-agriculture/
SafeHabitus Project	Building synergies between EU-funded projects	News	https://www.safehabitus.eu/building-synergies-between-eu-funded-projects/
Rural Pact	Online Forum by FLIARA project	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/news/online-forum-fliara-

	promotes Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas		project-promotes-women-led-innovations-agriculture-and-rural-areas_en
RURALIZATION PROJECT	FLIARA Project's Campaign Shines a Spotlight on Women-led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas	News	https://ruralization.eu/2023/06/fliara-projects-campaign-shines-a-spotlight-on-women-led-innovation-in-agriculture-and-rural-areas/
SafeHabitu s Project	Newsletter - July 2023	Newsletter	https://preview.mailerlite.io/emails/webview/337217/93301886013146914
Rural Pact	EU Rural vision - Rural Pact Community Newsletter - July 2023	Newsletter	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/newsletter-archives/46537
ECOLISE & Communities for Future	July Newsletter	Newsletter	https://communitiesforfuture.org/civicrm/mailling/view/?reset=1&id=182&cid=47107&cs=8d5b95c5d6b4d50146adc39a943d4c88_1689103937_168
ECOLISE & Communities for Future	Creating a regenerative and gender equal world	Newsletter	https://communitiesforfuture.org/civicrm/mailling/view/?id=137
Geografska širina	Projekt FLIARA - delavnica snovanja vizij za podeželje LAS Srce Slovenije	Newsletter	https://sites.google.com/view/geografskasirina/starej%C5%A1e-%C5%A1tevilke/2023/april-junij#h.emjlqal4gasu
DEMETER Project	Empowering Farmers - Demeter	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/a04532685a1d/demeter-newsletter-issue-8-march-16856757
EU Rural vision	Rural Pact Community Newsletter - March 2023	Newsletter	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/newsletter-archives/44644
AEIDL - The European Association for Innovation in Local Development	June - July 2023: Newsletter	Newsletter	https://us16.campaign-archive.com/?u=4073cd350ed87293c4dc26b72&id=17810de86d

Red Rural Nacional	Boletín RRN - ENERO 2023	Newsletter	https://www.redruralnacional.es/boletines/enero-2023
PDR CARM	Boletín informativo de enero de 2023 de la Red Rural Nacional - Noticias - PDR	Newsletter	https://pdr.carm.es/-/boletin-informativo-de-enero-de-2023-de-la-red-rural-nacional
EFEAGRO	Mundo Rural	Podcast	https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/mundo-rural/mundo-rural-desperdicio-alimentario/6811188/
PROMĚNY ZEMĚDĚLSTVÍ	Venkov se mění v konzum, role hospodáře se vytrácí. Projekt EU chce posílit úlohu žen	Podcast	https://zpravy.aktualne.cz/ekonomika/promeny-zemedelstvi/podcast-promeny-zemedelstvi-s-miladou-stastnou-z-mendelovy-u/r~6d55d326ca4811edba63ac1f6b220ee8/?fbclid=IwAR1-Hnp7R7eyDEHnv71iPp0HIIVPx80y7N3S-Vqe3kVFzyUmp92FWx7TZLc
Agri-Insider	In Her Field, Episode 1: Professor Maura Farrell, University of Galway, 19.03.23	Video	https://agriinsider.tv/programs/in-her-field-episode-1-ad553e?offset=278
EUCAPNE WORK	Establishing Synergies with EU Funded Projects - FLIARA	Social Media Post	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7095737273417117696?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3Afs_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3Aactivity%3A7095737273417117696%29
EUCAPNE WORK	Social innovation – Solutions for thriving agriculture, forestry and rural areas	Joint Article	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/publications/brochure-social-innovation-solutions-thriving-agriculture-forestry-and-rural-areas_en
Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (European Commission)	Solutions leading to thriving agriculture, forestry and rural areas	Joint Article	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/971c87e4-3a53-11ee-bbad-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-291163364
RED PAC (Rural Pact) Spain	AGOSTO 2023 - RED PAC	Newsletter	https://redpac.es/boletines/agosto-2023

LEADER	Leader April-June 2023 Newsletter	Newsletter	https://leaderfrance.fr/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/ELARD-Newsletter-April-June.pdf
ECOLISE & Communities for Future	September 2023 Newsletter	Newsletter	https://communitiesforfuture.org/civCRM/mailling/view/?reset=1&id=188&cid=51&cs=38392bf513c36e39a818c5eef028ddc8_1694525447_168&fbclid=IwAR2UNMPjDgRjZopjT9G0_8TYrznRWXRgu_9kWmdy-T_Xz_Ft3RJKrz4Fol
Red Española de Desarrollo Rural	Víctor Ricardo Martínez, proyecto FLIARA: «En el centro de las políticas rurales debería estar el espíritu de innovación»	News	http://www.redr.es/es/cargarAplicacionNoticia.do?identificador=35222
Rural Pact	Rural Pact Community Newsletter - October 2023	Newsletter	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/newsletter-archives/48703
Rural Pact	Policy Forum Report back from the thematic group discussions & stakeholder reactions (28/09/2023)	Video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0-juyGgJGMc
REDPAC	Convocatoria para mujeres innovadoras en la agricultura y las zonas rurales - Proyecto FLIARA	Post	https://redpac.es/anuncio/convocatoria-para-mujeres-innovadoras-en-la-agricultura-y-las-zonas-rurales-proyecto-fliaara
ECOLISE & Communities for Future	November 2023 Newsletter	Newsletter	https://communitiesforfuture.org/civCRM/mailling/view/?id=223
MUNDO RURAL EN POSITIVO (youtube)	Podcast MUNDO RURAL EN POSITIVO - ENTREVISTA FLIARA Michelle Perello - CEO de Consulta Europa	Podcast	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xw4P-8Wrpi0
Fedesiba	Dos convocatorias europeas abiertas	News	https://www.fedesiba.com/noticias/portada/1282-dos-convocatorias-europeas-abiertas-

	para la selección de proyectos innovadores de mujeres y jóvenes.		para-la-seleccion-de-proyectos-innovadores-de-mujeres-y-jovenes.html
Teagasc	Project FLIARA: Teagasc and lead coordinator University of Galway join a range of partners across the EU to bolster female-led innovation in rural areas	News	https://www.teagasc.ie/about/research--innovation/research-publications/tresearch-articles/2023/project-fliara.php
Tresearch V18	Project FLIARA	Magazine	https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2023/TRResearch-Winter-2023.pdf
Mundo RURAL EN POSITIVO	Innovación femenina en la agricultura y las zonas rurales con Michelle Perello de Consulta Europa	PR piece	https://mundoruralenpositivo.com/consulta-europa/?fbclid=IwAR0RixWPVSauo8u1RKIQNi_fVOND_t5J5KQPeYRR58cpg7f1e3xuS5FrcmQ
EU-FarmBook	Celebrating Women in Agriculture: EU-FarmBook wishes Happy International Women's Day	Joint Article	https://welcome.eufarmbook.eu/celebrating-women-in-agriculture-eu-farmbook-wishes-happy-international-womens-day/
transilvaniabusiness.ro	Proiectul FLIARA – Inovația Condusă de Femei în Agricultură și în Zonele Rurale	News	https://www.transilvaniabusiness.ro/2024/03/04/proiectul-fliara-inovatia-condusa-de-femei-in-agricultura-si-in-zonele-rurale/
BUSINESS PRESS AGRICOL	FLIARA: Inovația Condusă de Femei în Agricultură și în Zonele Rurale	News	https://www.businessagricol.ro/fliara-inovatia-condusa-de-femei-in-agricultura-si-in-zonele-rurale/
Gazeta de Agricultura	Proiect european FLIARA: Inovația Condusă de Femei în Agricultură și în Zonele Rurale	News	https://www.gazetadeagricultura.info/dezvoltare-rurala/24512-proiect-european-fliara-inovatia-condusa-de-femei-in-agricultura-si-in-zonele-rurale.html
Cotidianul Agricol	FLIARA: Inovația Condusă de Femei în Agricultură și în Zonele Rurale	News	https://www.cotidianulagricol.ro/fliara-inovatia-condusa-de-femei-in-agricultura-si-in-zonele-rurale/
Rețeaua Rurală	FLIARA – Inovația condusă de femei în agricultură și în	News	https://m.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=pfbid0JiUPvoKFtmxV5uT1XtxLJP4cBeY

Națională - RRN	mediul rural, finanțat prin programul Horizon Europe pentru perioada 2023-2025		y4dauwU3dh7aeFunMmPkpT1AQFnHhbcu96gTVI&id=100080457996606
Rural Pact	EU Rural vision - Rural Pact Community Newsletter - June 2024	Newsletter	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/news/rural-innovation-gets-gender-boost-through-new-community-practice_en
Rural Pact	Rural innovation gets a gender boost through a new Community of Practice	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/news/rural-innovation-gets-gender-boost-through-new-community-practice_en
Rural Pact	FLIARA Community of Practice Launch Event	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/events/fliara-community-practice-launch-event_en
Rural Pact Community Platform	FLIARA Community of Practice Launch Event	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/events/fliara-community-practice-launch-event_en
Communities for Future	Women, farmers and the climate: Join FLIARA's livestream launch	News	https://communitiesforfuture.org/fliara-cop-launch/
Maria Walsh	I joined a panel at the FLIARA Community of Practice (CoP) official launch yesterday to discuss Horizon Europe Projects.	Social Media Post	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mariawalsh_eu_fliara-community-of-practice-galway-ireland-activity-7213920235035205633-Gs9/?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Horizon Magazine	Seeds of change: Women's role in greening European agriculture	News	https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/horizon-magazine/seeds-change-womens-role-greening-european-agriculture?pk_source=x&pk_medium=euscience&pk_campaign=agriculture-environment-science-in-society
Horizon Magazine	Horizon Magazine (July 2024)	Newsletter	https://app.getresponse.com/view.html?x=a62b&m=BRusQO&mc=It&s=B9orSNy&u=yxXvx&z=ECqIhUX&
Horizon Science Blog	Seeds of change: Women's role in greening European agriculture	News	https://horizon.scienceblog.com/2797/seeds-of-change-womens-role-in-greening-european-agriculture/

Horizon Magazine	Seeds of change: Women's role in greening European agriculture	Video	https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=1175029686967805
Horizon Magazine	Seeds of change: Women's role in greening European agriculture	Video	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Bh-f8eTf7nl
Horizon Magazine	Seeds of change: Women's role in greening European agriculture	Video	https://x.com/HorizonMagEU/status/1808428131981635951
Irish Farmers Journal	Agri Careers: FLIARA celebrates rural women innovators	News	https://www3.farmersjournal.ie/careers/education/agri-careers-fliara-celebrates-rural-women-innovators-825940
Horizon Magazine	Horizon Magazine (Weekly newsletter) - 14th July, 2024	Newsletter	https://app.getresponse.com/view.html?x=a62b&m=BR14Jd&mc=It&s=B9orSNy&u=yxXvx&z=Ewm7Gsd&
Tresearch V19	FLIARA champions women's innovations	Magazine	https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2024/TRResearch_Autumn2024.pdf
EIT Food	How to empower women innovators in agrifood? Guidelines for programme design	Report	https://www.eitfood.eu/reports/how-to-empower-women-innovators-in-agrifood-guidelines-for-programme-design
European Research Executive Agency	European Week of Regions and Cities 2024	News	https://rea.ec.europa.eu/events/european-week-regions-and-cities-2024-2024-10-07_en
Wool in School	FLIARA	News	https://woolinschool.com/news/f/fliara
Filozofska fakulteta Univerze v Ljubljani	FLIARA: inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	https://www.ff.uni-lj.si/dogodki/fliara-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-na-podezelju?fbclid=IwY2xjawFac_xleHRuA2FlbQlxMAABHSZbqOMvU_XgEwulz3GYllzQpbkrPslASOn3Jq67QJop8jE2wLLKxNfKw_aem_98v616w056yakkk-eUVYQw
Inu.se	Empowering Women to Lead the Future of Rural Innovation: FLIARA Project Completes Case Studies Across Europe	News	https://lnu.se/en/meet-linnaeus-university/current/news/2024/empowering-women-to-lead-the-future-of-rural-innovation-fliara-project-completes-case-studies-across-europe/

Ministère de l'enseignement supérieur et de la recherche	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas (FLIARA)	News	https://scanr.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/projects/101084234
Geografska širina	Mednarodno srečanje izkustvene skupnosti projekta FLIARA v Ljubljani	News	https://sites.google.com/view/geografskasirina/starej%C5%A1e-%C5%A1tevilke/2024/julij-september#h.f1ezmvnbn4td
Radio Prvi, Od setve do žetve	FLIARA introduction by dr. Barbara Lampič, innovation journey by interviewee Polona Vrinik Karničar	Radio	https://prvi.rtvsl.si/podkast/od-setve-do-zetve/173251261/175066417
Slovenian Rural Development Network	Mednarodno srečanje izkustvene skupnosti projekta FLIARA, ki se osredotoča na inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	http://drustvo-podezelje.si/en/blog/item/1976-mednarodno-srecanje-izkustvene-skupnosti-projekta-fliara-ki-se-osredotoca-na-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-in-na-podezelju
O-STA	Mednarodno srečanje izkustvene skupnosti projekta FLIARA, ki se osredotoča na inovativnost žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju	News	https://o-sta.si/35859/mednarodno-srecanje-izkustvene-skupnosti-projekta-fliara-ki-se-osredotoca-na-inovativnost-zensk-v-kmetijstvu-in-na-podezelju
Kmečki glas	Inovativnosti žensk v kmetijstvu in na podeželju - Pot utirajo prodorne posameznice	News	Printed edition: https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/20241009_Objava-FLIARA_Kmecki-glas_page-0001.jpg
European CAP Network	Innovation and knowledge exchange EIP-AGRI Newsletter: Seeds of change: Women's role in greening European agriculture	Newsletter	https://776c9.r.sp1-brevonet/mk/mr/sh/1t6AVsd2XFnlG8XIZG9sMrEX5664Hs/icyBII9zzER3

REDR	El proyecto europeo FLIARA destaca el empoderamiento femenino en las zonas rurales de España	News	https://www.redr.es/es/noticias/el-proyecto-europeo-fliara-destaca-el-empoderamiento-femenino-en-las-zonas-rurales-de-espana/
Agerpres	Biro Rozalia (UDMR): Suntem o țară pe loc frunțaș la populația în mediul rural; să ne valorizăm femeile	News	https://agerpres.ro/2024/10/17/biro-rozalia-udmr-suntem-o-tara-pe-loc-fruntas-la-populatia-in-mediul-rural-sa-ne-valorizam-femeile--1372443
Spanish National Rural Network	Weekly Newsletter on Rural Areas	Newsletter	https://cdn.mc-weblink.sg-mktg.com/weblink/MTcyOTI1MTQzM3xBV mQ2N2VVaXZlQ1pEb3hHZmtFeC1HZUNH bnZvVjNDdE5Pa095NHhTaXZmSzNwTDIP cWFoM1ZzUTJMbKfYefD0ejQ0dnoxWg4 VwVfVU1kU0NMUFhwY1pFSVZUIFIYm 40S0tCR3ZJdFpQdFg3Xzc3MFVRNfpZW W0xeENJRXJBMHFIRlowTEhRZ2QtclI2eW hpVE9XYVpfYkNVS25BNEZkc2lxVGRwYk 9xUGYyZ2FTYmhJc0Y3OWRoQmdCOVR 1aG5kWG0tbV9ueC1EOEV4TIhDVGRzT1J PVXVNYmk1aDdJaDNaRVE0SVFTZ0NrY1 ZWM0x5Zk40YXg4TC1xY19UR3RGSVBpM TUxM1NVcGlhb1FTeG5BZlFzYS1rSTdoM WVuWjNpaU1OSDICYTVsVIJldEFOdXZlV Eo3NXFNamhtU0pkMmY3SnBrd0puby1qd FNHcy1udkZROhd6VHizWEZoR2NIN281 RfK0R2RDaxJ5TTRuQmxkOHgyU3JHUjc 5UHziWIVUaDZZcWdIMzdPQmVwaENZbl NIUGICQUdKVWp2MndDSUpnODJnc21u MHhVSkhSUU5zODdVc05QUmpjdWJ8OT u4K5qZ8tV L5v4YUFH6F9GzBfjNHtsP78x aNL4pXM=?fbclid=IwY2xjawF RitleHRuA2 F1bQlxMAABHd2EftKSb5rWMg LZf tofs2LZ aph4w4zu940OeSU50IQPhUpFFVdScnDC w aem LCw2ilkkfHttuvdINRkVw
CREA Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	Evento di networking AKIS in action: l'innovazione in agricoltura guidata dalle donne	News	https://www.crea.gov.it/web/politiche-e-bioeconomia/-/evento-di-networking-akis-in-action-sull-innovazione-guidata-dalle-donne
European CAP Network	New study examines policy and legal frameworks for	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/news/new-study-examines-policy-and-legal-frameworks-female-led-rural-innovation_en

	female-led rural innovation		
UNICAL	FLIARA Community of Practice - Evento dedicato alle donne innovatrici in agricoltura e nelle aree rurali, a cura del DISPES	News	https://www.unical.it/contents/calendars/view/eventi-unical/2969/
AgriLand	Women farming in the EU face 'issues' with finance access – Roche	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/women-farming-in-the-eu-face-issues-with-finance-access-roche/
APIGRANCA	Natalia Luis, en Italia como embajadora de FLIARA	News	https://apigranca.es/natalia-luis-en-italia-como-embajadora-de-fliara
Consulta Europa	FLIARA's 3rd Community of Practice in Italy Highlights the Role of Women in Rural Innovation	News	https://consulta-europa.com/fliara-cop-italy-rural-women/
Consulta Europa	FLIARA en Italia pone en valor el papel de las mujeres en la innovación rural	News	https://consulta-europa.com/es/fliara-en-italia-pone-en-valor-el-papel-de-las-mujeres-en-la-innovacion-rural/
AgriLand	EU Commission in Dublin to celebrate women in agri	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/panel-discussion-to-highlight-women-in-farming/
Irish Farmel Journal	Tag team: Ursula Kelly challenges the status quo	News	https://www.farmersjournal.ie/life/features/tag-team-ursula-kelly-challenges-the-status-quo-856091
EU Rural Pact	Empowering rural communities: gender equality and innovation in action	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/events/empowering-rural-communities-gender-equality-and-innovation-action_en
EU Rural Pact	Rural Pact Community Newsletter - February 2025	Newsletter	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/agri/newsletter-archives/60620
AgriLand	Role of women in Irish agriculture celebrated at Dublin event	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/role-of-women-in-irish-agriculture-celebrated-at-dublin-event/

Irish Farmel Journal	Women are farming's 'secret weapon' for the future	News	https://www.farmersjournal.ie/news/news/women-are-farming-s-secret-weapon-for-the-future-858929
EUCAPNE TWORK	Empowering Rural Communities: Gender Equality and Innovation in Action	News	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/events/empowering-rural-communities-gender-equality-and-innovation-action_en
EUFarmBook	Happy International Women's Day	News	https://welcome.eufarmbook.eu/happy-international-womens-day/
Ministrstvo za kmetijstvo, gozdarstvo in prehrano	Odprtje razstave Inovativne zgodbe žensk s podeželja	News	https://www.gov.si/novice/2025-03-14-odprtje-razstave-inovativne-zgodbe-zensk-s-podezelja/
MOREL Press Agency	Odprtje razstave inovativne zgodbe žensk s podeželja	News	https://www.morel.si/Notranja_politika/odprtje-razstave-inovativne-zgodbe-zensk-s-podezelja/
AgriLand	AgriLand partners with Agri Insider for National Dairy Awards	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/agriland-partners-with-agri-insider-for-national-dairy-awards/
AgriLand	FLIARA: Challenging stereotypes about women in farming	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/fliara-challenging-stereotypes-about-women-in-farming/
AEIDL	Empowering Rural Communities: Gender Equality and Innovation in Action	News	https://www.aeidl.eu/event/empowering-rural-communities-gender-equality-and-innovation-in-action/
CAP Network Ireland	FLIARA - Empowering Rural Communities: Gender Equality and Innovation in Action	News	https://capnetworkireland.eu/event/empowering-rural-communities-gender-equality-and-innovation-in-action/
GRANULAR	Empowering Rural Communities: Gender Equality and Innovation in Action	News	https://www.ruralgranular.eu/event/empowering-rural-communities-gender-equality-and-innovation-in-action/
GRASS CEILING	WHAT EXPERTS SAY: Interview to Dr. Maura Farrell	News	https://www.grassceiling.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/Grass-Ceiling-Interview-Maura-Farrell_compressed.pdf

European Landowners' Organization	Women for the Future of Agriculture 2025	Publication	https://europeanlandowners.org/publication/women-for-the-future-of-agriculture-2025/
SÜDWEST PRESSE	Das FLIARA-Projekt der EU: Frauen, die etwas ins Rollen bringen	News	https://www.swp.de/lokales/gaildorf/das-fliara-projekt-der-eu-frauen-die-etwas-ins-rollen-bringen-77377723.html
SWIFT Project	Academia, policymakers and the farming sector meet to discuss gender equality	News	https://swiftproject.eu/2025/05/08/academia-policymakers-farming-discuss-gender-equality/
Lokaltidningen Växjö	De vill lyfta kvinnligt företagande på Landsbygden	News	https://lokaltidningen-vaxjoalvesta.prenly.com/p/lokaltidningen-vaxjo-alvesta/2025-05-10/r/15/28/4341/1905903
Elard	ELARD Newsletter - June 2025 - 🌐 Multi-lingual	Newsletter	https://mailchi.mp/ffe8553f7d61/t3uhuptmfr-6742685?e=5ad4a744d1
Thünen Working Paper	Europäische Innovationspartnerschaft für Produktivität und Nachhaltigkeit in der Landwirtschaft (EIP-Agri) (EL-0702)	Article	https://www.thuenen.de/media/publikationen/thuenen-workingpaper/ThuenenWorkingPaper_265.pdf
Raidió Teilifís Éireann, Ireland's National Public Service Media	Today With Claire Byrne Tuesday 10 June 2025	Radio	https://www.rte.ie/radio/radio1/today-with-claire-byrne/2025/0610/1517681-today-with-claire-byrne-tuesday-10-june-2025/
Raidió Teilifís Éireann, Ireland's National Public Service Media	Competitive sheep shearing	Radio	https://www.rte.ie/radio/radio1/clips/22519364/
Barometern / Oskarsha	Malin is passionate about female leaders – brought	News	https://www.barometern.se/2025-06-26/malin-brinner-for-kvinnliga-ledare-tog-innovatorer-fran-hela-europa-till-odevata/

mns-Tidningen	innovators from all over Europe to Ödevata		
Kalmar.nu	Malin brinner för kvinnliga ledare – tog innovatörer från hela Europa till Ödevata	News	https://kalmar.nu/malin-brinner-for-kvinnliga-ledare-tog-innovatorer-fran-hela-europa-till-odevata/
Aktualitet	Malin brinner för kvinnliga ledare – tog innovatörer från hela Europa till Ödevata	News	https://www.aktualitet.se/?a=d3d3LmJhcm9tZXRlcm4uc2UvYXJ0aWt0bC9tYWxpbi1icmlubmVyLWZvci1rdmlubmxpZ2EtbGVkYXJLLXRvZy1pbm5vdmF0b3Jlci1mcmFuLWlhbG9tZXVyb3BhLXRpbGwtb2RldmF0YS8=
EU Agenda	Women leading rural innovation: From vision to action	News	https://euagenda.eu/events/2025/10/17/women-leading-rural-innovation-from-vision-to-action
Agenda ONekin!	Women leading rural innovation: From vision to action	News	https://onekin.eus/ekitaldia/women-leading-rural-innovation-from-vision-to-action/
Rural Pact Community Platform	Women leading rural innovation: From vision to action	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/events/women-leading-rural-innovation-vision-action_en
EUCAPNE NETWORK	Women leading rural innovation: From vision to action	News	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/events/women-leading-rural-innovation-vision-action_en
CAP Network Ireland	FLIARA Final Conference – Women Leading Rural Innovation: From Vision to Action	News	https://capnetworkireland.eu/event/fliara-final-conference-women-leading-rural-innovation-from-vision-to-action/
European Committee of the Regions	FLIARA Final Conference: Women Leading Rural Innovation: From Vision to Action	News	https://cor.europa.eu/en/plenaries-events/fliara-final-conference-women-leading-rural-innovation-vision-action
ELARD	Meet the FLIARA Ambassadors: Women Leading Innovation in Rural Europe	News	https://elard.eu/meet-the-fliara-ambassadors/

Horizon Europe Ireland	FLIARA: Challenging gender stereotypes around farm and rural innovation	News	https://horizoneurope.ie/global-challenges-european-industrial-competitiveness/food-bioeconomy-natural-resources-agriculture-and-environment/challenging-gender-stereotypes-around-farm-and-rural-innovation
GRANULAR	Women Leading Rural Innovation: From Vision to Action	News	https://www.ruralgranular.eu/event/women-leading-rural-innovation-from-vision-to-action/
Plataforma AKIS	Women leading rural innovation: from vision to action	News	https://akisplataforma.es/en/events/women-leading-rural-innovation-vision-action
Netzwerk Zukunftsräum Land	17. Oktober 2025 - FLIARA Final Conference Live Stream	News	https://www.zukunftsraumland.at/termine/fliara-final-conference-live-stream/
EU4Advice	EU4Advice at the FLIARA Project Final Conference	News	https://eu4advice.eu/eu4advice-at-the-fliara-project-final-conference/
Lapuan Sanomat	Eläinavusteisuus malliksi Eurooppaan	News	https://fliara.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/magazineFLIARA FIN.jpg
Limerick City Community Radio	Business Focus - October 22nd, 2025	Podcast	https://www.mixcloud.com/LCCR/business-focus-october-22nd-2025/
Rural Pact Community Platform	Empowering rural women: FLIARA project conference calls for inclusive innovation and policy change	News	https://ruralpact.rural-vision.europa.eu/news/empowering-rural-women-fliara-project-conference-calls-inclusive-innovation-and-policy-change_en
Teagasc	Strengthening women-led innovation in farming and rural areas	News	https://teagasc.ie/news-events/daily/strengthening-women-led-innovation-in-farming-and-rural-areas/
Agriland	We can't keep talking about farmers as if we mean men'	News	https://www.agriland.ie/farming-news/we-cant-keep-talking-about-farmers-as-if-we-mean-men/
Siikajokilaakso	Maaseudun naisyrittäjä kohtaa	News	https://www.siikajokilaakso.fi/maaseudun-naisyrittaja-kohtaa-samat-haasteet-kaiki/12377634

	samat haasteet kaikilla Euroopan laidoilla		
Jönköpings-Posten	Debatt - Detta riskeras när lokala förskolor läggs ned	News	https://www.jp.se/2025-11-28/detta-riskeras-nar-lokala-forskolor-laggs-ned/
Linnaeus University	National FLIARA symposium was held at Linnaeus University	News	https://lnu.se/en/meet-linnaeus-university/current/news/2025/FLIARA-symposium-at-lnu/
HNEE Newsletter	Newsletter für Forschung und Transfer an der HNEE: SCIENCE MATTERS	Newsletter	https://t798feb28.emailsys1a.net/ mailing/1/8403512/23683901/98fb23f802/index.html

Table 62. FLIARA Media Clipping

ANNEX 2 – ATTENDANCE TO EVENTS

Who attended	Type of event	Title of the event	Date	Location	Target group
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	Food Vision 2030 - A World Leader in Sustainable Food Systems	01/02/2023	Dublin, Ireland	Policy Makers
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Meeting	The 2nd Meeting of the 6th Mandate of SCAR AKIS	12-13/04/2023	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Forum	The European Startup Village Forum	28/02/2023	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community
Annie Roos and Helene Ahl (LNU and HLK)	Conference	Rural Pact Conference	04/05/2023	Uppsala, Sweden	Industry
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Event	President of Ireland's Summer Garden Party	21/06/2023	Galway, Ireland	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell, Louise Weir, Elena Herrera, Víctor Martínez (Galway and CE)	Webinar	Tools4CAP first Info Session	26/06/2026	Online	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell - Louise Weir (Galway)	Webinar	Gender and Agroecology Webinar	05/07/2023	Online	Scientific Community

Maura Farrell, Louise Weir (Galway) - Silvia Sivini, Irene Leonardelli (UNICAL)	Congress	XXIXth European Society for Rural Sociology Congress Crises and the futures of rural areas. WG Sessions WG 7: Rural Quality of Life: Gender and other perspectives	3- 7/07/2023	L'Institut Agro Rennes- Angers, Rennes, France	Scientific Community
Anastasia Oprea (ECOLISE)	Event	2023 European Ecovillage Gathering	12- 17/07/2023	Germany	Stakeholde rs
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Sister Project Event	GRASS CEILING - Show case event in Brussels 2023	12- 14/09/2023	Brussels	Scientific Community
Tara Farrell, Niamh McGuinness (LWL and Galway)	Sister Project Event	University of Galway's Rural Studies Centre Visit	13/09/2023	Galway, Ireland	Scientific Community
Hannu I. Heikkinen, Élise Lépy (OULU)	Sister Project Event	RURACTIVE KICK OFF MEETING	13- 15/09/2023	Bologna	Scientific Community
Niamh Nolan (Galway)	Fair	Ireland's National Ploughing Championships	19 - 21/09/2023	Ireland	Civil Society
Maura Farrell and Louise Weir (Galway)	Forum	Shaping the future of rural areas	27- 29/09/2023	Guadalajar a, Spain	Scientific Community
Louise Weir (Galway)	Webinar	Presentation at INSITU Webinar Series	30/10/2023	online	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Online Conference	RENOVERTY - Conference	31/10/2024	online	Scientific Community

Annie Roos and Helene Ahl (LNU and HLK)	Conference	Rural areas and regions in transition: A conference for rural and regional researchers in Sweden	08-09/11/2023	Stockholm, Sweden	Scientific Community
Víctor Ricardo Martínez, Beatrice Avagnina (CE)	Workshops	Erasmus+ EUROPE Project: Addressing challenges experienced by communities in remote and rural areas.	22-23/11/2023	Gran Canaria, Spain	Stakeholders
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	Duhallow Farming for Blue Dot Catchments EIP – End of Project Conference	07/12/2023	Cork, Ireland	Stakeholders
Louise Weir, Maura Farrell, Tuomas Kuhmonen, Belyta Tembo (Galway and UTU)	Conference	2023 European LEADER Congress in Brussels	18-19/12/2023	Brussels, Belgium	Stakeholders
Susanne von Münchhausen (HNEE)	Conference	BIOFACH & VIVANESS 2024	13-16/02/2024	Nuremberg, Germany	Scientific Community
Anastasia Oprea (ECOLISE)	CfF session	Women's leadership in regenerative intentional communities	07/03/2024	Online	Stakeholders
Louise Weir, Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	EU CAP Network workshop 'Women-led innovations in agriculture and rural areas'	17/04/2024	Krakow, Poland	Advisors, researchers, representatives from farmers association

					s, chambers of agriculture, industry, managing bodies, local authorities, press, etc. from across Europe.
Silvia Sivini, Irene Leonardelli (UNICAL)	Conference	VII AGROMIG International Seminar "Migrations, Agrifood and Rural Change"	23- 24/05/2024	Rende, Calabria, Italy	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	A Shared Response To A Shared Responsibility - Mary Robinson Climate Conference	05- 06/06/2024	Ballina, Ireland	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell, Aisling Murtagh and Louise Weir (Galway)	Conference	North Atlantic Forum Conference	20/06/2024	Letterfrack, Ireland	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell, Aisling Murtagh and Louise Weir (Galway)	Conference	35th International Geographical Congress – Dublin 2024	29/08/24	Dublin, Ireland	Scientific Community
Milada Šťastná, Antonín Vaishar, Tuomas Kuhmonen and Belyta Tembo (MENDELU and UTU)	Conference	EURORURAL '24 - European Countryside and De-Globalization	02- 05/09/2024	Brno, Czechia	Scientific Community

Louise Weir, Maura Farrell, Tuomas Kuhmonen, Silvia Silvini, Willem Korthals Atles (Galway, UTU, UNICAL and TU Delft)	Meeting	Lunchtime Debate and Policy Discussion with the European Commission	01/10/2024	Online	Policy Makers
Willem Korthals Altes, Gerdy Verschuure -Stuip, Vitnarae Kang (TU Delft)	Meeting	Introductory Meeting with the Working Group Women in Agrifood of the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Food Security and Nature in the Netherlands.	02/10/2024	The Netherlands	Policy Makers
Susanne von Münchhausen, Maura Farrell, Louise Weir (HNEE and Galway)	Meeting	SCAR meeting AKIS	09/10/2024	Online	Policy Makers

Maura Farrell, Louise Weir, Víctor R. Martínez (Galway and CE)	Webinar	Reducing women's inequalities in Agricultural Areas: the role of digitalisation	22/10/2024	Online	Policy Makers
Annie Roos (LNU)	Workshop	Forskarsmedja Uppdrag landsbygd: tema Kommersiell service, företagande och näringsliv (Research workshop Uppdrag Landsbygd: theme Commercial service, entrepreneurship and business)	25/10/2024	Online	Policy Makers
Maura Farrell, Louise Weir, Víctor R. Martínez (Galway and CE)	Webinar	AKIS in Action: Strengthening AKIS through women-led innovation	19/11/2024	Online	Policy Makers
Milada Šťastná, Antonín Vaishar, Michaela Tichá, Jan Zloch (MENDELU)	Conference	30th International Geographical Conference	20/11 - 22/11/2025	Nitra, Slovakia	Scientific Community

Aisling Murtagh (Galway)	Webinar	SERIGO Community of Practice launch webinar	21/11/2024	Online	Researchers
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	EIT Women In Agrifood Stories 2024	04/12/2024	Lisbon, Portugal	Decision-makers
Louise Weir, Víctor R. Martínez (Galway and CE)	Webinar	Integrating a Feminist Perspective in Research Projects	12/12/2024	Online	Decision-makers
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Presentation of the FLIARA Project	European Parliament Session	12/12/2024	Brussels, Belgium	Decision-makers
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Presentation of the FLIARA Project	European Parliament's Regional Development (REGI) Committee visit	25/02/2025	Galway, Ireland	Decision-makers
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Presentation of the FLIARA Project	European Commission Representation in Ireland	03/04/2025	Dublin, Ireland	Policy Makers
Felicia Tulder (HNEE)	Presentation of the FLIARA Project	Female pioneers in agriculture	03/06/2025	Berlin, Germany	Scientific Community
UL Team	Exhibition	Innovative power of women in the countryside	18/03/2025	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Decision-makers
Maura Farrell, Aisling Murtagh and Louise Weir (Galway)	Policy Forum	GRASS CEILING European Policy Forum Session	24/03/2025	Online	Policy Makers
Silvia Sivini and Irene Leonardelli (UNICAL)	Conference	Conoscenza, riconoscimento, gratitudine . Le donne nelle aree Fragili	28-29/03/2025	Rovigo, Italy	Scientific Community

Annie Roos, Helene Ahl (LNU and HLK)	Conference	10th Annual Entrepreneurship as Practice Conference	09/04-11/04/2025	Jönköping, Sweden	Scientific Community
Annie Roos (LNU)	Workshop	Det uppfinningsrika Småland	16/05/2025	Växjö, Sweden	Industry
Aisling Murtagh (Galway)	Conference	Irish Sociology Conference 2025	05/08/2025	Cork, Ireland	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Policy Forum	ATHENA Equality Policy Event at the European Parliament	13/05/2025	Brussels, Belgium	Policy Makers
Maura Farrell, Anne Kinsella (Galway and Teagasc)	Festival	European and Connacht Sheep Shearing AND WOOLHANDLING Championships	30/05 to 01/06/2025	Galway, Ireland	General Public
Aisling Murtagh (Galway)	Conference	22nd annual Rural Entrepreneurship Conference	03/06 to 05/06/2025	Bangor, Wales	Scientific Community
Felicia van Tulder (HNEE)	Exhibition	German Organic Field Days 2025	18/06 to 19/06/25	Saxony, Germany	General Public
Maura Farrell, Sara Mikolič, Silvia Sivini and Annamaria Vitale (Galway, UNICAL and UL)	Conference	30th European Society for Rural Sociology Congress	07/07 to 11/07	Rīga, Latvia	Scientific Community
Anastasia Oprea, Laura Incze (ECOLISE and ELARD)	Festival	European Ecovillage Gathering 2025	12/08 to 17/08	Lengyeltóti, Hungary	Civil Society

UL Team	Exhibition	European Researchers Night Event	02/09/2025	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Civil Society
Anastasia Oprea, Laura Incze (ECOLISE and ELARD)	Conference	Entrepreneurial opportunities for rural women through LEADER	04/09/2025	Târgu Mureș, Romania	Scientific Community
Annie Roos (LNU)	Workshop	Samverkansforum Blekinge	05/09/2025	Online	Industry
Annie Roos (LNU)	Workshop	Träffpunkt Ryssby	08/09/2025	Ryssby, Sweden	Civil Society
Maura Farrell, Aisling Murtagh (Galway)	Conference	National Ploughing Championships: Breaking Ground – Female Leaders in Agriculture	17/09/2025	Screggan, Ireland	Civil Society
Louise Weir (Galway)	Conference	Rural Pact Conference: 'From vision to action: Empowering rural areas for the future'	16/09 to 17/09	Kortrijk/Coutrai, Belgium	Scientific Community
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	AGRIGEP Final Conference	25/09/2025	Prague, Czech Republic	Scientific Community
Galway, UTU, CE, Teagasc, OULU, UL, LNU, TU Delft, MENDELU, HNEE, UNICAL and LWL	Networking Event	Mental Health & Farming – European Parliament	16/10/2025	Brussels, Belgium	Women Innovators
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	6th European Rural Parliament	20/10 - 23/10/2025	Scotland, UK	Scientific Community
Gerdy Verschuure -Stuip, Willem Korthals	Conference	Cultivating Change: Promoting equal opportunities in	27/10/2025	Paris, France	Policy Makers

Altes, Anne Kinsella (TU Delft and Teagasc)		food systems - OECD			
Anastasia Oprea, Laura Incze (ECOLISE, ELARD)	Policy Event	From Innovation to Political Action – The Voice of Rural Women	30/10/2025	Saschiz, Mureş County, Romania	Policy Makers
Felicia van Tulder (HNEE)	Workshop	FLINTA Science Slam Eberswalde	05/11/2025	Eberswalde, Germany	Scientific Community
Milada Šťastná, Antonín Vaishar, Michaela Tichá, Jan Zloch (MENDELU)	Conference	Expert seminar - Women in the Agri-Sector – Inspiration, Innovation, Impact (Institute of Knowledge-based Agriculture and Innovation)	11/11/2025	Nitra, Slovakia	Scientific Community
Silvia Sivini (UNICAL)	Conference	XIII Edizione Giornate della Soft Economy	20-22/11/2025	Treia, Italy	Civil Society
Annie Roos, Rafael Sales (LNU)	Conference	Jordbruksekonomisk konferens 2025	02/12/2025	Uppsala, Sweden	Industry
Maura Farrell (Galway)	Conference	Final Showcase Event – GRASS CEILING Project	04/12/2025	Brussels, Belgium	Scientific Community
Víctor Ricardo Martínez, Silvia Pérez Palomo (CE)	Exhibition	Accelerating Innovation Through Women Leadership	04/12/2025	Warsaw, Poland	Women Innovators
Susanne von Münchhausen (HNEE)	Conference	„Starke Frauen – starke Landwirtschaft“ at the German Federal Ministry for Agriculture	03/03/2026	Berlin, Germany	Policy Makers

Table 63. FLIARA Participation in events

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